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Where do the archival clues lead us? Is Karol Wojtyła a Doctor of the Church?

“Wojtyła Studies” has published several texts reporting on the latest discoveries in archival research on Karol Wojtyła’s work.¹ Continuing this theme, we would like to present further significant discoveries of materials of whose existence we were previously unaware, and which – like the previous ones – significantly enrich our knowledge of Karol Wojtyła’s thought.

Preserved in various manuscripts and typescripts, we have recently uncovered two important texts which represent a significant part of Karol Wojtyła’s significant contribution to the development of ethics and moral theology.

Both texts can likely be dated to the 1950s or 1960s, and further research will allow us to determine in greater detail the context in which these materials were created.

Regarding moral theology, the Archives of the Metropolitan Curia have unearthed the text “Moral Theology,” a quasi-textbook in which Wojtyła expounds on the most important issues of moral theology. The list of materials below is presented according to the archival reference numbers:

1. AKKW C II² 7/102 [Moral Theology – text without chapter VI, typescript]
2. AKKW C II 7/102a [Moral Theology – rough draft of manuscript]
3. AKKW C II 7/103 [Moral Theology – full text without p. 54, manuscript]
4. AKKW C II 7/103a [Moral Theology, manuscript, full text, pp. 214]

The second text is a study on ethics and was also found in the archives of the Metropolitan Curia in Krakow. Its origins also suggest the 1950s or 1960s. Below is a list of materials:

1. AKKW C II 7/104 [Ethics [study], manuscript]

A related text, but different in content:

1. AKKW C II 22/181 [Course for aspirants. Ethics, manuscript].

¹ Cf. K. Petryszak, *The Origins of Karol Wojtyła’s Philosophical Anthropology as Recorded in Coll.[atio] and Corr.[igenda] Included in the Notes for his Habilitation Thesis*. „Wojtyła Studies” Vol. 1, No. 1 (2024), 110-125; K. Petryszak, *The First Archival Material Presented in „Wojtyła Studies” – Introduction*. „Wojtyła Studies” Vol. 1, No. 2 (2024), 2-6; K. Petryszak, *Introduction to the Series of Articles in the Debate after the Publication of „Person and Act”*. „Wojtyła Studies” Vol. 2, No. 1 (2025), 2-4.

² The notation AKKW stands for: Archiwum Kardynała Karola Wojtyły (Archives of Cardinal Karol Wojtyła). The notation “CII” is the designation of the collection of philosophical materials written by Wojtyła and is part of AKKW.

The previously unknown texts by Wojtyła mentioned above allow us to conclude that Wojtyła's thought is not limited to texts that are more widely known and published. However, its depth and consistency with the Church's teaching are revealed and expanded through subsequent archival discoveries. Moreover, not only is this unanimity with the teaching of the Church noticeable, but also a deepening of reflection and a striving to uncover new aspects of the Church's teaching. This primarily concerns teaching about the human being and love.

The materials mentioned above – as well as those previously announced and, in some cases, even those already published as part of the Polish critical edition of Karol Wojtyła's philosophical works³ – after analysis and being placed in a broader context, i.e., in relation to later materials and the philosophical (primarily ethical and anthropological) themes present in John Paul II's papal teaching, allow us to propose the following thesis: Due to his contribution to the development of Catholic thought, Karol Wojtyła deserves to be included among the Doctors of the Church. Such a proposal is not a new initiative; it has been voiced by many Catholic thinkers and theologians, who provided a number of strong arguments supporting it.⁴

He not only deserves but – as we will demonstrate shortly – also meets the necessary conditions for becoming a Doctor of the Church.

The title of Doctor of the Church may be awarded to anyone who has made a significant contribution to deepening the understanding of the mystery of God and has significantly increased the richness of Christian experience. In the case of Karol Wojtyła, these conditions are met. The main orientation of Wojtyła's thought lies in the personal relationship between man and God, and between man and man in the context of the (man–man) relationship with God. This is clearly demonstrated by his fundamental study, "Love and Responsibility," as well as the materials we have already mentioned in "Wojtyła Studies," and those recalled in this text. Secondly, if considered outside the context of placing man and his experience in relationship to a personal God, Wojtyła's second fundamental work, "The Person and Act," is incomplete. If this kind of incompleteness is valid in relation to his famous work, so it is also valid in relation to his subsidiary works, or those just discovered. No less importantly, the substratum against which Wojtyła presents his deepened understanding of the rich Christian experience is revealed.

³ Cf. K. Wojtyła, *Dzieła filozoficzne*, vol. I-II (Kraków: WN UPJPII, 2024-2025).

⁴ E.g. see A. Napiórkowski, P. Wachoń, *Will St. Faustina and St. John Paul II Become Doctors of the Church? Polish Saints and Apostles of Divine Mercy* (Kraków: Klasztor Ojców Paulinów, 2017); G. Weigel, "Pope St. John Paul II, Doctor of the Church?" *First Things* April 2, 2025.

This deserves all the more attention because he drew inspiration from and significantly expanded upon the thought of previous scholars, including the Doctor of Grace (*Doctor Gratiae*, St. Augustine), the Angelic Doctor (*Doctor Angelicus*, St. Thomas Aquinas), and the Mystical Doctor (*Doctor Mysticus*, St. John of the Cross). He not only developed and deepened their thought, thanks to which they were included among the Doctors of the Church, but also harmonized it and created a new way of understanding the human being and the human being in relation to God.

The argument outlined above contains a response to a possible objection concerning not so much Wojtyła's fulfillment of all the conditions necessary for being counted among the Doctors of the Church, but the name of a potential new Doctor of the Church. Shouldn't the name of this – hopefully – future proclaimed Doctor be John Paul II, rather than Karol Wojtyła? After all, in 2019, thanks to the efforts of the Polish episcopate, supported by Cardinal Stanisław Dziwisz, a request was submitted to His Holiness Pope Francis I to recognize John Paul II as a Doctor of the Church. So, why do we want to split hairs and propose a new proposal instead pursuing an existing initiative?

Let us expound on the arguments that allow us to understand the perspective proposed here. A broader outlook on John Paul II plays a significant role here, including his pre-papal philosophical and theological activities and resulting achievements.

First and foremost, thorough analyses of Karol Wojtyła's philosophical and theological texts – starting from the mid-1940s – and newly discovered archival materials allows us to postulate that every significant innovation proposed by John Paul II in papal teaching was in fact developed in the pre-papal period.

Furthermore, considering the way in which the official content of papal teaching was edited, one can presume that some formulations (perhaps even key ones) were supplemented, refined, or “polished” by the editors of papal documents. This does not mean changing the essence of John Paul II's thought. However, it prevents the precise determination of authorship by the signed author, as is the case with Karol Wojtyła's texts. This argument is secondary but still important.

Finally, the third argument is that Karol Wojtyła and John Paul II are the same person. This is not an obvious statement in the context of discussions centered on the continuity of the subject in which Wojtyła's thought participated and continues to participate. From this perspective, therefore, it is irrelevant whether the proposal to elevate Karol Wojtyła or John Paul II to the rank of Doctors of the Church is justified because both names concern the same person,

the same subject. Regardless, given that, while maintaining the continuity of the subject, this subject developed his most important theses as Karol Wojtyła, bringing a better understanding of man himself and man in relationship to other persons (including the Divine Persons). These resonated strongly only in papal teaching; it follows that we should focus on the period in which these ideas arose, not on the period of their resonance.

Karol Wojtyła made significant contributions in three philosophical and theological fields: ethics/moral theology, anthropology, and the closely related study of the human person. The person and the person in relationship with others, as we have already mentioned in this text, is at the heart of Wojtyła's philosophy and theology. All his efforts in various fields indicate that emphasizing the personal nature of man's relationship with himself, with others, and with God has always been the goal of Karol Wojtyła's thought. The introduction and development of this perspective ultimately led the Church's teaching down a more personalistic path, helping to advance our understanding of the mystery of participation in the communion of persons, as well as the relationship between persons and Persons. However, all of this was the original thought of Karol Wojtyła, who, as John Paul II, drew on the resources already developed by Karol Wojtyła.

For this reason, it may be tentatively proposed that official efforts be made to include Karol Wojtyła, rather than John Paul II (or Karol Wojtyła/John Paul II), among the Doctors of the Church under the title *Doctor Humanus* or *Doctor Personalis*.

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**The Concept of Philosophical Anthropology in the Thinking of Cardinal Karol Wojtyła
(An Attempted Interpretation Based on the Study *Person and Act*)¹**

Fr. Marian Jaworski

translated by Sydney Sadowski²

“The main slogan repeatedly uttered by Husserl and his colleagues in Göttingen in the first decade of the 20th century was: back to the work!” (R. Ingarden).

As the main slogan in this case we say here: back to the work as the basic source of its understanding.

I. Preliminary Assumptions

1. The Question of the Primacy of Being in St. Thomas Aquinas and the Field of the Philosophy of Being

The concept of being in St. Thomas, as we know, is an analogical concept, and above all it is an analogy of proper proportionality. Closely related to this is the questions of what constitutes the principal analogy, that is, what being is in the primary sense (*per prius*), and whether there is only one type of primary being, or whether there are different “types” of primary being and what they

¹ Note: This text was originally published as: “Koncepcja antropologii filozoficznej w ujęciu kardynała Karola Wojtyły (Próba odczytania w oparciu o studium *Osoba i czyn*),” *Analecta Cracoviensia* Vol. 5 (1973), 91-106. The original article can be found at: <https://czasopisma.upjp2.edu.pl/analectacracoviensia/issue/view/214>. The text used by author was the 1969 Polish edition: K. Wojtyła, *Osoba i czyn* (Kraków: Polskie Towarzystwo Teologiczne, 1969). The translation used for this text were taken from Karol Wojtyła, *Person and Act and Related Essays*. “The English Critical Edition of the Works of Karol Wojtyła/John Paul II,” Vol. I, ed. Antonio Lopez, trans. by G. Ignatik (Washington D.C.: The Catholic University of America Press, 2021). Editorial additions to the translation are explained or noted by a footnote.

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are. This issue, as can easily be seen, is fundamental to all philosophy of being. It is impossible to develop it further here. Let us recall that the order of human knowledge of being is, according to St. Thomas, opposite of the primacy of being in itself. That which is being *prius quoad nos* is not being *prius in se*. The concept of substantial being is given us through accidental being and we arrive at the concept of spiritual substances and God through material substances.

The order of cognition of different “kinds” of being determines the fields of philosophical knowledge. First of all, we must distinguish between the philosophical knowledge of material being and the philosophical knowledge of non-material being, meta-physics (divine knowledge, first philosophy).

Both orders of knowledge have, according to the thinking of St. Thomas, their own proper objects and distinct methods.³ There is also a connection between them, despite their distinctiveness. This relationship is bilateral. Philosophical knowledge of the world of material substances finds its end, as we have already noted above, in non-material beings (*substantiae separatae*). Philosophical knowledge of non-material beings, as those that are *magis entia* and thus possess a greater degree of universality, allows us to consider being as being, and in this light all beings that in some way participate in them.⁴ However, this type of procedure (considering different “kinds” of being in the light of the general theory of being) is justified and possible after their existence has been established and adequate knowledge has been obtained.⁵ (Otherwise, the general theory of material existence would be “metaphysics,” as it is in materialism, in the sense of a general theory of existence.)

2. EXPERIENCE AS A SOURCE OF PHILOSOPHICAL KNOWLEDGE

Another fundamental thesis, which is closely related to what has been said above, is the acceptance of experience as a source of knowledge in the thought of St. Thomas. Experience, of course, can concern entities that are directly given to us, that is, material entities. This does not mean, however,

³ I write more about this in the article: “Próba reinterpretacji punktu wyjścia dowodów istnienia Boga,” in: *Studia z filozofii Boga*, Vol. II, Warsaw 1973.

⁴ See: *In Boetii de Trinitate*, Lect. II, qu. II, a. 1; Lect. II, qu. I, a. 4, ad 6.

⁵ J. Kalinowski, referring to the position of L. B. Geiger, states, among other things: “After all, to claim, for example, that being is not necessarily material, one must first prove, if not that God exists, then at least that the human soul is immortal. And in order to maintain that being can be accidental or necessary, one must inevitably prove the existence of God.” “Ontologia czy aitiologia,” *Znak* 111 (1963), 1070 – M.A. Krąpiec thinks differently, “O rozumienie metafizyki,” *Znak* 111, 1082.

that it is purely sensual, as extreme empiricists maintain. On the contrary, the unity of the cognitive act in man excludes this kind of conception of human experience.⁶

Contemporary philosophical trends,⁷ which are increasingly breaking away from the rationalist concept of philosophy, increasingly emphasize the necessity of accepting experience as the source of all philosophical knowledge. The development of an adequate theory of experience and its various varieties is still an open problem.⁸

In the light of these assumptions, which we consider to be correct, we would now like to investigate Cardinal Wojtyła's study *Person and Act*. As can be concluded from what has been said, we are not concerned with the validity of the substantive solutions proposed by him, but with the philosophical character of the work itself.

II. PHILOSOPHICAL ANTHROPOLOGY FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF THE PHILOSOPHY OF BEING

The subject of analysis in the book *Person and Action* is the “*study [of] the act that reveals the person; ... a study of the person through the act.*”⁹ The goal that the author strives for above all is “an understanding of the human person for his own sake” (p. 593). Similarly on page 105 “to understand man precisely as a person. This is the proper end of our inquiries in this study.” With this goal in mind, the author undertakes a study of the act, because in his opinion, it is the act which reveals the person: “For such is the nature of the correlation inhering in experience, in the fact that ‘man acts’: the act constitutes a particular moment of revealing the person. The act allows us to have the most proper insight into his essence and to understand it most fully. We experience that man is a person, and we are convinced of this because he performs acts.” (p. 104).

Cardinal Wojtyła conducts his analyses from the perspective of the philosophy of being. At the same time, He does not want to give up, on the contrary, He wants to take advantage of

⁶ See, among others: K. Wojtyła, *Person and Act*, 102-103.

⁷ See: R. Ingarden, *Z badań nad filozofią współczesną*, Warsaw 1963, 294; A. Dondeyne, “L’expérience préphilosophique et les conditions anthropologiques de l’affirmation de Dieu,” in: *L’existence de Dieu*, Tournai 1963, 149-150.

⁸ Cf. John E. Smith, *Experience and God* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1968). In particular chapter 1 “Healing Experience.”

⁹ Karol Wojtyła, *Person and Act*, 103. Translator’s note: please note that the translation is altered slightly from the Ignatik translation to better fit the original text of the author which is as follows: “Przedmiotem analiz w książce *Osoba i czyn* jest „studium czynu, który ujawnia osobę; studium osoby poprzez czyn.”

the enrichment that we owe to the philosophy of consciousness, namely the more thorough knowledge of man “in the context of consciousness” (p. 112). According to the author “[a]n attempt to correctly unify in the conception of the person and the act the understandings that emerge from the experience of man in both its aspects *must in some measure become an attempt to unify two philosophical orientations, in a sense, two philosophies*” (p. 112).

In connection with the subject and purpose of the research set by Cardinal Wojtyła, the following types of questions arise: 1) how should we understand his commitment to the philosophy of being, or more precisely, in which field of the philosophy of being does he place his study of man as a person, 2) how does he understand the attempt to merge two philosophical orientations, and 3) to what extent has he shown it in the concept of person and act, thereby indicating that it is possible, at least within certain limits.

1. Philosophical anthropology as a presentation of the specific categories of human existence.

For Cardinal Wojtyła, the human person, being the object of experience, is not only the content of consciousness, is not just something thought, but is a concrete reality that really exists: “*this study aims in the broadest sense to explicate the reality that the person is*” (p. 106). “*For we are not concerned with the abstract but with a penetration into the actually existing reality*” (p. 110). And in yet another place: “*In the present reflections – in accord with the cognitive presuppositions made in the introductory chapter – we do not intend to sever the ‘I’ from its ontological implications. Every man is given in integral, that is, simple, experience as a *suppositum* – as a being that is the subject of existence and action*” (p. 596).

Cardinal Wojtyła distances himself from all types of positions: idealistic, phenomenalist, actualistic, and, therefore, the emphasis on his philosophical orientation is clear and unambiguous and requires no further explanation.

However, in our opinion, it should be noted that the author places his reflections on the human person in the perspective of his *own* human existence; he is concerned with categories that are proper to the human person, which, it seems to me, has not been adequately addressed by many discussants who see the study *Person and Act* as a kind of phenomenology and deny it a strictly philosophical character.

There is no doubt that Cardinal Wojtyła, to a large extent, uses the phenomenological method, and a realistic type,¹⁰ similar to, among others, the phenomenological method of Max Scheler, by treating direct data (and therefore phenomena) not as functions of consciousness, but as entities that actually exist.¹¹ He therefore uses the method of description, reduction and observation, so well known to those who have encountered the phenomenological method. He also emphasizes the direction of phenomenological explanation, noting that: “*The reasons that explain this reality (i.e. a human person - my addition) are contained in experience*” (p. 110).¹² But He does not stop there. Phenomenology implies, in Cardinal Wojtyła’s work, as well as for many other representatives of contemporary philosophical reflection, to mention only Heidegger and Dondeyne here, ontology.¹³ This is consistent when one takes into account that he wants to remain on the basis of the philosophy of being,¹⁴ and from the philosophy of consciousness he wants to retain what it actually provides in human cognition from the side of consciousness, and therefore the starting point is the data of consciousness, or more precisely, the consciousness of action, the act. We read, among other examples: “*Man not only acts consciously but also has the consciousness that he acts and, moreover, that he acts consciously*” (p. 125). He does not “intend an absolutization of consciousness. *Our goal is only to open an aspect that was too confined and that remained only an implication in the traditional conception*” (p. 593). Thus, according to Cardinal Wojtyła, the experience of “I” carries ontological implications.

This ontology, as we understand it, is not yet metaphysics *sensu stricto*. Nor is it an ontology in the sense of a theory of possible beings. It is rather a philosophical reflection that has as its subject the category of human existence as a person. Philosophical reflection of this type aims, first of all, at understanding this being in itself by discovering its constitutive features.¹⁵ As the author points out, and as we have already quoted in another context, it is about how “*to understand the human person for his own sake*” (p. 117). This can only be done by identifying those “moments” that constitute a person. The way to this is through the explication of what

¹⁰ The realistic position was represented by Husserl’s students from Göttingen, who were influenced by A. Reinach. R. Ingarden believes that Husserl, in his early period, also took a realistic position with regard to the real world. See: R. Ingarden, *Z badań*, 552-553.

¹¹ See, among others: Maurice Dupuy, *La philosophie de la religion chez Max Scheler*, Paris 1959, 248.

¹² Cf. A. Dondeyne, “L’expérience,” 151.

¹³ See: A. Dondeyne, “L’expérience,” 151.

¹⁴ Cf. M. Dupuy, *La philosophie*, 248.

¹⁵ Whereas: „metaphysicus considerat etiam de singularibus entibus, non secundum proprias rationes, per quas sunt tale vel tale ens, sed secundum quod participant communem entis rationem.” *In Boetii de Trinitate*, Lect. II, qu. I, a 4, ad 6.

experience contains. “Here, understanding,” writes Cardinal Wojtyła, “grows directly from experience without any intermediary stages, without reasoning” (p. 157). This is because “[t]he experience of man not only reveals that reality to us but also generates the need to explain it and at the same time creates the basis for this explanation. The wealth and diversity of experience, so to speak, provoke the mind, so that it tries to grasp the already-understood reality of the person and act in the most comprehensive way and to explain this reality most fully. This, however, can be accomplished only by way of an increasingly deep entry into experience, into its content. Thanks to this, the person and act are in a sense brought out of darkness. Standing before the mind that cognizes them, they appear more and more fully and more and more comprehensively. Interpretation, or reductive understanding, constitutes, *so to speak, and exploration of experience*. The very word ‘reduction’ ought not to be erroneously understood. It does not in the least mean a reduction in the sense of diminishing or limiting the wealth of the experienced object. The aim is to consistently bring out this object. The exploration of the experience of man must be a cognitive process in which the constant and homogeneous development of the original vision of the person in the act and through the act is accomplished. During the entire process, this vision must be consistently deepened and enriched” (pp. 108-109).

We find concrete examples of this position throughout the study *Person and Act*. For example, on the question of the spirituality of the person the author states: “The spirituality of man is manifested in consciousness, thanks to which it forms in lived-experience the experiential inwardness of his existence and action” (p. 147).

The validity of this approach is supported by both substantive and historical reasons in terms of Thomistic tradition.

And so, when it comes to substantive reasons, then 1° – if we do not want to practice pure rationalism in relation to human philosophy, then we must first indicate the reasons explaining his essence in the experience itself; and 2° – we need to know who man is in himself, what his essence is, before we can meaningfully ask whether or what reasons are required in addition to it,¹⁶ and

¹⁶ According to Husserl, all sciences are based on certain ideas and fundamental concepts which themselves cannot become the subject of research. Therefore, it is necessary to clarify what these basic concepts actually mean and from where their meaning initially grows. In Husserl’s language, this can be expressed as follows: the noematic content of basic concepts must be captured both in terms of the essence revealed in them and in terms of their origin. This kind of explanation of the basic noematic content has nothing to do with speculation about the essence that is carried out from the outside. The fundamental explanation can only be achieved in such a way that the basic eidetic content is sought in its original form and is drawn from it in such a way that nothing is added to this original content. We must already know what we mean when we say, for example, nature or history, before we can proceed towards further

how the essential “moments” of human existence can be interpreted within the framework of a general theory of being.¹⁷

The human person must therefore be given to us visually in experience. This can be called an interpretation, an objectification of human experience. How could we possibly know this? And even if someone from outside could point this out to us (Revelation),¹⁸ what significance would it have for us if it could not be found and verified in our own experience? Would it then constitute a reality “for us” or rather conceptual poetry?

This position is also an extension of the Thomistic tradition. For St. Thomas (following Aristotle), philosophical reflection on beings, in the definition of which “sensory matter” cannot be omitted, does not constitute metaphysics in the *sensu stricto*, but the philosophy of natural beings (*scientia naturalis*).¹⁹ *Scientia naturalis* also treats the soul as a form of the body.²⁰ Gilson says the same thing, in his own way. “Anthropology cannot be derived from metaphysics. Like other creatures, man is also a being animated by the act of being, but exceptionally his nature cannot be known independently of this act.”²¹ Knowledge in this field of being is achieved by pointing out the essential structural moments in what is given to us.²² The fact that Cardinal Wojtyła, from the entire wealth of human experience, chooses the fact of conscious action in particular, does not mean a fundamental change in the philosophical concept, but rather an enrichment of it with this aspect which, as he himself points out “*was too confined...in the traditional conception*” (p. 593).

This type of philosophical anthropology does not exclude a strictly metaphysical interpretation in two respects: 1° — insofar as it leads to the acceptance of the existence of a substantial soul that can exist independently of the body, and 2° — insofar as the structural

explanation. It is precisely a matter of explaining what was originally conceived from itself or from its original data. See: B. Welt, “Der Gottesbeweis und die Phänomenologie der Religion,” in: *Auf der Spur des Ewigen*, Freiburg – Basel – Wien 1965, 315-316. In our opinion, the same applies to man as a person. In trying to ultimately understand man as a person, the question must arise whether his relationship to God constitutes the reason that constitutes him in himself, and thus whether God is “inscribed” in the definition of man or whether he threatens it in the sense of alienation. See more on this topic in my article: “Człowiek a Bóg,” in: *Logos i ethos*, Kraków 1971; also: “Teologia a antropologia,” *Analecta Cracoviensia* 3 (1971) 58-59.

¹⁷ See further considerations in this article on the second aspect of metaphysical interpretation.

¹⁸ See: Romano Guardini, *Świat i osoba*, published in a joint volume: *Koniec czasów nowożytnych, Świat i osoba, Wolność – łaska – los*, Kraków 1969, 177.

¹⁹ *In Metaph.*, Lib. VI, Lect. I. nr. 1161.

²⁰ *In Metaph.*, Lib. VI, Lect. I. nr. 1159.

²¹ E. Gilson, *Elementy filozofii chrześcijańskiej* (Warszawa: Instytut Wydawniczy Pax, 1965), 189.

²² See, among others: S. Świeżawski – Ks. M. Jaworski, *Byt*, Lublin 1961, 67-69.

“moments” of human existence are explained within the framework of the general theory of being. Cardinal Wojtyła draws attention to both directions of this interpretation, although he does not explicitly systematize them. As for the metaphysical interpretation in the first aspect, Cardinal Wojtyła, not wishing to confuse the fields of philosophical knowledge or to commit the error of *petitio principii*, essentially limits himself to philosophical anthropology *sensu stricto*, that is, to demonstrating the structural moments of human existence as a person. This alone is a significant methodological advantage. At the same time, he points out that this type of anthropology is resolved in a specific way in substantial metaphysics, the spiritual human soul: “Although the foundations of man’s spirituality, in a sense, its roots [St. Thomas would say here: its end – my comment], reside outside the direct sphere of experience – *we reach them by way of reasoning* [emphasis mine] – spirituality itself has an experiential expression, becoming in a sense a sum of manifestations” (p. 147).

This position again reminds us of the view of St. Thomas, who taught about the object and end of the philosophy of material beings. The philosophy of man leads to the “root of spirituality,” which leads, let us add, to the acceptance of a substantial soul possessing its own act of existence.²³ Considering it as such, which is precisely what philosophical anthropology leads to, constitutes a separate type of philosophical reflection, belonging to metaphysics.²⁴

There are many examples of metaphysical interpretation in the second aspect. Right away in the first chapter, we note that “the equivalent of our ‘act’ [*czyn*]... is *actus humanus*” (p. 121). The author notes: “In the philosophical tradition of the West, the phrase *actus humanus* also presupposes a certain interpretation of act, namely, one that was developed on the basis of the philosophy of Aristotle in antiquity and of St. Thomas Aquinas in the Middle Ages. This interpretation is realistic and objectivistic as well as metaphysical. It stems from the entire conception of being, and directly from the conception of *potential-actus*, by means of which the Aristotelians and Thomists explain the changeable and dynamic character of being... A close link with the corresponding *potential*... is always characteristic of expressing *actus* in light of the entire Aristotelian or Thomistic conception of being” (pp. 121-122). In another place: “The two objective structures, namely, ‘man acts’ and ‘something happens in man,’ determine two fundamental directions of the dynamism proper to man... *The activity and passivity* – *agere and pati* – are made

²³ See: Gilson, *Elementy*, 194-195.

²⁴ *In Metaph.*, Lib. VI, Lect. I, nr. 1159.

manifest in them *as the constitutum of the structures and the objective basis of their diversification*. It is known that both *agere* and *pati* constitute two separate categories. The experience of human action and of what happens in man certainly greatly helped in distinguishing these categories. These two categories – *agere* and *pati* – not only oppose but also condition and explain each other in man just as they do in metaphysics” (pp.163-164). That is all when it comes to quotes in this regard. Let us also note that, according to Cardinal Wojtyła, human experience reveals and verifies both the ontic structure of man as a person proper only to him, and the ontic structure that constitutes his participation in the universal categories of being.²⁵

All this entitles us to see a philosophical and fundamental character in the study *Person and Act*. Of course, many issues still require further development and more precise clarification here. However, this was not the purpose of the study *Person and Act*. Building this type of methodology of philosophical anthropology is the task of specialists. Here we only want to present its outline, which is included in the study *Person and Act*. This outline can undoubtedly provide creative inspiration for the development of a more comprehensive methodology of philosophical anthropology, not outside of, but within the framework of Thomistic thought. The attempts made so far have been: 1° — overly “metaphysical” in the sense that they interpreted human existence “from above” within the framework of general systemic assumptions, and did not therefore strive to understand it in its own specific categories. (Is this not why modern philosophies of the subject grew beyond the traditional lines of philosophy?);²⁶ 2° — human experience as a basis for building a philosophical anthropology was not sufficiently take into account. Cardinal Wojtyła’s study, in our opinion, addresses these shortcomings, and at the same time, by taking a stance on the philosophy of being, remains an extension of Thomas’s philosophical orientation.

This brings us to the answer to the second question, which is related to Cardinal Wojtyła’s attempt to integrate this philosophical orientation with the orientation of the philosophy of consciousness.

²⁵ See footnote 14.

²⁶ Cardinal Wojtyła seems to answer this question at least partially himself when he states that: “Without the full revelation of this subjectivity there is no way of reaching and explicating the full and objective comprehensive content of these facts [human action and its relationship to the person].” And that, “subjectivism can also develop due to a too narrow and unilateral objectivism. What protects us from this is a possibly comprehensive analysis of the objective in all its aspects” (p. 158).

2. The concept of merging two philosophical orientations: the philosophy of being and the philosophy of consciousness.

Cardinal Wojtyła clearly stated how he understood the attempt to merge two philosophical orientations: He is concerned, as we have already quoted, with the enrichment that comes with “a more thorough cognition of man in the context of consciousness” (p. 112). Cardinal Wojtyła does not, therefore, have in mind a philosophy of consciousness that reduces all reality to the subject-consciousness (it is not about, as he himself writes, the absolutization of consciousness, p. 127; 593). Then it would be difficult to talk about the philosophy of being as opposed to the philosophy of consciousness. The point here is to take into account the relevant data of human experience (consciousness of action), but without the kind of interpretations that present subjectivism ultimately leading to idealism, or various varieties of the philosophy of the transcendental subject. “Subjectivism,” as the author states, “in the given case would consist in reducing acts exclusively to lived-experience, and moral values... to the very contents of consciousness. *However, once consciousness ceases to be understood as an aspect,*” which the author tried to show in this chapter, “*it also ceases to explain subjectivity, that is, the subjectivity of man and his acts, and it itself becomes an exclusive subject. Subjectivism understands consciousness as an integral and exclusive subject...* under this assumption, with this mental attitude, both lived-experiences and their objective equivalents, that is, values, cease to be something real. They remain only as contents of consciousness: *esse = percipi*. Finally, consciousness itself ceases to be something real and becomes merely a thought subject of contents. The path to subjectivism ends in idealism” (pp. 158-159; 599).

By opposing the interpretation offered by subjectivism presented above, the author aims to demonstrate that taking into account this type of experiential data as a starting point is not only not intrinsically linked to the immanentist interpretation, but is in fact of great importance for realism. In other words: the method of immanence, reflection on the relevant data of consciousness, can both point to a transcendent reality in relation to it, as well as to a concrete, actually existing subject, and thus to the transcendence of a real subject-person, which is the ontological source of consciousness. We read that: “To ascertain the man-person’s subjectivity has a fundamental significance *for the realism* [emphasis mine] and, indeed, the objectivism of our study. *For in*

reality man is a subject and experiences himself as a subject. The dynamic relation – or correlation – between person and act is realized on this basis. Without ascertaining the subjectivity of man, no plane exists on which we could comprehensively grasp this relation” (p. 157). And further justification of this importance of human subjectivity for complete realism (experiencing the act, experiencing the person’s causative relationship to it, experiencing moral value): “*All these are objective facts, which nonetheless possess their objective and realness only and exclusively in the subjectivity of man*” (p. 158).

The position of subjectivism, as can be concluded from the study *Person and Act*, is based not so much on the accepted starting point as on the insufficient consideration of the direct data of self-knowledge²⁷ that justify the realistic position. Before we move to that, however, let us note here that this concept of combining two philosophical orientations has particular importance when we consider that modern philosophies of the subject have oscillated precisely in the direction of idealism and subjectivism. Accentuating and further developing the direction of the solution presented in the study *Person and Act* should become the subject of a separate academic dissertation, perhaps even more than one. The path shown by Cardinal Wojtyła is certainly new, and the stakes are very high and therefore it is worth the effort.

3. An attempt to integrate the philosophy of being and the philosophy of consciousness in relation to the human person.

Regardless of any future work that will address the program and direction of the solution outlined by Cardinal Wojtyła in his study, let us attempt to show, in a broad outline and by way of example only, how he implements his program of integrating both of the aforementioned philosophical concepts.

Cardinal Wojtyła, starting from the consciousness of the act, reverses, as it were, the order that has been accepted so far in the traditional concept, according to which “man exists and acts ‘consciously,’ yet his existence and action do not have a specific source in consciousness” (p. 127) “... the entire human cognition – the ability and habit of active understanding – closely cooperates with consciousness” (p. 132).

²⁷ See below quotes from pp. 594 and 134.

Cardinal Wojtyła distinguishes all forms of knowledge from self-knowledge, the object of which is one's own "I." Thanks to self-knowledge, consciousness reflects actions and their relationship to one's own "I." Taking this fact into account is of paramount importance. It affects the character of the "I" and opposes the idealistic position which does not "adequately consider the way in which everything that inheres in consciousness does so" (p. 594). "Without self-knowledge, consciousness would be deprived of semantic contents concerning... man's own 'I' as an object... The idealists postulate a state like this, for in it consciousness can be considered a subject that produces its contents with no regard for any factor located outside consciousness itself. A valid question in this line of thought arises – namely, whether consciousness itself can be considered a real subject or whether it is only its own product" (p. 134).

Thus, an in-depth analysis of data and the way they are embedded in consciousness as a starting point characteristic of the philosophy of consciousness leads to different conclusions about the nature of the consciousness of the "I" than is the case in idealistic trends.

And further: "...self-knowledge has nothing to do with some kind of philosophy whose subject is the 'I.' Then it would be about an abstracted, generalized 'I'; ... *In self-knowledge, the object is the 'I,' concrete and 'one's own'*" (p. 137).

And that is why, according to Cardinal Wojtyła, "*the boundary of objectivity and realism in the conception of man... is marked by the acknowledgment of self-knowledge*" (p. 159).

Cardinal Wojtyła sees in consciousness a trait that he describes as "reflective." It consists of a mental turn toward the subject as such. Thanks to this "this object, which ontologically is a subject... experience[s] himself as a subject – that is... experience[s] his own 'I'" (p. 596). So we have a subjective experience of the subject *suppositum*, which in ontology has a purely objective character, abstracting from the aspect of experience. "In fact, the word 'I' contains more than *suppositum*, for it contains the subjective lived-experience of subjectivity and implicates the object that is a subject (that is, subjectivity in the objective and ontological sense – precisely that which *suppositum* denotes). However, if we severed the word 'I' from its implication, which is the *suppositum*, then this 'I' would merely denote the consciousness-related aspect or, in other words, the psychological aspect of subjectivity" (p. 596).

The above argument takes us a big step forward in relation to the previous statements, where Cardinal Wojtyła questioned primarily the position of subjectivism or idealism in the area of the subject — consciousness. We have here a connection between the subjective experience of

the subject and the ontological *suppositum*, thanks to the reflexive nature of consciousness. This also indicates how Cardinal Wojtyła understands the ontological implications of experience. We experience of ourselves as beings that are the subject of existence and action (see: pp. 596-597). “Ontologia czy aitiologia,” *Znak* 111, (1963).

And hence the conclusion: “Consciousness is linked with a being, that is, with a concrete man ‘who is myself,’ who objectively is some ‘I.’ Consciousness neither obscures this being nor absorbs it into itself, as would follow from the basic premise of idealistic thinking, according to which *esse* is *percipi* (‘to be’ is the same as ‘to be the content of consciousness,’ while no being outside consciousness is accepted). Quite the contrary; consciousness *inwardly, as it were, reveals* this being, the human being – the person... Lived-experience is not a reflex that appears on the surface of man’s being and acting. Quite the contrary – it is *the mode of the actualization of being and acting that man owes to consciousness*. It is, in a sense, a final and definitive mode in which *the real* [emphasis mine] and objective energies contained in man as *a being* [emphasis mine] are actualized not only objectively but also in the profile of his subjectivity, *finding their subjective completion in lived-experience*” (p. 597).

Analyzing agency against the background of human dynamism, Cardinal Wojtyła comes to the following statements that confirm and complement his previous statements about the nature of human existence: “*In no way can we question his* [the person’s] *unity and identity at the foundations of efficacy and subjectivity*, structurally contained in action and in what happens in man” (p. 174). “The subjectivity of man that is common to both structures – to action and happening – found its expression in the concept of *suppositum* in the philosophy practiced according to the principles of Aristotle and Thomas Aquinas... *Suppositum indicates* either the very being of the subject or *the subject as being*. This subject as a being inheres at the basis of every dynamic structure, of every action and happening, of every efficacy and subjectivity. This *being is real*, the being – ‘man’ really existing, and consequently *really acting* (pp. 174-175, emphasis mine). “The man-person ought to be identified as a *suppositum* at the first and fundamental view. The person is a concrete man – the *individua substantia*, as Boethius declares in the first part of his classical definition” (pp. 175-176).

To sum up the considerations made from points one to three, let us emphasize the main points: 1° — Cardinal Wojtyła, thanks to the relevant data of human experience, the experience of subjectivity, illustrates certain claims of classical ontology visible in the plane of human existence,

and thereby provides their verification; 2° — Questions the subjectivist and idealist interpretation of human consciousness.

As can be seen, we wanted to show (not entirely, however) Cardinal Wojtyła's approach in the study *Person and Act* (formal aspect) and the realistic solution that he arrives at in the man-person section. However, in accordance with the task we set ourselves in this article, we cannot comment on the substantive correctness of individual decisions in terms of their merits. It seems to us, however, that the method of proceeding and visualizing used by Cardinal Wojtyła brings with it the type of obviousness about which he writes that "it seems to indicate the essential property of revelation or manifestation of the object, the cognitive feature characteristic of it. At the same time, however, evidentness means that the understanding of the fact 'man acts' as the act of the person... finds complete confirmation in the content of experience, that is, in the content of the fact 'man acts,' with its enormous frequency" (pp. 102-103).

Let us also note – and this is not without significance – that the same direction of the solution (a concrete, real subject) can be found in Roman Ingarden's treatise "Responsibility. Its Ontic Foundations," published in *The Little Book of Man* (published after his death in Krakow in 1972). Ingarden, asking about the ontic foundations of responsibility, had to question solutions that reduced a person to a stream of consciousness or to a pure "I" and opt for a realistic solution. "All theories," he states, "which reduce the person to a multitude of pure experiences are insufficient to explain the ontic foundations of responsibility. Only if one regards man, and in particular his soul and his person, as a real object existing in time, which has a special, characteristic form, is it possible to fulfill the demands of responsibility" (p. 132).

III. A REALISTIC CONCEPT OF EXPERIENCE

We will now proceed to read the study *Person and Act* in the light of the second assumption we made at the beginning, namely the issue of experience as a source of philosophical knowledge. The realistic conception of man – person that Cardinal Wojtyła presents to us is not only possible but also justified, thanks to the outline of a more adequate, realistic theory of experience that he presented in the introduction to his work.

Cardinal Wojtyła understands his study as an objectivization “of the great cognitive process that may be defined as the experience of man” (p. 95). For the basis of knowledge about man is always experience (p. 97-98). The author starts from the fact that “man acts” (p. 101).

Speaking about human experience, Cardinal Wojtyła explains how he understands “experience” in general. First, from the negative side, he opposes the phenomenalist position, that is, the reduction of the sphere of experience to the function and content of the senses themselves (p. 101-102). Positively, Cardinal Wojtyła, 1° — connects experience with specific fields of facts; 2° — experience, according to him, indicates the directness of cognition itself, the direct cognitive contact with the object. This directness is not limited to sensory acts: “We must state that a mental act at least participates in this directness of grasping the object... It seems... that the mind is engaged already in experience itself, thanks to which it establishes contact with the object, a contact that is equally, though in a different way, direct. For this reason, *every human experience is at the same time some understanding of what I experience*” (p. 102). The author adds: “It seems that this position opposes phenomenism and is proper to phenomenology, which emphasizes above all the unity of the act of human cognition” (p. 102). Therefore, the Author takes the position “that *the act is a particular moment of the vision* – that is, the experience – *of the person*... It is the intellectual vision given on the basis of the fact ‘man acts’” (p. 102).

And so, the person is given to us here in the fact that “man acts.” This alone indicates that this way of experiencing, through facts, excludes the conception of direct data as pure content of our consciousness. Experience is a means of direct cognitive contact with the reality of a fact that is independent of our consciousness. Here it is a way of cognitive contact with the reality of the person given through the act (the act reveals the person). And hence, for example, such statements by Cardinal Wojtyła: “... this study... aims *in the broadest sense to explicate the reality that the person is*” (p. 106). “The present study comes into being precisely as an expression of the need to explain or interpret *the rich reality of the person* [emphasis mine] given to us together with acts – and through acts – in the experience of man... *However, there exists the need for a more comprehensive explanation of the reality of the person and act*, a need based on some fundamental understanding of the person and act. The experience of man not only reveals that *reality* [emphasis mine] to us but also generates the need to explain it and at the same time creates the basis for this explanation. The wealth and diversity of experience constitute, so to speak, provoke the mind, so that it tries to grasp the already – understood *reality* [emphasis mine] of the person and act in

the most comprehensive way and to explain this reality most fully. This, however, can be accomplished only by way of an increasingly deep entry into experience, into its content” (pp. 108-109).

On this basis, we can speak of a further “healing” of the experience²⁸ by Cardinal Wojtyła. Phenomenology has undoubtedly made a great step in this respect, overcoming, for example, all kinds of psychologisms. However, a legitimate question arises whether the so-called *epoché* itself does not in certain cases constitute an obstacle to a precise and complete observation of the phenomenon and does not thereby falsify the data.²⁹ A thorough analysis of the direct data of consciousness and the way in which they are contained in it, however, indicates, as Cardinal Wojtyła tried to show, that one cannot ignore the reality of a specific subject if one does not want to falsify these data. This is also why we are talking here about further healing of experience.

The full explication of what is given in human experience confirms in its own way, that Cardinal Wojtyła’s general understanding of experience is correct, and its application to man is not arbitrary.

Thus, we come to the final conclusion. Getting rid of all prejudices should be based primarily on experience. Experience must be freed from all deforming subjectivist or idealistic theories. When we consider the data of human experience without prejudice, we find that not only is psychologism overcome, but also Husserl’s later position of transcendental idealism. Clarification of the data of human experience leads to realism. It reveals the moment of reality of a concrete subject contained within it. If, as R. Ingarden writes, “the data of experience not only enable us to learn about objects, but also have a justifying power, motivating our beliefs on the one hand, and verifying the concepts and judgments we have acquired about given objects on the other,”³⁰ then the study by Cardinal Wojtyła is of decisive importance for the realistic position regarding the man – person. This is also where its particular importance lies, regardless of its substantive achievements. As such, it also shows the direction for the development of a contemporary realistic philosophy of the subject – man, and further outlines the way to a more complete justification of the realistic position in general.

²⁸ We borrow this term from J.E. Smith in his book *Experience and God*; see footnote 8.

²⁹ See: M. Dupuy, op. cit. 249.

³⁰ R. Ingarden, *Z badań*, 290.

Encounter, Entrustment, and Witness through Work:

Karol Wojtyła and the Imitation of St. Joseph

Grzegorz Ignatik¹

Abstract

The goal of this article is to deepen appreciation for St. Joseph's significance in human and Christian life and to encourage greater imitation of St. Joseph in light of that significance. This article does not intend to highlight all the personal virtues of this great saint or to explore in detail his relations to Christ Jesus and the Blessed Virgin Mary. Instead, after identifying the concept of imitation, the article examines the fundamental principle involved in imitating St. Joseph and considers several personal virtues that organically proceed from that principle. Although every man is called to imitate St. Joseph, this article considers such imitation particularly within the context of the ministerial (hierarchical) priesthood and priestly formation. In answering the question of what the imitation of St. Joseph truly entails, the article demonstrates that this imitation remains not only a suitable but also a feasible choice for the contemporary man, and especially the Christian. To accomplish this goal, the article draws primarily from the teaching of Karol Wojtyła prior to 1978.

Keywords

imitation, family, work, fatherhood, masculinity, Karol Wojtyła, St. Joseph

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Introduction

The goal of this article is twofold: first, to deepen our appreciation for St. Joseph’s significance in human and Christian life; second, to encourage greater imitation of St. Joseph in light of that significance.² This article does not intend to highlight all the personal virtues of this great saint or to explore in detail his relations to Christ Jesus and the Blessed Virgin Mary. Several other works accomplish that task.³ Instead, after identifying the concept of imitation, the article examines the fundamental principle involved in imitating St. Joseph and considers several personal virtues that organically proceed from that principle. Although every man is called to imitate St. Joseph, this article considers such imitation in the context of the ministerial (hierarchical) priesthood and those men preparing for ordination. Therefore, in addition to an introduction and conclusion, the article consists of four parts: “On Imitation,” “The Fundamental Principle of Imitating St. Joseph,” “Personal Loci of This Imitation,” and “Application of This Imitation to Priesthood.”

In answering the question of what the imitation of St. Joseph truly means, the article demonstrates that such imitation remains not only a suitable but also a feasible choice for the contemporary man, and especially for today’s Christian. It suggests that, by imitating St. Joseph, man fulfills his fundamental task of living on earth as man. Furthermore, the article aims to see this life through a sacramental lens. Indeed, the central theme here is not mere imitation but sacramental integration, which becomes more clearly identified in the imitation of St. Joseph. It is difficult to capture the essence of this imitation in a few words. Nonetheless, I wish to suggest the phrase “encounter, entrustment, and witness through work” as our lodestar to the person of St. Joseph and his imitation. I think this phrase captures not only God’s attitude toward St. Joseph but also—and more importantly the focus of this brief work—the sacramental or integrative aspect of St. Joseph’s life that is worthy of imitation.

In order to accomplish my goal, I will draw primarily from the teaching of Karol Wojtyła on the concept of imitation and the person of St. Joseph. I will focus especially on texts he authored

² I thank Fr. Marek Kasperczuk, STD, my colleague at the Pontifical College Josephinum, for his valuable remarks that helped me improve this article.

³ See, for instance, F.L. Filas, *Joseph: The Man Closest to Jesus* (Boston: Pauline Books & Media, 1962); John Paul II, *Redemptoris Custos: On the Person and Mission of Saint Joseph* (apostolic exhortation, 1989).

in or before 1978, that is, prior to his election to the papacy.⁴ These few, little-known texts by the Polish prelate offer a rich and profound vision of St. Joseph as well as Wojtyła's understanding of imitation.

Part 1: On Imitation

The Means and Goal of Imitation

The world today is quite ambivalent with respect to imitation. On the one hand, we see examples of imitation everywhere. Every commercial, every concert, and every movie offers its audience models to imitate, fashions to copy, and products to own and use. On the other hand, imitating others is frowned upon as lacking originality, given its non-spontaneous origin. To be truly oneself, one is encouraged to reinvent oneself—to be an absolute self-mover. To be indifferent to others and to move independently of them, relying solely on one's own will and dispositions as the only guide, seems to be the epitome of authenticity and freedom.

However, genuine imitation is neither enslavement nor servitude, nor witless copying. Rather, in itself, it is a conscious and voluntary activity of a person. "I want to be like you" or "I wish to follow you" does not take away personal freedom and responsibility. Instead, the need for imitation is dictated by the true good, perceived thanks to the other or *in* the other. Hence, the reality of imitation indicates a difference between the actual and an ideal state desired and feasible for a particular subject to attain. It manifests that we are still on a journey toward the perfection (fulfillment) of life, whether individual or social. The ideal state is realized by following a personal exemplar (a person-model). Ultimately, and according to Wojtyła's

⁴ Wojtyła's teaching on St. Joseph used in this article is taken from his articles and homilies. In particular:

- "Święty Józef," in: K. Wojtyła, *Aby Chrystus się nami posługiwał* (Kraków: Wydawnictwo Znak, 1980), 82–87; first published in *Tygodnik Powszechny* 14, No. 12 (1960).
- "Wypełnić życie prawdą Ewangelii," in: K. Wojtyła, *Odnowa Kościoła i świata: Refleksje soborowe* (Rome: Fundacja Jana Pawła II, 2014), 28–32; first given as a speech on Vatican Radio on November 24, 1962, and then published in *Notificaciones e Curia Metropolitana Cracoviensi* 1–2 (1963): 23–26.
- "Uroczystość św. Józefa-Robotnika – 1 Maja," in: K. Wojtyła, *Słowo Boże skierowane do człowieka w roku liturgicznym: Część druga—od Wielkanocy do Adwentu* (Częstochowa, 1981), 13–16; a sermon first given on May 1, 1969 (Podgórze, Church of St. Joseph).
- as well as the sermons given on March 19, 1968 (Kraków, Church of St. Joseph); on January 12, 1969 (Zakopane, Church of the Most Holy Family); on May 1, 1970 (Kraków, Church of St. Joseph); on May 1, 1970 (Podgórze, Church of St. Joseph); on March 19, 1974 (Kraków, Church of St. Joseph); on March 19, 1976 (Kraków, Church of St. Joseph); and on January 15, 1978 (Kraków, Studium for the Theology of Marriage and Family).

These sermons, in their original Polish, are cataloged under AKKW E III and available in the Archive of the Metropolitan Curia in Kraków, Poland.

personalistic vision, the goal of imitation is an improvement or renewal of the one who imitates. In theological terminology, we call the process of such renewal “conversion.” We can also speak here of the “configuration” of the subject to his model. Of course, the “conversion” in this context entails the person’s turning away from sin and facing God in order to renew the divine image in himself and thereby introduce it into the world. To sum up, imitation is transformative of the subject’s interior (*ad intra*) and exterior (*ad extra*).

Wojtyła’s concept of imitation can be considered in light of these two aspects. For him, imitation pertains to the person’s properly human acts and to his morality (his moral value). These elements are indispensable for genuine imitation in its interior and exterior dimensions.

Imitation in the World of Immanuel Kant and Max Scheler

Karol Wojtyła’s views on imitation are formed by Christian revelation as well as philosophical reflections, especially on the thought of Immanuel Kant and Max Scheler.⁵ Scheler opposed his personalistic ethical system to the aprioristic, formalistic system of Kant. According to Kant, the source of man’s ethical life is human reason, which ought to live by an *a priori*, universal form of law. All ethical action is done for the sake of the law while disregarding the motivation originating from any values found in the world, any goods perceived through experience. For this reason, there is little place for imitation in the Kantian ethical system as morality must find its origin in the individual’s own embracement of the norm in the *a priori* form of pure practical reason. In his *Groundwork of the Metaphysics of Morals*, Kant clearly states that:

Imitation has no place at all in moral matters, and examples serve for encouragement only, i.e. they put beyond doubt the feasibility of what the law commands, they make intuitive what the practical rule expresses more generally, but they can never entitle us to set aside their true original, which lies in reason, and to go by examples.⁶

⁵ See K. Wojtyła, “On the Metaphysical and Phenomenological Basis of the Moral Norm (According to the Conceptions of St. Thomas Aquinas and Max Scheler),” in: K. Wojtyła, *The Lublin Lectures and Works on Max Scheler*, “The English Critical Edition of the Works of Karol Wojtyła/John Paul II,” vol. 2, ed. A. Lopez, trans. by G. Ignatik (Washington, D.C.: Catholic University of America Press, 2023), 351–352; K. Wojtyła, “The Evangelical Principle of Imitation: The Teaching of the Sources of Revelation and Max Scheler’s Philosophical System,” in: Wojtyła, *The Lublin Lectures*, 561–570, 571–572.

⁶ I. Kant, *Groundwork of the Metaphysics of Morals*, trans. by M. Gregor (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2011), 47.

Consequently, even good ideas or behavior observed in others would be treated with suspicion because they did not originate in oneself. For Kant, imitation seemed merely an exterior affair and, ultimately, unworthy of the person.

In contradistinction to Kant, Scheler encourages imitation as a properly personal affair. According to Scheler, nonpersonal, abstract, and universal norms cannot contain moral values and are thus ethically moot. Only man—the human person—as a model for imitation can be morally fruitful. On this particular point, Wojtyła notes that Scheler overcame Kantianism by referring to the sound ethical tradition of Aristotle.⁷ In that tradition, a good man was the model and measure of moral conduct. However, the concept of imitation in Scheler is peculiar, in accordance with the phenomenological presuppositions of his system. For him, imitation takes place through the follower’s lived-experience of the model’s values. The basis of imitation is the love of the disciple for the person-model.⁸ Here is how Wojtyła explains the central significance of love in Scheler’s moral system:

By co-experiencing, through the love for the person of the Master, his world of ethical values, the disciples intentionally experience in their feeling the same ethical values. The whole “imitation” would be reduced to that.⁹

Lastly, the person who imitates his exemplar experiences the moral values secondarily—that is, “on the occasion” of the affinity to the other. Due to the threat of Pharisaism (a self-interest in pursuing the good), neither moral perfection nor moral value is the center of imitation, or even volition, in the Schelerian system.

According to Wojtyła, Scheler reduces the principle of imitation to the intentional sphere. Unfortunately, the emotional lived-experience of values in the Schelerian system (in which one *per se* experiences values in their hierarchy) drowned the person’s lived-experience of the truth about the good. That is, human life no longer involves personal moral judgment on human acts in

⁷ See, for instance, Wojtyła, “On the Metaphysical and Phenomenological Basis of the Moral Norm,” 352.

⁸ “The love for the person who is the model (and, as that model, constitutes an ideal) opens up the ideal value essence of that person to the disciple-imitator, makes it accessible for the emotional-cognitive acts of the disciple, and thereby enables imitation.” K. Wojtyła, “An Assessment of the Possibility for Building a Christian Ethics Based on the Presuppositions of Max Scheler’s System,” in: Wojtyła, *The Lublin Lectures*, 411. See also Wojtyła, “The Evangelical Principle of Imitation,” 565.

⁹ K. Wojtyła, “Max Scheler’s Ethical System as a Means of Developing Christian Ethics,” in: Wojtyła, *The Lublin Lectures*, 511.

light of the norm of morality. For Scheler, what matters most in imitation is the master's ideal value essence experienced by the disciple and, thereby, a formation or reformation of that disciple's ethos, rather than a development of the person's real ethical perfection. In this case, lived-experience in some sense obscures or disregards being. Wojtyła summarizes his realistic position *vis-à-vis* Scheler's intentional position as follows:

According to the Gospel, it is impossible to have the true model for imitation in isolation from his real acts. *It is only on account of the real objective ethical value of his acts that man becomes the model for another. Also, it is only by the real objective ethical value of his acts that man becomes the imitator of this model. Although it is impossible to think of imitation without being concerned for the model's world of values, this concern alone is not yet ethical. It becomes such only by corresponding acts.*¹⁰

That is how Wojtyła corrects the overly subjectivistic concept of imitation in Scheler in favor of a realistic concept, which, by the way, includes the aspect of lived-experience.

Imitation in Christianity

Wojtyła observes that imitation has always been invoked in Christian tradition as an integral task of Christian life. Sacred Scripture contains numerous texts that demonstrate the principle of imitation at work. It suffices to recall Christ's words "Follow me," as they convey an invitation not merely to join the group of disciples (see Mt 8:18–22 or 9:9) but also to morally imitate the person of Jesus (see Mt 16:24 or Mt 19:21). Christ explicitly sanctions imitation by his words: "I have given you an example, that you also should do as I have done to you" (Jn 13:15), for "apart from me you can do nothing" (Jn 15:5). We see similar encouragement expressed by the apostles, not only with respect to Christ Jesus but also to their own persons. For instance, St. Paul encourages other Christians to "Be imitators of me, as I am of Christ" (1 Cor 11:1; also see Eph 5:1; 1 Thes 1:6; 2 Thes 3:9; and Phil 3:7). Similar calls to imitation are found in texts authored by Sts. Peter and John (see 1 Pet 1:15; 2:21; and 1 Jn 2:3).

Let me briefly observe that, in the first place, Christ's encouragement of imitation is grounded in his own imitation of the Father by virtue of Christ's divinity. For example, we read

¹⁰ K. Wojtyła, "The Principle of 'Imitation,'" in: Wojtyła, *The Lublin Lectures*, 572 (emphasis original).

Christ's admission that "the Son can do nothing of his own accord, but only what he sees the Father doing; for whatever he does, the Son does likewise" (Jn 5:19). Taking the call for imitation directed by Christ to the apostles, and by the apostles to the disciples, we discover by analogy that relation expresses a primordial form of being. In other words, "Christian existence is put with Christ into the category of relationship" because becoming and being a Christian means to become and be a son.¹¹ What I wish to emphasize now is the intrinsic link between imitation and sonship. Sonship is the fundamental and personal principle of authentic imitation.

As indicated above, the task of imitation entails a model or ideal to be striven for. Wojtyła points out that the model for imitation is always a person whose moral perfection is manifested in his action, in the acts he performs.¹² The principle of imitation entails the model's real ethical perfection and not just his lived-experience of a world of values (as seen in Scheler). Hence, the existence of moral perfection in general is insufficient unless it accompanies a concretely existing person as the model. It is through his acts that the person realizes and manifests his moral perfection (if these acts are good) or moral turpitude (if these acts are evil). By imitating our model, we endeavor that the good we see in the acts of our model be analogously realized in our own acts and, consequently, in our own person.

We see that the means of imitation here is not merely to follow external acts "automatically," as it were. Furthermore, imitation does not entail focusing on one's lived-experience to the exclusion of external acts and facts. Rather, the point of imitation is to realize one's personhood by interior moral growth and fulfillment precisely in and through human acts (including external bodily acts). Wojtyła summarizes the features of a model-ideal in Christianity by calling it—or, rather, him, for this model is always a person—religious, real, practical, and ethical.¹³ By analogy, first, imitation is *religious* because to follow a good model (Christ or St. Joseph, for instance) is a task received from God that places man in a positive relation to him, since ethical perfection in man is a reflection of God's perfection. Second, this imitation is *real* because it concerns not merely an intentional sphere (consciousness and the lived-experience

¹¹ See J. Ratzinger, *Introduction to Christianity*, trans. by J.R. Foster (San Francisco: Ignatius Press, 2004), 186–187.

¹² See Wojtyła, "The Evangelical Principle of Imitation," 562. Wojtyła speaks of a certain "self-creation" through conscious acts, by which man becomes good or evil in virtue of the goodness or evilness of the acts he performs. See, for instance, K. Wojtyła, *"Person and Act" and Related Essays*, "The English Critical Edition of the Works of Karol Wojtyła/John Paul II," vol. 1, ed. A. Lopez, trans. by G. Ignatik (Washington, D.C.: Catholic University of America Press, 2021), 171–173.

¹³ See Wojtyła, "The Evangelical Principle of Imitation," 563–564, 568–571.

connected with it) but also the whole being. Third, imitation in Christian understanding is *practical* because the task of imitation is not merely theoretical but also involves the human will and properly human action. Lastly, imitation has an intrinsic *ethical* aspect because it aims at the subject's moral goodness and is performed in conformity with norms of morality. Such a comprehensive vision presupposes and expresses an integral anthropology confirmed in light of Revelation.

Part 2: The Fundamental Principle of Imitating St. Joseph

Religious Source of the Imitation

Karol Wojtyła's reflections on the suitability of imitating St. Joseph possess both human and religious significance—that is, they show relevance to both our human existence and our supernatural life. Wojtyła finds the fundamental reason for imitating St. Joseph in the fact of his closeness to the life of Christ and his mother, the Blessed Virgin Mary. Let me note immediately that this closeness has a definitive structure: it is realized in and through marriage and the family. St. Joseph enjoys a close relationship with Christ and his mother as the spouse and husband of Mary and as the foster father of Jesus.

From within these relationships of spousality and fatherhood, St. Joseph encountered the supernatural mystery of the Incarnation—the fact that the Son of God assumed a human nature and became a man. In God's providential plan, Joseph was granted the grace to stand most closely to the nexus of the divine and human elements as they were united on earth (*humanis divina iunguntur*). Besides the Blessed Virgin Mary, he remained in the earthly life of our Lord the longest, even longer than the apostles themselves. Another reason for his special position in the divine plan of salvation is the very fact that God entrusted to him both his Son and the mother who bore him into the world. For this reason, the Church venerates St. Joseph by celebrating his feast days (St. Joseph, Spouse of the Blessed Virgin Mary; St. Joseph the Worker; the Holy Family) and by introducing his name into the Canon of the Holy Mass before the transubstantiation (by Pope St. John XXIII), immediately after mentioning the name of the Blessed Virgin Mary and preceding the names of the apostles and martyrs. Therefore, St. Joseph is the chosen patron of many causes, peoples, and institutions.

The Key Principle

This closeness to the mystery of the Incarnation gives St. Joseph an unprecedented insight into two great matters of human existence: family (which is based on the marriage between one man and one woman) and work. We cannot imagine human existence without these two realities, nor should we. We are (and ought to be) born into families and realize our humanity and personhood through our own work, through our own actions, on the basis of who we became in our families. To put it differently, we are human because our existence starts with family and proceeds on its foundation. Whatever we do in life and with our life, we do on the foundation of the relationships into which we entered by birth—that is, our relationships with our mother, father, siblings, grandparents, and extended family members. It is no wonder that, from ancient times, family life has been considered a school of life. As we know, this life, this work that the human person does by his acts, transforms not only the world around him but primarily the subject himself, especially in his moral, properly personal aspect. Therefore, Wojtyła says that family is indispensable because this is where man becomes man.¹⁴

A moment ago, I said that the closeness to the mystery of the Incarnation grants St. Joseph a unique insight into two fundamental aspects of human existence: family and work. It is precisely this connection between divine mysteries and human affairs that Karol Wojtyła highlights in his reflections on St. Joseph. These divine mysteries are not only hidden in the innermost being of the Most Holy Trinity but also manifest in the world. They enter the life of mankind and permeate the history of man most notably in the form of family (and marriage) and work. Wojtyła discusses this both in the context of creation as the primordial revelation of God, and in the context of divine revelation, which is cloaked, as it were, within this creation. God neither rejects nor forgets the work of his hands; rather, he elevates it by accomplishing his divine plan precisely in and through his creation. Therefore, while matrimony, family, and work reflect the nature of the Creator, they also acquire new value and a sacramental (soterial) mission in the reality of the Holy Family. This is why Wojtyła considers St. Joseph “key” to both the divine mysteries and the most fundamental human concerns.

Yet, there is another reason for this key significance of St. Joseph in relation to these mysteries. It is perhaps better to say that he is the key to divine mysteries precisely because of his participation in the human mysteries—again, the mysteries of marriage, family, and work. To put

¹⁴ See Karol Wojtyła’s homily given in Zakopane, the Church of the Most Holy Family, on January 12, 1969.

it differently, what we need to imitate in St. Joseph is also his degree of *integration*, the integration between his interiority or spirituality and his exterior life as manifested in his work in the world.¹⁵ It is precisely this integrative character of St. Joseph that is the most essential foundation of his imitation. I will discuss this character in greater detail in the following reflections.

Family: The Interior Aspect of St. Joseph's Life

Of course, St. Joseph's insight into the matters of family and human labor entailed his own attitude toward them. We wish to imitate him both because of this attitude and because of the acts by which he proved to be a model worthy of imitation for us. Wojtyła considers two central aspects of St. Joseph's significance for man. We can call them the *ad intra* and *ad extra* aspects—the interior and the exterior dimensions of St. Joseph's person and life. They are exemplified by the above-mentioned realities of family and work, respectively.

The interior aspect (*ad intra*) relates to the Holy Family, of which St. Joseph was the head. He was the chaste spouse¹⁶ of the Blessed Virgin Mary and the foster father (*pater putativus*) of her Son, Jesus Christ. Wojtyła considers the interior aspect of St. Joseph's life to be genuinely contemplative. It was St. Teresa, the great reformer of the Carmelite order, who noticed a particular connection between the person of St. Joseph and contemplative life.¹⁷ Due to his day-to-day presence and interaction with the divine mysteries—his silent presence, we might add (for Sacred Scripture records not one word of his)—

in his paternal, thus full of loving care and diligent gaze at the Incarnated God and his Mother (...) we can quite easily consider St. Joseph's life as an ideal or even a prototype of the contemplative life.¹⁸

¹⁵ Integration is one of the central concepts in Karol Wojtyła's philosophy and theology. For more information, see, for instance, Wojtyła, *Person and Act*, 295ff., and G. Ignatik, *Communicating Life: Karol Wojtyła and Humanae Vitae* (Washington, DC: Humanum Academic Press, 2024), 214ff.

¹⁶ For a more detailed explanation of Wojtyła's concept of chastity (purity) as both a human virtue and a divine gift (i.e., the moral and charismatic aspects) as well as the task of integrating chastity in the human person, see Ignatik, *Communicating Life*, 298–306. St. Joseph integrated both aspects of chastity—moral and charismatic—in his life as the husband of Mary and the foster father of Jesus.

¹⁷ See Wojtyła, "Św. Józef," 83. See, especially, St. Teresa of Jesus, *The Life, Relations, Maxims and Foundations Written by the Saint*, ed. J.J. Burke (New York: The Columbus Press, 1911), 32 (chapter 6, par. 12 of *The Life of S. Teresa*).

¹⁸ Wojtyła, "Św. Józef," 83.

Therefore, the “silence” of St. Joseph in Sacred Scripture is not a sign of his irrelevance to the life of Jesus and Mary and their mission of proclaiming the Gospel. Quite the contrary, this silence expresses his attitude of loving, wonder-filled gaze directed at the mystery of God as manifested in the members of his family. This contemplative attitude is expressed in the words spoken of the Blessed Virgin Mary, that she “kept all these things, pondering them in her heart” (Lk 2:19). St. Joseph fixed his gaze at God who became man—who accepted human life, embraced human work, and entered into the reality of human family. We could even repeat with Wojtyła that while he fixed his gaze on God he was, at the same time, gazing at man: at ordinary human affairs, human work, and family life.¹⁹

Wojtyła observes that St. Joseph’s life is a hidden one, a life marked by fulfilling one’s obligations in *obedience*. Wojtyła seems to be using the word “obedience” (in Polish *posłuszeństwo*, from *szuchać* or *słyszeć*— to listen or to hear) to express Joseph’s contemplative attitude. It is this attitude of listening upon which all the St. Joseph’s actions in the world rely. The richness of this type of life can be understood only from within (*ad intra*), on the foundation of the person’s contemplative union with God. This interior union, however, has an exterior dimension, the dimension to which we now turn.

Work: The Exterior Aspect of St. Joseph’s Life

We can call the exterior aspect of St. Joseph’s significance—the *ad extra* dimension—the social dimension, thus distinguishing it from the contemplative aspect. This social aspect is most readily recognized, as here we see St. Joseph as the head of the family at Nazareth. As is well known, the family is the elementary cell of any society, nation, country, and the Church. Being the head of the Holy Family, St. Joseph works to sustain it and protect it from any dangers or enemies who threaten it. This fact is expressed especially in the image of Joseph the Worker, for his profession was that of carpentry or masonry, as Scripture tells us. Also, we have the image of Joseph the Protector or Patron. Wojtyła notes that the Church’s celebration of St. Joseph shows how close she wishes to be to all people and the most fundamental matters of human life.

However, this social aspect—as it is achieved and manifested through work—possesses a fundamentally personal and theological character. On the one hand, the work performed outside the family is not merely an epiphenomenon of the family life. Rather, although dependent on man,

¹⁹ See Karol Wojtyła’s homily in Kraków, the Church of St. Joseph, on March 19, 1968.

work in all its kinds—the intellectual and physical, the creative and mass-produced—has its own worth or value. St. Joseph is a man who realizes this value in his life and, thereby, appreciates human labor in the dimension of temporality. If human work is a vocation of man, this vocation not only pertains to human fate in its secular dimension but also, precisely in its secular character, becomes a vessel for manifesting and fulfilling the divine *benepiacitum*, as I have already observed.

On the other hand, his work bears great significance for the Church’s mission in the world. St. Joseph’s work, done for the sake of keeping his family alive, entered the plan of our salvation. The Second Vatican Council summarized the soteriological significance of human work with its famous statement on the instrumentality of the humanity of Jesus:

For by His incarnation the Son of God has united Himself in some fashion with every man. He worked with human hands, He thought with a human mind, acted by human choice and loved with a human heart.²⁰

By analogy, and taking into account the interior and exterior aspects of St. Joseph’s life and work, we can safely say that the plan of salvation proceeded through the heart and hands of St. Joseph. The foster father of Jesus teaches that our work in this world is not just our fate but can also become a means of salvation—a path toward eternal life, as Wojtyła observes.²¹ The essential thing to note here is the relational aspect of human work, as seen in St. Joseph, who works not in separation from or indifference to others but for the sake of others and, most importantly, from within his relations to others. Therefore, by working in the world, St. Joseph not only performed necessary acts to provide for his family (by drawing from the world) but also effected a transformation of the world in the image of the Triune God (by introducing his family into the world, as it were, through nourishing the world with his skill). This transformation is most beneficial to the world and its development. For these reasons, the life of the humble spouse and father from Nazareth echoes the already-quoted words of Christ: “the Son can do nothing of his own accord, but only what he sees the Father doing; for whatever he does, that the Son does likewise” (Jn 5:19).

²⁰ Vatican II, *Gaudium et spes*, 22.

²¹ See Wojtyła, “Uroczystość św. Józefa-Robotnika – 1 Maja,” 15.

Encountering God in the Family and Human Work

St. Joseph's significance for today's life finds its source in his closeness to the mysteries of God that he encountered in the Holy Family. This personal encounter is a sort of contemplation, though it emphasizes the relational and reciprocal character of the "I" facing the other (the "thou," or even the "we"). This "facing the other" is actually an "interaction"—another important feature of encounter. To encounter means an active, dynamic state in which persons engage in some kind of communication or even dialog. In order for this communication to happen, they have to be present to each other, close to each other. This feature of encounter is precisely what Wojtyła wished to convey by noting St. Joseph's closeness to the divine mysteries. Another important feature of encounter is the possibility of imitation. Encounter enables discipleship, in which one can recognize the true goodness of the person-master and follow (or imitate) him. Finally, an encounter involves the whole person, who is taken, as it were, into the sphere of the other and into his relations. We can see how closely the features of encounter align with those of imitation, as seen above. The key point here is that the encounter with God in the family continues in human work.

The imitation of St. Joseph, even in his exterior dimension of work, both confirms and elevates every man's work, manifesting its significance and value. Wojtyła notes the "transitive" and "intransitive" moments of human work by quoting Scripture.²² In its *ad extra* aspect, man transforms the face of the earth by his labor in accord with God's mandate directed to the first man and woman: "Fill the earth and subdue it" (Gen 1:28). Wojtyła understands this command as a task given to man to continue the work of creation by completing it. This "completion," he explains, means deriving new values from creation by shaping it through work. Of course, Wojtyła also stresses the *ad intra* dimension of work. By his work, man not only transforms and conquers the world but also transforms and conquers himself. Hence, Scripture teaches, "in your patience you will possess your souls" (Luke 21:19).²³ According to the Polish prelate, this passage also reveals the moment of suffering in human work (in both its exterior and interior aspects)—namely, that work entails effort, and a certain attrition of self.

Perhaps the words of one of Wojtyła's favorite Polish poets, Cyprian Kamil Norwid, can provide a suitable conclusion to our reflections in this part. As I have attempted to show,

²² See *ibid.*

²³ This translation is taken from the Vulgate: "*In patientia vestra possidebitis animas vestras.*" The RSV renders this as, "By your endurance you will gain your lives."

the justification for imitating St. Joseph lies in the union of the interior and exterior dimensions of human existence within the context of an ongoing conversation with God. In his poem *Promethidion*, Norwid describes this union in two lines:

Beauty exists that we might be enticed to work;
Work, that we might be resurrected.²⁴

In other words, the beauty we now contemplate in wonder enables and motivates us to act in this world, and our work here on earth springs forth in us, bearing fruit in eternal life. We see a certain *exitus–reditus* dynamic operative here. Beauty, which finds its source in the mystery of God, spurs us to work toward the eschaton. Note how the poet’s linking between beauty and work affirms the moral (personal and transformative) value of the work that leads to resurrection—that is, to eternal existence in Jesus Christ.

A Digression: In Actione Contemplativus

Let me now offer a small digression concerning the values of the active and the contemplative life. The imitation of St. Joseph, as I have presented it here, means an appreciation of the active life (as signified by his work outside of the family) precisely because of its intrinsic reference to the interior life (as signified by his intimacy with the mystery of the Holy Family). I see the exterior work as a two-directional movement. On the one hand, work is a kind of remembrance of the family in the outside world. On the other hand, this same work is a sort of being “shaped toward” or being conformed (configured) to that family. In other words, the value of the *ad extra* aspect of existence is understood as a contemplation through action. A brief look at St. Thomas and Hans Urs Von Balthasar will elucidate my point.

In his discussion on whether a religious order devoted to the contemplative life is more excellent than one given to the active life, St. Thomas Aquinas assigns the highest position to the orders devoted to preaching and teaching, ranking them above those devoted to contemplation. In his hierarchy, third place belongs to those orders that are occupied with external actions.²⁵

²⁴ From *Dialogue I*: “Bo piękno na to jest by zachwycało / Do pracy – praca, by się zmartwychwstało.” See Cyprian Kamil Norwid, *Wybór wierszy* (Warszawa: Krajowa Agencja Wydawnicza, 1989).

²⁵ *Summa theologiae* II–II, q. 188, a. 6.

Aquinas explains that the action which flows from the fullness of contemplation is to be preferred to simple contemplation, while simple contemplation is greater than an outward occupation of service (such as receiving guests, serving food, and the like). Likely bearing in mind the imitation of our Lord Jesus, he says that as it is better to enlighten than merely to shine, so too is it better to hand on to others the object of one's contemplation than merely to contemplate it. (Incidentally, this also conforms to the relational character of Christianity we mentioned earlier.) Again, this "fruition" is not merely the product of reflection but is itself the object contemplated.²⁶

In one of his works, Hans Urs von Balthasar critiques this traditional hierarchy of values concerning religious orders by indicating the danger of pitting the active life against the contemplative, and vice versa.²⁷ This danger arises when emphasizing the superiority of the activity of the spirit, which has its end in itself over its enslavement to earthly activity. Namely, this emphasis may create an undue superiority of what is inner and personal compared to what is external and social, of what is directed above man (*actio immanens*) versus that concerned with the earthly and human (*actio transiens*). As a consequence, there may arise a neglect of the neighbor, hence a decrease in love. According to Balthasar, an idea of contemplation shared with the Greeks is too individualistic and intellectualistic.²⁸ Instead, he proposes a solution in which the two dispositions, contemplative and active, mutually condition each other so that action becomes the fulfillment of contemplation. In light of understanding Christ's actions as simply the expression of his contemplation—in other words, as the form of contemplation—Balthasar suggests the Ignatian formula *in actione contemplativus* as more fitting for Christian life and presupposing the Thomistic *actio ex plenitudine contemplationis derivatur*.²⁹ We can fittingly apply Balthasar's solution to the life of St. Joseph. Accordingly, his work becomes a particular contemplation of divine mysteries—a constant prayer (see 1 Thess 5:17).

²⁶ Hence, St. Thomas says, *sicut enim maius est illuminare quam lucere solum, ita maius est contemplata aliis tradere quam solum contemplari*. See *ibid.*, II–II, q. 188, a. 6.

²⁷ H.U. von Balthasar, *The Word Made Flesh: Explorations in Theology* (San Francisco: Ignatius Press, 1989), 229.

²⁸ *Ibid.*, 238.

²⁹ *Ibid.*, 230, 234–35, and 238. See Thomas Aquinas, *Summa theologiae* II–II, q. 188, a. 6.

Part 3: Personal Loci of this Imitation

The above principle of imitating St. Joseph also demonstrates the reason for this imitation. As I have mentioned above, this reason lies in his person being the “key” between human affairs and divine mysteries. Of course, the imitation of St. Joseph in his interior and exterior dimensions entails his personal perfections. As I explained in the introduction, this article will not discuss Joseph’s personal virtue in detail, even though all his perfections can be easily associated with those that will be discussed in this part. Below, I will consider several areas that particularly pertain to our topic, starting with the problem of masculinity.³⁰

Masculinity and the Church’s Activity

Wojtyła recognizes that the person of St. Joseph provides ample material for reflections on the essence of masculinity. The previous reflections on the *ad extra* and *ad intra* aspects of St. Joseph’s life and activity provide the basis for our considerations here. Wojtyła begins his reflections on masculinity with the external aspect as the more visible one. He associates this aspect with apostolic activity, since the apostles were men (males) who were called and sent to continue Christ’s work by creating and organizing his Church. Their successors—bishops, along with their priests and deacons—continue this work. This social-religious mission entrusted to men (males) is most active and evidently “exterior.” Their unique participation in Christ’s magisterial, priestly, and governing offices entails elements of spiritual struggle and conquest. Their responsibility for proclaiming the Gospel is inevitably linked with an offensive and defensive attitude. However, it is evident that the striving for “domination,” as characterized by masculinity, is, in Wojtyła’s opinion, balanced and, so to speak, purified by the reality of service.³¹ One could rightly conclude that the drive for struggle and conquest was given to the man (male) for the sake of service. Every man

³⁰ Wojtyła speaks of the “problem of masculinity,” taking “problem” to mean a subject matter for inquiry and not hinting at the nonsensical opinion that there is something intrinsically wrong or toxic with being male. What is of interest here is that Wojtyła discusses masculinity in reference to not femininity but to St. Joseph and his relation to God and his mysteries. This “vertical” vision of masculinity to some degree explains and substantiates its reality.

³¹ Clearly, the proper integration of both service and struggle (domination) is indispensable for full and mature masculinity. It seems to me that the loss or rejection of the latter results in effeminate men—concerned with others to the detriment of their own identity—whereas the loss or rejection of the former produces brutish men, concerned only with themselves and their self-serving goals. The imitation of St. Joseph corrects such extremes in men as it also removes the danger of clericalism in the ordained. Another strong biblical model of masculinity that comes to mind here is St. Paul.

(male) is called to be a servant—one who carries out his responsibility for others, especially his spouse and children.

According to the Polish prelate, the image of St. Joseph both transcends and complements this social-apostolic dimension of masculinity. In addition to being a protector, a defender, and a provider, St. Joseph is primarily a caretaker, a guardian, a spouse, and a father. This spousal and paternal dimension, which highlights his interiority, seems to Wojtyła more fundamental than any external social, organizational, or administrative activity. Every man (male) is called to be a spouse, to be betrothed, to be a bridegroom. In other words, the man must be oriented inward—toward his beloved, toward his marriage and family—before, and while, he is turned outward toward the world. As we learn from Sacred Scripture, the person of St. Joseph unites both attitudes within himself in a natural and effective manner, thus shedding light on the proper understanding of masculinity. Wojtyła concludes that

Man should be not only a social activist, an organizer, proclaimer and defender of an idea, but also a father and caretaker. Otherwise, he does not realize the whole moral fullness of his masculine individuality.³²

Therefore, this unitive principle (between the *ad extra* and *ad intra* dimensions of St. Joseph's life as a man) should be applied to the activity of the Church today. Wojtyła sees that all external, social-administrative activity of men (males) in the Church must be permeated with the spirit of fatherhood or care. Otherwise, such activity—even impressive in its external expression—will be inevitably afflicted with interior emptiness. Man is truly apostolic only when he is, first and foremost, paternal or caring. Any man (male)—not just ordained clergy—is fully himself when he unites these two aspects in his person. Consequently, interpersonal and social relations cultivated on the basis of this union will develop harmoniously in a manner worthy of human persons. In other words, this is how Wojtyła imagines love to be realized in a masculine manner.

³² Wojtyła, “Św. Józef,” 85. In light of this Wojtylian view of St. Joseph, I consider associating masculinity with exteriority and femininity with contemplative interiority in its various biological, psychological, and religious contexts to be an oversimplification.

A Word on Femininity

Even though Wojtyła does not speak on femininity when discussing St. Joseph’s significance for mankind, let me make a couple of observations in light of the above dimensions of masculinity. By pointing out the social-activist (*ad extra*) and spousal and fatherly (*ad intra*) aspects of masculinity, Wojtyła does not wish to deny women their role in transforming the world outwardly and in their capacity as caregivers. Like men, women are called to contemplate the divine mysteries and draw on them—or, better, embody them—in their actions. However, their attitude, which we could best describe as “Marian,” after the Blessed Virgin Mary, who is its epitome, is concerned with reception and cultivation rather than struggle and domination.³³ The heart of the feminine attitude is its service of life in the most intimate manner. According to Wojtyła, the woman is the servant of life, while the man is the servant of this servant. Of course, by this service, he himself also serves life—the very life that he initiated and that his beloved spouse received and nurtures. Whatever St. Joseph, as the true spouse of Mary and the foster father to Jesus, does outside his family is done from within it and for its sake. Again, this action is detrimental neither to masculine receptivity nor to the outside world, but it greatly enriches both.

Being Just with Respect to the Lord

As I have indicated above, Wojtyła recognizes the link between divine mysteries and human affairs, for which St. Joseph is a “key.” However, instead of discussing principles of contemplative and active life and providing a solution for integrating them, Wojtyła presents St. Joseph’s life as both a model of integration and a model for imitation. Together with Sacred Scripture (Mt 1:19), the Church calls St. Joseph *just* or *righteous* (δικαιος). Traditionally, to be just in this context means that Joseph was “adorned with virtue.”³⁴ Without denying this interpretation, Wojtyła does not focus on the saint’s habits. Instead, he calls him “just with respect to God,” by which he refers to Joseph’s interior attitude. What he means is that St. Joseph gave himself—and everything that was needed—to God in order to fulfill God’s plan. Wojtyła explains what he means by being just with

³³ In his *Theology of the Body*, John Paul II interprets Eph 5:22, in which St. Paul calls wives to be subject to their husbands. According to the Polish pope, this “submission” is the wife’s openness to being loved by the husband. He explains that “*the husband* is above all *the one who loves*, and the wife, by contrast, is *the one who is loved*. One might even venture the idea that the wife’s ‘submission’ to the husband, understood in the context of the whole of Ephesians 5:22–23, means above all ‘the experiencing of love’.” See John Paul II, *Man and Woman He Created Them: A Theology of the Body*, trans. by M. Waldstein (Boston: Pauline Books & Media, 2006), 92:6.

³⁴ See, for instance, Filas, *Joseph*, 20.

respect to God the Creator in his book *Love and Responsibility*.³⁵ There, he asks about how man can repay the debt for everything he received from God—most fundamentally, his existence and nature—if “to be just” means to give back what is due to the other. He arrives at the following conclusion:

When man reflects on all this from the point of view of justice with respect to the Creator, the following conclusion arises: if I want to be fully just with respect to God the Creator, I should direct toward him all that is in me, my whole being, for he has the first right to all this.³⁶

The Polish thinker also points out that even this returning of everything is insufficient to obtain a level of equality between man and God. In his opinion, only love can bring a certain equality, as love is a complete surrender and belonging to an other. In other words, Wojtyła recognizes the great love that St. Joseph had for his Creator when he calls him “just with respect to God.” This love, as a fruit of encounter, is worth imitating.

The Humility of Always Being a Child

Let me further develop the context of sonship we discovered above while discussing the essence of imitation. In light of our sacramental understanding of St. Joseph’s work, I want to highlight one more reason for following him: St. Joseph’s *humility*. Although we do not know whether—and to what extent—his *ad extra* actions were illuminative or enlightening to others, whether inside or outside the Holy Family, we must hold that his acts were performed for the sake of his family. Joseph’s silence, in which he performed his tasks, expresses his humility. This obedient silence confirms the contemplative attitude of justice—of which I have just spoken—that every father should acquire in his work. To be silent here means to discover and to wonder at the divine mystery present in one’s own work. This silence is an expression of not only man’s contingency and dependence on God the Creator, but also his total entrustment to him. It reminds man of his existential depth—that is, that he is a creature proceeding from God the Trinity. Wojtyła links

³⁵ K. Wojtyła, *Love and Responsibility*, trans. by G. Ignatik (Boston: Pauline Books & Media, 2013).

³⁶ *Ibid.*, 235.

the reality of fatherhood with that of becoming a child in his 1964 mystical drama *Radiation of Fatherhood*.³⁷

At the beginning of our reflections, I displayed the greatness of St. Joseph in the fact that God entrusted to him his Son, his mother, his family, as well as other divine mysteries. These mysteries include not only the mystery of the Incarnation, but also those of man's redemption and of the Church. Therefore, Wojtyła calls Joseph "a man of divine entrustment." Moreover, God the Father entrusts not only all these, but also his own fatherhood to the man Joseph.³⁸ He chooses St. Joseph to be a true father to his Son! However, all these objective facts alone are insufficient to describe the greatness of Joseph and his life. What is most relevant here is his interior attitude toward all that God entrusted to him. In other words, the correlative aspect of God's entrustment is St. Joseph's interior attitude of *responsibility* as his response to it. The "silent" actions undertaken to care for and protect Christ and his mother are signs of his responsibility. In his *opus magnum*, *Person and Act*, Wojtyła speaks of responsibility as a person's conscious response to values in truth, which entails their affirmation and cultivation.³⁹ In his *Radiation of Fatherhood*, the Polish poet portrays the moment of accepting fatherly responsibility by the protagonist Adam.⁴⁰ Wojtyła describes this responsibility as a sort of perichoresis—a reciprocal possession of the other in one's heart. Adam's fatherly responsibility for Monika is deeply bound with love, that is, with his appreciation of her value as a person and as his daughter. As a father, St. Joseph must have shared such an interior attitude with respect to his adopted son Jesus and his wife Mary.

Together with this responsibility, St. Joseph undertook the mission of the Redeemer and the goal of redemption. In other words, St. Joseph was not only conscious of the mystery he encountered, but he also participated in it. What is of key importance for us now is that this mystery is not just his personal involvement with Christ, although this definitely occurred. The mystery here is the fact of St. Joseph's life in the Holy Family. We could say that because he was an integral

³⁷ See K. Wojtyła, "Radiation of Fatherhood," in: K. Wojtyła, *The Collected Works and Writings on Theatre*, trans. by B. Taborski (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1987), 339, 362.

³⁸ See Wojtyła's sermon delivered in Kraków, the Church of St. Joseph, on March 19, 1974.

³⁹ See, for instance, Wojtyła, *Person and Act*, 272.

⁴⁰ See Wojtyła, "Radiation of Fatherhood," 333–364. After reflecting on his solitude and the reality of the child, Adam still finds fatherhood burdensome. But once he enters into a dialogue with his adopted child Monika and feels the obligation to protect her from a poisonous viper that surprised them on their walk, he becomes aware of interiorly accepting the responsibility of fatherhood. Both the father and the child become aware that they find themselves in each other's heart and grow in this mutual belonging. They express this perichoresis by the word "mine": "my father," "my child."

member of this family—this body—which God made for the sake of his Son and for the sake of redemption, Joseph, in both his person and his work, was also integral to this mystery being realized in history.

Fatherhood as Making a Home

Just a moment ago, I spoke of God making the Holy Family, which by no means contradicts the truth that St. Joseph, as the head of that family, was the one who helped shape it. By entrusting his family to St. Joseph, God entrusted him not only with the task of serving his family, but also—in some sense—with that of building it. This is the task entrusted to all human fathers (as well as to mothers, though differently), especially with respect to the external dimension of the familial community that we call “home.” Wojtyła affirms that St. Joseph is a model for all husbands and fathers precisely because their vocational task is to create a human home—a familial home. The Polish prelate stresses that “home” is not merely a place but also a community, a community with a particular atmosphere of mutual presence, closeness, and support. This familial home is also familiar: it is the proper place for human beings to live and grow together. Therefore, Wojtyła calls home “the fundamental strength of man.”⁴¹ Our Lord Jesus lived at home with Mary and Joseph for thirty years, thus affirming that this home provided strength for him—the Son of God—as well. Consequently, as Wojtyła remarks, a homeless man is, in a sense, unbalanced or shaken in his own humanity, in his human vocation. Such a man misses the gift of parental love, conjugal love, and filial love—both with respect to himself as well as others (namely, his parents, spouse, and children).

Part 4: Application of this Imitation to Priesthood

Encountering God in the Family

To imitate St. Joseph, then, means two things for priests. First, it means continuing one’s encounter with the Trinity. This encounter consists in approaching the Father in the Holy Spirit through participation in the sacred mysteries in the person of Christ the Son. This participation will be both habitual and actual. Second, this imitation is to be realized in the world by encountering others in communion: to be consistent with the language used here, in any network of relations.

⁴¹ See Karol Wojtyła’s homily given in Kraków, the Church of St. Joseph, on March 19, 1976.

As St. Joseph encountered the divine mystery of the Trinity within his life in the Holy Family, the priest is to live his contemplative encounter with God from within the various relations in which he exists in a particular time and space. These relations are many: his immediate and extended family in which he was raised, his parish or parishes to which he belonged and in which he serves, his community of friends and brother priests, his diocese, and his country as a whole. In other words, the imitation of St. Joseph entails entering the world and making God the Father present from within worldly families—that is, within the various relations and institutions of this world. This imitation is, namely, a true *contemplata aliis tradere*—a true tradition (handing on) of what is contemplated.

Witness Through Work

What I have said about the significance of St. Joseph—his life and work—has a profound application to the life and work of the Catholic priest.⁴² The work of the priest has both external (social and apostolic) and internal (spiritual and contemplative) aspects. Furthermore, it is performed in the world and for the world, though its primary concern is the human person and his union with God.⁴³ And because this union cannot be achieved outside the human heart, the work of priests and bishops is called “pastoral.” That is, they are pastors and guardians of souls in the likeness of Jesus Christ (see 1 Pt 2:25). This is why the imitation of St. Joseph is so important for priestly formation and pastoral ministry. By imitating St. Joseph, the seminarian and the priest draw their work from the mystery of the invisible God and apply it to their actions, thereby transforming this world and their own selves in the likeness of Christ. In other words, the imitation of St. Joseph roots the priest in the sacramental dimension of Christ’s mission on earth. To put it differently, this imitation grounds the priest in the mystery of the Incarnation—the union and reconciliation of God and man in Jesus Christ—without neglecting or overemphasizing its human and divine dimensions, that is, the aspects of the sign and grace. St. Joseph is worthy of imitation because, in his person, Divine Providence expressed what is closest to every man and linked that to the eternal, divine plan of salvation. This means that, by imitating St. Joseph, priests become—like him—closest to what is dearest to every man: family and work. They continue building their

⁴² Although Wojtyła does not explicitly make this reference, he discusses the work of the priest in his homily given for the feast of St. Joseph in Podgórze, the Church of St. Joseph, on May 1, 1969.

⁴³ See the secular aspect of the work of the priest in Vatican II documents, for instance, in *Lumen gentium* 28 and 31, as well as *Presbyterorum ordinis* 3 and 9 (“placed in the midst of the laity”).

parish and diocesan family by their ministry, while at the same time supporting the family and the work of those entrusted to their care.

Priest and Human Vocation

In his 1976 retreat for the papal household, entitled *Sign of Contradiction*, Wojtyła presents priesthood as a reminder of, or expression of, the fundamental vocation of man. The priest is a response to man's perennial questions about the meaning of his existence and that of the whole world. As a part of this retreat, Wojtyła says,

Priesthood is an expression of the meaning given to man and the world by their relationship with God. And the profoundest of truths about man and the world is that they both belong to God, Creator and Redeemer...The priesthood in particular is the form of self-expression of the man for whom the world's ultimate meaning can be found only in the dimension of the transcendental: in turning towards God who, as the fulness of personal Being, in himself transcends the world. Without relationship and without self-giving, the whole of human existence on earth loses its meaning.⁴⁴

On the other hand, this attitude frees the priest from being preoccupied with results. Cardinal Ratzinger expressed this point when, in his reflection on the Cross of Christ, he noted that "Success" is not another name for God.⁴⁵ To imitate the "silent" St. Joseph means to speak the whole truth to God concerning one's own being. In a certain sense, this means having time only for God—to use it for him and not just for oneself. Cardinal Ratzinger notices precisely this fact when he says:

The speechlessness of a human being who is able to say nothing more to God can become a prayer, if this very speechlessness is brought before the God who listens.⁴⁶

⁴⁴ K. Wojtyła, *Sign of Contradiction* (New York: The Seabury Press, 1979), 130, 132.

⁴⁵ J. Ratzinger, "The Eucharist—Heart of the Church," in: J. Ratzinger, *Theology of the Liturgy: The Sacramental Foundation of Christian Existence*, trans. by J. Saward, et al. (San Francisco: Ignatius Press, 2014), 259.

⁴⁶ J. Ratzinger, "Praying in Our Time," in: J. Ratzinger, *Dogma and Preaching: Applying Christian Doctrine to Daily Life* (San Francisco: Ignatius Press, 2011), 115. See *ibid.*, 116.

Priest as a Sign of the Times

It is a well-known fact that the authentic signs of God’s presence and purpose are to be discerned (and not merely detected) in the happenings, needs, and desires of the modern age by scrutinizing and interpreting the signs of the times in light of the Gospel.⁴⁷ However, the priest of today should not merely be formed to pass judgment on these signs. He himself should be a sign of the times! In my estimation, he will become one when he imitates good models of fatherhood, such as that of St. Joseph. Of course, in imitating St. Joseph the priest creates God’s home—he builds God’s house—the House of Joseph. It is his task. As we saw Wojtyła pointing out, this house is more than a place, it is a community with a climate of mutual closeness, communication, and support, and with growth in humanity and holiness. In his pastoral ministry, the priest—as a spouse to the Church and a father to God’s people—is to create and build such a home wherever he is. Only then will he become a sign of hope, a sign of the times in the sense of being a sign for the times.

Conclusion

On the one hand, God listened to St. Joseph and chose him so as to make him “lord of his house and ruler of all his possessions” (Ps. 105:21). He also supported and guided him. On the other hand, in St. Joseph we see the proper relation to God (the contemplative encounter and total entrustment) and the proper relation to the world (transforming it in the image of God through work). The imitation of this man entails an integration of these relations in one’s life together with others—a life of communion in a family—which is a true conversation with God.

⁴⁷ See, for instance, Vatican II, *Gaudium et spes*, 4, 11, 44. For more detail on the signs of the times, especially in the thought of Karol Wojtyła, see Ignatik, *Communicating Life*, 148–151.

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**The Perfection of Powers and Integration of the Person:
St. Thomas Aquinas and Karol Wojtyła on Virtue**

Jove Jim Aguas¹

Abstract

One of the main influences on Karol Wojtyła, or St. John Paul II, is St. Thomas Aquinas; at the very foundation of Wojtyła's philosophy is a profound understanding of St. Thomas's philosophy, which served as an anchor as Wojtyła navigated through the philosophy of phenomenology. One common notion or concept that both philosophers wrote extensively about is virtue, which is the focus of this paper. By relating and synthesizing their respective notions, a positive and more holistic understanding of virtue can be provided. While they have their respective notions of virtue, owing to their respective philosophical backgrounds, they both offer valuable insights into the nature and importance of virtue in achieving human flourishing, developing the moral well-being of individuals, and forming moral character. Generally, for St. Thomas, virtue is the perfection of power, which for Wojtyła or St. Pope John Paul II is moral proficiency expressed in the integration of the person. This paper is divided into four parts: the first is a general discussion on virtue, the second is a discussion of St. Thomas' notions of habit and virtue, the third is Wojtyła's notion of human act and virtue, the fourth is an attempt at synthesizing the thoughts of St. Thomas and Wojtyła on virtue.

Keywords

Karol Wojtyła, St. Thomas Aquinas, virtue, human person, reason

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Introduction

The moral decay we are experiencing in our society today can be traced to the lack or absence of moral character in our society. The increasing dishonesty, lack of integrity, decline in respect for human dignity and life, the breakdown of family and social structures and values, the rise in social injustice, prevalence of materialism and moral relativism, increasing crime and violence, normalization of corruption, and predominance of fake news are all indicative of moral decay—that is, the absence or decline in moral standards and values. While there are many reasons for this moral decay, it ultimately points to the absence of moral character in our society, and this very absence of moral character points to the absence of virtue. Virtue is the foundation of moral character, and when virtue is not rightly and fully developed, there is no foundation on which to build moral character.

Moral character is the individual's thought patterns, feelings, actions, and behavior, which reflect one's moral values; it manifests the individual's commitment to ethical principles and values and encompasses virtues such as honesty, integrity, respect, compassion, courage, self-control, and truthfulness. A person with strong moral character acts morally and ethically because they have developed the virtues that guide them in decision-making and actions in daily life and in various situations. A morally upright person is predisposed to act and behave in an ethical manner.

Virtue is the cornerstone of strong moral character. Generally, virtue is a developed habit—a permanent disposition that becomes part of the character of the person. However, there are various understandings of habit, which makes our understanding of virtue problematic. The modern understanding of habit is often framed more in the context of psychology, where it is considered as actions that are triggered automatically in response to contextual cues associated with performance.² In social psychology, it is understood as an “organized response to stimuli.” Through interstimulation, feeling, thinking, and learning, these actions become organized into habits, and habit-building modifies original human nature and gives acquired nature its characteristic forms and meanings.³ This understanding of habit reduces it to the level of the involuntary and nonrational. In the general understanding, the real meaning of virtue has lost its significance in modern times—to the point that being virtuous is often

² D.T. Neal, W. Wood, J.S. Labrecque, P. Lally, “How do habits guide behavior? Perceived and Actual Triggers of Habits in Daily Life,” *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology* Vol. 48 (2012), 492–498.

³ E.S. Bogardus, *Fundamentals of Social Psychology* (New York: Century, 1924), 34–44 (Chapter 4: “Habitual Nature”).

interpreted as abstaining from joyful living. For example, a woman may be considered virtuous or may consider herself very virtuous because she neither drinks nor smokes; a man may consider himself virtuous if he abstains from sex. While these may be manifestations of a virtuous character, they represent a very narrow understanding of virtue. This can be attributed to a very rigid moral tradition or interpretation of morality. Being virtuous is often equated with a narrow moral attitude that is judgmental toward others. In the end, virtue has lost its real and true meaning, which, etymologically speaking, is more than the narrow understanding of being abstinent or temperate.

The motivation of this paper is to bring to the fore the philosophical meaning of virtue through the notions of St. Thomas Aquinas and Karol Wojtyła. Through this, a positive and more holistic understanding of virtue can be provided. While each has their respective notions of virtue due to their respective philosophical backgrounds, both offer valuable insights into the nature and importance of virtue in achieving human flourishing, developing the moral well-being of individuals, and forming moral character. Generally, for St. Thomas, virtue is the perfection of power; for Wojtyła (St. Pope John Paul II), it is moral proficiency expressed in the integration of the person. This paper is divided into four parts: first, a general discussion on virtue; second, a discussion of St. Thomas's notions of habit and virtue; third, Wojtyła's notion of the human act and virtue; and fourth, a synthesis of the thoughts of St. Thomas and Wojtyła on virtue.

The term virtue comes from the Latin root *vir*, for man, and *virtus*, which originally meant manliness, strength, or valor, but over time this term came to mean moral excellence. Thus, virtue denotes moral excellence based on right action and right thinking, producing goodness of character. It is an essential quality of a person that defines the human goodness of the individual. Deeply rooted in human character, virtue is a capacity that can be developed.⁴ According to Alasdair MacIntyre, a virtuous practice is a complex form of socially established cooperative human activity that systematically extends, elevates, or amplifies human powers to achieve excellence.⁵

The first articulation of the nature of virtue can be traced to the Greek thinkers, who developed theories for evaluating conduct based on the excellence of an individual's character. For Socrates, the good life consists in the practice of the virtues; for him, virtue is knowledge. Plato, following his mentor Socrates, associated virtue with self-control and freedom from desires. In answering the question

⁴ D. Bright, B. Winn, J. Kanov, "Reconsidering Virtue: Differences of Perspectives in Virtue Ethics and the Positive Social Sciences," *Journal of Business Ethics* Vol. 119 (2014), 445-460.

⁵ A. MacIntyre, *After Virtue: A Study in Moral Theory* (3rd Edition) (Notre Dame, Indiana: University of Notre Dame Press, 2007), 187.

“What is the good life?”, Plato, following Socrates’s dictum, affirmed that “virtue is knowledge.”⁶ He developed the thesis that a life of reason is the happiest and the best. Knowledge produces a harmonious person, and an orderly, well-balanced personality results when reason governs desires and passions. A virtuous person—that is, a rational individual—is one who is truly happy.⁷

Likewise, Aristotle relates virtue to happiness. For him, happiness is not a passive state to be achieved, but it characterizes what we do and how we do it.⁸ The way to happiness involves knowing the right principles to follow and applying them in real life. For Aristotle, the performance of an activity must accord with virtue or excellence. Virtue refers to the excellence of a thing or its disposition to perform its proper function effectively. Thus, virtue or excellence is attained through repeated action that perfects the function. In his two treatises on ethics, the *Nicomachean Ethics* and the *Eudemean Ethics*, Aristotle begins with a discussion of *eudaimonia*, which means “happiness” or “flourishing,”⁹ and then turns to an examination of the nature of *arête*—“virtue” or “excellence”—and the character traits that human beings need in order to live life to its fullest.

In the East, Chinese sages like Confucius also stressed the importance of cultivating virtues as the foundation of a good ethical and social life. Central to Confucian teaching is the cultivation of human virtues. Every normal human being cherishes the aspiration to become a superior man—a sage or *Jun Tzu*. The sage is more than a *literati* or a learned man; he is well rounded, not only literate but also useful to the state and to society. Personal development and cultivation take place in the context of human relationships—particularly within society. So, a fully developed person is one who maintains good relationships with others and is a contributing member of the community. Ritual and filial piety are manners that prescribe how one should act and relate with others, and these should be grounded in an attitude of benevolence or human-heartedness (or *Jen*).

⁶ Plato, “Meno,” in: *Plato: Five Dialogues. Euthyphro, Apology, Crito, Meno, Phaedo* (2nd ed.), trans. by G.M.A. Grube (Indianapolis-Cambridge: Hackett Publishing Company, 2002), 78-79.

⁷ See J.J. Aguas, *The Good and Happy Life: An Introduction to Ethical Systems and Theories* (Manila: UST Publishing House, 2019), 71.

⁸ *Ibid.*, 80

⁹ Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, trans. by W.D. Ross, in: *The Basic Works of Aristotle*, ed. R. McKeon (New York: The Modern Library, 2011), Book I, Chapters 4-7; Aristotle, *Eudemean Ethics*, trans. by P.L.P. Simpson (New Brunswick: Transaction Publishers, 2013), Book II.

St. Thomas on Habit and Virtue

The Nature of Habit

In the *Summa Theologiae* (First Part of the Second Part, Questions 49–67)¹⁰ and in his *Disputed Questions on the Virtues* (DQV),¹¹ St. Thomas Aquinas discusses the nature of virtue. In the *Summa Theologiae*, he provides a causal definition of virtue and characterizes it as a good operative habit. But what is a habit? The term “habit” is derived from the Latin *habere*, meaning “to have” or possess; *habitus* means something that is truly *had* or possessed. To possess something is to have dominion over it and to be able to use it at will. St. Thomas makes the connection between habit and possession by comparing a habit to a possession insofar as we have the thing possessed “at our fingertips.” It is something that we practice until it becomes second nature to us. For example, when we possess the propensity to press the keys on our cellphones, it feels as though typing on the keyboard is literally at our fingertips. Following Averroes, Aquinas emphasizes that “A habit is that by which someone acts when he wills.”¹² Similarly, he quotes St. Augustine: “A habit is that whereby something is done when necessary.”¹³

When applied to the human body, a habit may mean a condition or state of being; when applied to human action, it may indicate a certain deportment or disposition. In the course of our physical development, our body develops certain dispositions, such as our manner of walking or other motor activities. However, St. Thomas clarifies that such operations proceed from the soul through the body. Thus, they belong principally to the soul, and secondarily to the body. Therefore, the dispositions for such operations are principally in the soul, but they can be secondarily in the body.¹⁴ Generally, a habit is an acquired mode of behavior that has become nearly or completely involuntary. It is an almost permanently fixed disposition to act or behave in a certain way. Habits are developed through repetition; thus, they are an effect of repeated acts and create a propensity to reproduce certain acts. This is why we say we possess a habit. Habits, once acquired, are difficult to change and cause an individual to act or behave easily and readily in one way or another. They are more or less stable and provide the facility to

¹⁰ St. Thomas Aquinas, *Summa Theologica*, trans. by Fathers of the English Dominican Province (Benziger Bros. Edition, 1947); henceforth, *ST*.

¹¹ St. Thomas Aquinas, *Disputed Question on the Virtues in General*, trans. by R. McNerny (South Bend, Indiana: St. Augustine’s Press, 1999); henceforth, *DQV*.

¹² Aquinas, *ST*, I.II, 50.5.

¹³ *Ibid.*, I.II, 49.3sc.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*, *ST*, I.II, 50, 1.

act or operate. As a kind of disposition, habit refers to a quality that focuses on human capacities to operate in a specific way.

St. Thomas further elaborates on the nature of habit as a quality or disposition by stressing four specifying features: it is *stable*, *operative*, *valent*, and *nature-directed*. First, habit is a *stable* quality or disposition.¹⁵ St. Thomas regards habit as *difficile mobilis*—that is, a disposition that is difficult to change; it is not an easy-come, easy-go kind of quality. He says: “We call habits those qualities which, by reason of their very nature, are not easily changed, in that they have unchangeable causes.”¹⁶ Habits reside in the faculties as stable dispositions or qualities that dispose the faculties to act in a certain way, depending on the type of habit. A habit is not a “transient quality” but an “immanent quality” of its bearer. One does not become a chain smoker by smoking a single cigarette, nor does one become a generous person by one act of generosity. However, when one becomes a chain smoker, it is difficult to break the habit; similarly, a generous person will always act generously toward others.

Second, a habit is an *operative* quality. Habits are disposed toward acts or operations. By its very nature, habit is related both to an act and to the subject or bearer to which it belongs.¹⁷ Since habits are not directly observable, they can be known only through the acts to which they dispose their bearer.¹⁸ Following Aristotle, St. Thomas states that habits result from repeated acts. He says, “As neither does one swallow nor one day make spring, so neither does one day nor a short time make a man blessed and happy... Therefore, a habit of virtue, and for the same reason other habits, are not caused by one act.”¹⁹ Habits can grow or be diminished. “Repeated acts cause a habit to grow. But if the act falls short of the intensity of the habit, such an act does not dispose to an increase of that habit but rather to a lessening thereof.”²⁰ And since they increase through the same cause that engenders them, so too they diminish by the same cause that corrupts them.²¹ The habit of reading is increased by repeated acts of reading, but such a habit can also be decreased and corrupted by repeated acts of indolence or laziness.

Habits do not only give us the power to act but they give us the power to act readily and with dexterity. A faculty without a habit is the simple power to act; a faculty with a habit is the power to act with perfection. Thus, habits become—or are called—“second nature.” The faculty is like the first nature,

¹⁵ *Ibid.*, I.II 49; see also N. Austin, *Aquinas on Virtue* (Washington, D.C.: Georgetown University Press, 2017), 29-31.

¹⁶ Aquinas, *ST*, I.II, 49.2.

¹⁷ *Ibid.*, I.II 49.3.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*, II.II, 4.1.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, I.II, 51.3.

²⁰ *Ibid.*, I.II, 52. 3.

²¹ *Ibid.*, I.II, 53.2.

and habit is the second. It is something that inclines or disposes us to act or perform our functions perfectly. Reading is a simple power or operation, but when we develop the habit of reading, even difficult texts become easier; and when we perfect the skill of reading, we become excellent readers. For example, the first assigned reading in philosophy may be daunting, but years of reading can make us adept at reading long and difficult texts. Similarly, when we develop the habit of playing online games, we perfect our skills. St. Thomas refers to habit as the “first actuality” of a capacity in that it begins to perfect a potential. But it is not itself the “second actuality” or its full completion in operation.²² Habit, then, is “halfway between pure potentiality and the complete act.”²³ Habits are operative because they are principles of operation. A habit is neither the pure potentiality of some subject nor its complete realization in operation; it is instead something intermediate between the two. “A habit lies midway between potentiality and actualization.”²⁴

Third, a habit has a *valent* quality—that is, one that is either good or bad. For St. Thomas, a habit is never value-neutral; it is “a disposition according to which something is disposed well or badly.”²⁵ Being good or bad belongs to the very concept of habit. Since a habit is a condition or disposition, it is either good or bad. Just as the condition of a body can either be healthy or unhealthy, a habit is either a good or a bad disposition, which belongs to habit’s rationale.²⁶ For St. Thomas, a habit is, by definition, a good or bad state to be in—that is, it is a valent quality. He further states that a good habit is contrary to a bad habit, just as a virtue is contrary to a vice. A good habit or virtue is disposed to an act that is appropriate to the agent’s nature, while a bad habit or a vice is disposed to an act that is inappropriate to the agent’s nature. For instance, acts of virtue, such as wisdom, are appropriate to human nature in that they are in conformity with reason, while acts of vice, such as indolence, are opposed to human nature since they do not conform to reason. Thus, it is clear that habits are distinguished in species according to the difference between good and evil.²⁷

Fourth, St. Thomas claims that habits are qualities that are *nature-directed*. It is important to understand what St. Thomas meant by nature—especially human nature. Nature is dynamic, not static; the nature of a thing is what that thing is, so, generally speaking, “the essence of anything, what its

²² *Ibid.*, I.II 49.3 ad 1.

²³ *Ibid.*, I.II, 50.4.

²⁴ *Ibid.*, I.II 73.1c.

²⁵ *Ibid.*, I.II, 49.2c.

²⁶ *Ibid.*, I.II, 49.2 ad 1.

²⁷ *Ibid.*, I.II, 54.3.

definition signifies, is called a nature.”²⁸ While essence signifies what a thing is as it can be defined and known by the human mind, nature signifies the essence of a thing insofar as it has an order to the proper operation of that thing, since nothing is without its characteristic operation.²⁹ Nature, therefore, refers to a telos—that is, the proper operation of a thing. St. Thomas, in this regard, follows Aristotle’s dictum: nature acts for an end. Human nature entails certain rational powers or capacities oriented to act. However, these powers, in and of themselves, are incomplete and indeterminate—potential, so to speak—and human nature alone is not an adequate principle for a human being’s characteristic operation and flourishing. These rational powers need to be completed by dispositions that complete and perfect them.³⁰ We have the rational power to understand complex ideas, such as philosophical ideas, but we need habits or dispositions to perfect this power. Thus, a human individual can reach his potential through acquiring and exercising human habits. This is what human habits are for: the realization of a human’s incomplete natural powers—that is, the perfection of those potentials or powers.

This is what St. Thomas meant by habits as nature-directed dispositions. He states, “Habit implies a certain disposition in order to a being’s nature, and to its operation or end, according to which disposition it is well or badly disposed to this nature and operation.”³¹ All qualities are “modes” or “determinations” of a subject, and a habit is that specific kind of quality that modifies or determines its subject “in order to the nature of a thing.”³² It is this fourth feature that brings together all the specifying features of habits. Habits are not just a conglomeration of properties; there is an essential core from which the other features flow. It is because habit is a nature-directed disposition that it is stable, operative, and valent.

The Nature of Virtue

With respect to our bodies, we have some powers in common with animals, such as biological powers like nutrition and growth, which are based on our being and not on our acts. But only those powers that are proper to the rational soul—the rational powers—belong to man alone. Hence, human virtue cannot pertain to the body but only to that which is proper to the rational soul. Accordingly, human virtue does not imply an ordering to being but rather to act. It therefore belongs to the very notion of human virtue

²⁸ *Ibid.*, I,II, 29.1 ad 4.

²⁹ Austin, *Aquinas on Virtue*, 38.

³⁰ Aquinas, *ST*, I,II, 55.2c.

³¹ *Ibid.*, I,II, 49.4.

³² *Ibid.*, I,II, 49.2c.

that it be a habit. St. Thomas elaborates: “Virtue denotes a certain perfection of a power. Now, a thing’s perfection is considered chiefly in regard to its end. But the end of power is the act. Wherefore power is said to be perfect insofar as it is determined toward its act.”³³

However, since some powers are determined by their acts to their nature, like the active natural powers—for example, biological powers—they are also called virtues in themselves. On the other hand, the rational powers, which are proper to man, are not determined to one thing but are related indeterminately to many, and they are determined to their acts, so, properly speaking, our rational powers are also virtues. As mentioned already, our rational powers are not determined by one act but by the repetition of acts and so are subject to habits that provide them with perfecting “second natures.” Following Aristotle, St. Thomas says, “Activities cause us to be skilled. But this is through virtue. Therefore, virtue is caused in us by acts.”³⁴

Since habits are value-laden and never value-neutral; they are either good or bad. As previously mentioned, good habits are called virtues, and bad habits are vices. St. Thomas states, “Human virtue, which is an operative habit, is a good habit, and operative of the good.”³⁵ But in what sense is virtue a good habit? According to St. Thomas, “A good habit is one that disposes to an act fitting to the nature of the agent.”³⁶ As human beings, our nature is based on our rational nature. Thus, anything against the order of our rational nature is properly against our nature as human beings, and anything that is in accordance with our rational nature is in accordance with our nature as human beings. St. Thomas concludes, “human virtue, which makes a human being good and his work good, is in accordance with the nature of a human being in as much as it agrees with reason, whereas vice is against the nature of a human being insofar as it is against the order of reason.”³⁷ Hence, “a moral habit has the rationale of human virtue, insofar as it is conformed to reason,”³⁸ while “vice is opposed to virtue because it implies a disposition by which a thing is disposed to that which does not benefit its nature.”³⁹ Hence, virtues are not good because they are in accord with certain external norms of goodness; they are good because they are in accordance with our rational nature as human beings.

³³ *Ibid.*, I.II, 55, 1; *QDV*, 1.

³⁴ *Ibid.*, 9, ad.

³⁵ Aquinas, *ST*, I.II 55.3c.

³⁶ *Ibid.*, I.II, 54.3c.

³⁷ *Ibid.*, I.II, 54.3c.

³⁸ *Ibid.*, I.II, 58.2.

³⁹ Aquinas, *QDV*, 2, ad 10.

Moreover, virtues are not only good habits because they are in accordance with our rational nature: they are good because they imply the perfection of a power. As habits, they enhance and perfect our natural powers. The virtue of temperance enhances or perfects our natural capacity for restraint, and justice enhances our capacity to be fair to others. Now, the virtue of a thing is determined by the maximum that its power is capable of, and the maximum of any power must be what is good because evil implies a defect; thus, vice cannot maximize our power. Human virtue, which is an operative habit, is a good habit and productive of good works,⁴⁰ and vice is not. A virtue improves and perfects a rational faculty, inclining it toward the good—the good of the faculty, of the will, and of the whole man in terms of his ultimate destiny. St. Thomas explains:

Virtue perfects a power with respect to a perfect act. But a perfect act is the end of the power or of the one acting. Hence, virtue makes both the power and the agent good, as was said earlier. Thus, in the definition of virtue, there is something that pertains to the perfection of the act and something that pertains to the perfection of the power or agent.⁴¹

Now, there are two requirements for an act to be perfect: first is that the act be right; second is that the habit cannot be the principle of the contrary act. Hence, a principle of a good and a bad act cannot be a perfect principle of a good act because habit is the perfection of a power. That is why it must be the principle only of a good act and in no way of a bad.⁴²

Virtue is not called good because it itself is a good but because by it, something else is good.⁴³ The moral good refers to the act, the habit, and the object of the act. Similarly, moral evil is said of a bad act, which is a sin, and of a bad habit, which is a vice. Hence, virtue is that which makes the one having it good and makes his act good with moral goodness, while vice is what makes the one having it evil and makes his act evil with moral badness.⁴⁴

⁴⁰ Aquinas, *ST*, I.II, 54.3.

⁴¹ Aquinas, *QDV*, 2.

⁴² *Ibid.*, 2.

⁴³ *Ibid.*, 2, ad 1.

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*, 2, ad 10.

Types of Virtues

For St. Thomas, there are three kinds of virtues: the intellectual virtues, the moral virtues, and the theological virtues. Following Aristotle, St. Thomas enumerates three intellectual virtues: wisdom, which is the knowledge of the highest causes of reality; understanding, which is the capacity to grasp the first principles of demonstration; and science, which is the systematic, demonstrative knowledge of a certain subject matter.⁴⁵ The moral virtues—also referred to as the “cardinal” virtues—are prudence, justice, temperance, and courage.⁴⁶ Prudence is the ability to judge between actions with regard to what is appropriate at a given time—that is, doing the right thing at the right moment and in the right place. Justice is the virtue of giving what is due and is the most extensive virtue. Temperance, also known as restraint, is the practice of self-control, abstention, and moderation, and tempering the appetites. Courage, or fortitude, is forbearance, strength, endurance, and the ability to confront fear, uncertainty, and intimidation.⁴⁷

The theological virtues are faith, hope, and charity. They are theological because they direct us to God.⁴⁸ Faith is the belief in God and in the truth of His revelation, as well as obedience to Him. Hope is the expectation of and desire to receive, refraining from despair, and the capability of not giving up. It is the belief that God will be eternally present in every human’s life and never give up on His love. Charity is a supernatural virtue that helps us love God and our neighbors the same way as we love ourselves.

St. Thomas distinguishes the intellectual and moral virtues from the theological virtues. He states: “The object of the theological virtues is God Himself, Who is the last end of all, as surpassing the knowledge of our reason. On the other hand, the object of intellectual and moral virtues is something comprehensible to human reason. Therefore, the theological virtues are specifically distinct from the moral and intellectual virtues.”⁴⁹ St. Thomas recognizes that theological virtues are infused in man by God.⁵⁰ The infused virtues are independent of human operation; they are directly produced by God in the operative faculties of a man and differ mainly from the acquired because they do not imply the human effort that determines the faculty toward a particular kind of activity, namely, the facility induced by repetition. God Himself pours in the infused virtues. While the habits of virtue are acquired through man’s effort and for his natural perfection in a manner that is connatural to him, man has acquired, by divine

⁴⁵ Aquinas, *ST*, I.II, 57.2.

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*, I.II, 61.2.

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*, I.II, 61.3.

⁴⁸ *Ibid.*, I.II, 62.1.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*, I.I, 62.2.

⁵⁰ Aquinas, *QDV*, 10, respo. 10.

influence beyond the supernatural principles, certain infused virtues by which he is perfected in operations ordered to the end of eternal life.⁵¹

Since habits can be increased and nourished, so can virtues. Acquired virtues are increased and nourished by the acts that cause them. According to Aristotle, a habit is a good virtue—that is, the proper or right way of doing something.⁵² When we repeatedly perform good acts, we develop virtues: human excellences or dispositions to perform or act in a proper manner or way. By consistent efforts to concentrate on a good act and by doing it repeatedly over a long period of time, one gradually develops a permanent disposition to perform such an act, thereby acquiring the virtue. In the case of infused virtues, they are increased by the act of God, by whom they are caused. St. Thomas states: “Our acts dispose for an increase of charity and the infused virtues, as a man at the outset, by doing what is natural to him, prepares and disposes himself to receive charity from God. Subsequent acts can merit an increase in charity because they presuppose charity, which is the principle of merit.”⁵³

Wojtyła’s Notion of Human Act and Virtue

One of the main influences on Karol Wojtyła, or St. John Paul II, was St. Thomas Aquinas; at the very foundation of Wojtyła’s philosophy lies a profound understanding of St. Thomas’s philosophy, which served as an anchor as Wojtyła navigated through the philosophy of phenomenology. However, despite the significant influence of St. Thomas, Wojtyła developed his own notion of virtue as a rich and complex concept that emphasizes the importance of habitual disposition based on the human act, self-determination, reason, and integration. His discussion on virtue offers a deeper understanding of the nature of human action and the importance of moral character. From his thoughts, it is evident that virtue is the foundation of moral life and the source of all moral goodness. Virtue is not something abstract or detached from life; on the contrary, it has deep “roots” in life itself, it springs from life and forms it. Virtue has an impact on a person’s life, actions, and behavior. It follows that, in all these reflections of ours, we are speaking not so much of virtue as of man living and acting “virtuously”; we are speaking

⁵¹ *Ibid.*, 10, respo. 10.

⁵² Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, Book 1, Chapter 13.

⁵³ Aquinas, *DQV*, 10.

of the prudent, just, and courageous man, and finally, precisely today, we are speaking of the “temperate” (or “sober”) man.⁵⁴

The Human Act

Wojtyła notes the slight difference in his use of the term “act” (*czyn*), which he takes exclusively as man’s conscious action, and the term *actus humanus*. The notion of the human act in the traditional sense places more emphasis on deliberateness or voluntariness. In the Aristotelian tradition, human action is primarily an “ethical” category, and the basic considerations are the voluntariness and culpability of the human agent and the ethical character of the action. Hence, human acts must be distinguished from the acts of man, which are involuntary actions. While Wojtyła stresses that “act” (*czyn*) in the Scholastic sense is defined as *actus humanus* or, more specifically, as *actus voluntarius*, his emphasis is on the anthropological importance of the act, that is, the act as revealing the nature of the person. The act (*czyn*) is a concretization of the dynamism proper to the human person because it is accomplished in a manner proper to the free will.⁵⁵ Hence, it is only a man’s deliberate or voluntary act that can be called an “act” or “action.” Furthermore, human action also means conscious action; voluntary action must also be regarded as a conscious act because it is accompanied by consciousness. When we say “voluntary act,” we implicitly refer to the kind of act that is related to the power of free will.⁵⁶ Hence, the phrase “conscious acting” to some extent corresponds to the *actus voluntarius* of Aristotelian and Thomistic philosophy because any action pertaining to the human will must also be conscious.

Wojtyła emphasizes that a man acts or performs an action, which is a fact that is given to us in experience; he adds that the fact that “I act” is an experiential datum. However, this experiential fact is not an isolated fact but must be understood in relation to or in the context of the entire human dynamism, which refers to the totality of man’s experience.⁵⁷ The entire human dynamism includes all of man’s functions, powers, and faculties. However, not all that belongs to human dynamism is reflected in consciousness.⁵⁸ Some functions or powers are not accompanied by consciousness; there are functions

⁵⁴ John Paul II, *General Audience*, Wednesday, 22 November 1978 (https://www.vatican.va/content/john-paul-ii/en/audiences/1978/documents/hf_jp-ii_aud_19781122.html).

⁵⁵ K. Wojtyła, *Person and Act and Related Essays*, “The English Critical Edition of the Works of Karol Wojtyła/John Paul II,” Vol. I, ed. Antonio Lopez, trans. by G. Ignatik (Washington D.C.: The Catholic University of America Press, 2021), 122; henceforth, *PA*.

⁵⁶ Wojtyła, *PA*, 122.

⁵⁷ See J.J. Aguas, *Person, Action and Love: The Philosophical Thoughts of Karol Wojtyła (John Paul II)* (Manila: UST Publishing House, 2014), 70; henceforth *PAL*.

⁵⁸ Wojtyła, *PA*, 125.

or powers that operate without us being conscious of them. For example, my writing this paper is an act accompanied by my consciousness; I am aware of what I am writing and the fact that I am writing. When I take my meals, I am conscious as I eat, but the way the food is digested by my body is something that is no longer accompanied by my consciousness. Thus, while there are those functions or powers that are accompanied by consciousness, there are also those that happen or manifest without the accompaniment of consciousness.⁵⁹ This is one of the bases for the distinction between an “act” and a “happening.”

The person himself causes human action; it proceeds from him and comes about in him through his own agency. In this sense, the self, or the “I,” is at the center of the total lived experience of “I act.” When the person acts, it is the self that brings about the act, and not anybody else; the person experiences himself as the agent of the act. This is the moment of efficacy, the lived experience of being the agent of the act.⁶⁰ When a person acts, he experiences himself as the cause of his actions; he knows that it is he who brings the action into existence and sustains its existence. By experiencing himself as the efficient cause of the action, “man discovers that he is completely immanent in the action and simultaneously transcends it.”⁶¹ In “happening,” on the other hand, there is no efficacious participation of man. Although the function happens in him, he does not really consciously bring it into existence. The experience of “something happens” comes to the self regardless of the self, and sometimes even despite or in spite of the self. When something happens to me, the dynamization has occurred without the efficacious contribution of my “I.”⁶²

The human act is a self-determined act. Self-determination is the very basis of freedom. We are free when we can determine not only our actions, but also ourselves. Thus, conscious and voluntary action is related to freedom. This freedom is manifested in the lived experience when man can move from the “I can” and “I need not” to “I want” or “I will.”⁶³ Since the act is the self’s own and it is experienced as such, it is also something that the self *may* or *need not* do. But the self can say, “*I will.*” This means that there are some things that a person can do but need not do. One can just sit in one corner and do nothing, or one can take a book and read. It is in this instance that the person experiences the moment of freedom, the moment of efficacy, the moment of the will, the moment of self-determination. Since the self

⁵⁹ *Ibid.*, 128.

⁶⁰ *Ibid.*, 168.

⁶¹ R. Buttiglione, *Karol Wojtyła: The Thoughts of the Man Who Became Pope John Paul II* (Grand Rapids, Michigan: WB. Eerdmans Publishing Co., 1997), 135.

⁶² Wojtyła, *PA*, 168.

⁶³ *Ibid.*, 203.

is the agent of his actions, he determines the act and, in the process, determines himself. The first subject of the self-determination of man is himself, his own self, so that when deciding about anything, the person decides about himself.⁶⁴ This is something that is not present in those occurrences that merely happen in man. When I eat and my body digests the food that I eat, this happens without my voluntary action or determination. Wojtyła further explains,

This first definition of self-determination in the experience of human action involves a sense of efficacy on the part of the personal self: “I act” means “I am the efficient cause” of my action and of my self-actualization as a subject, which is not the case when something merely “happens” in me, for then I do not experience the efficacy of my personal self.⁶⁵

The will,⁶⁶ which is regarded as one of the essential constitutive elements of man, a faculty through which the person realizes himself, is at the center of the self-determination of the human person.⁶⁷ Wojtyła points out that it is through the decision of the person’s will that he becomes the agent of his action; hence, it cannot be considered as something that happens in man.⁶⁸ When I decide to read a book or write an article, I manifest my will and myself; I determine the course of my action. The relation between the person and his will, wherein the will manifests itself in the person’s action, is what Wojtyła calls self-determination.⁶⁹ The power of self-determination is free will. As discussed in the preceding section, St. Thomas Aquinas explains that by a power man is as if empowered to act, and by a habit he is apt to act well or ill.

One particular act of the will is volition, that is, an intentional act directed toward a proper object, which could be an end or a value. Volition is a general term that may be applied to all the desires, wishes, and intentions of the person. Some kinds of volition can only be considered as “happenings,” since they do not really proceed from the will; they appear already as wants or desires. Some of our desires are influenced by our emotions, so that we blindly desire any object, like wanting expensive clothes and

⁶⁴ G. Hołub, T. Biesaga, J. Merecki, M. Kostur, *Karol Wojtyła* (Kraków: Ignatianum University Press, 2019), 57.

⁶⁵ K. Wojtyła, “The Personal Structure of Self-Determination,” in: K. Wojtyła, *Person and Community: Selected Essays*, trans. by Th. Sandok (New York: Peter Lang, 1993), 189.

⁶⁶ The will is also described as “rational appetite,” particularly by St. Thomas. Wojtyła explained that the term “appetite” has the element of directed striving towards an end and at the same time has the element of desire, which, for Wojtyła, points to the direction of what happens in man. So, the term “rational appetite” is almost a contradiction. Hence, Wojtyła used the term “intentionality” to refer to an act of the will. See Wojtyła, *PA*, 228.

⁶⁷ Aguas, *PAL*, 70.

⁶⁸ See Buttiglione, *Karol Wojtyła*, 142.

⁶⁹ Wojtyła, *PA*, 207.

pieces of jewelry. Wojtyła clarifies, however, that “I want” is different from “I will.” Wanting is directed towards a definite external object, like wanting wealth or food. But what is significant in Wojtyła’s analysis is the clear distinction between the intentionality of human volition, which consists in the will’s directing itself toward its objects, and the non-intentional self-determination which objectivizes the human self. In this sense, volition has an intentional object, whereas self-determination has no intentional object but the self. Intentionality and self-determination are intimately related because, without the intentionality of the will, moral action is impossible, whether the object intended is internal or external. However, the person, before directing his will toward those objects, influences himself, since the person is a primary object of himself, which results in self-determination.⁷⁰ And when both self-determination and intentionality are present in an act of the will, such an act reveals human causal efficacy and human transcendence most completely.⁷¹

The notion of self-determination presupposes the complex structure of the human person. It points to man’s specific complexity and to two aspects of human action, namely, self-possession and self-governance.⁷² According to Wojtyła, only the one who has possession of himself and is simultaneously his own sole and exclusive possession can be a person.⁷³ Self-determination is possible only on the ground of self-possession; only the person who really possesses himself, the one who really owns himself, can determine and decide for himself. Thus, because “I will” is an act of self-determination at a particular moment, it presupposes structural self-possession. Only the things that are man’s actual possessions can be determined by him. Since I possess myself, I can determine myself.⁷⁴

As a consequence, self-possession has another relation within the very structure of the human person, one that relates to the will and is indispensable for understanding self-determination. This is the relation of self-governance, which states that the person who possesses himself can govern himself. Wojtyła clarifies that self-governance implies not only self-control but also the power of man to govern himself. Because of self-determination, every man actually governs himself; he actually exercises a specific power over himself that nobody else can exercise or execute.⁷⁵ Self-governance differs from

⁷⁰ G. Hołub, “Philosophical Anthropology and Ethics in the Thought of Karol Wojtyła,” *Studia Gilsoniana* Vol. 11, No. 1 (January–March 2022), 157.

⁷¹ See J. Kupczak, *Destined for Liberty* (Washington, D.C.: The Catholic University of America Press, 2000), 117.

⁷² Aguas, *PAL*, 85.

⁷³ Wojtyła, *PA*, 209.

⁷⁴ *Ibid.*, 208.

⁷⁵ *Ibid.*, 209.

self-control in that it is something far more fundamental and far more strictly related to the inner personal structure of man. It refers to man's power to govern himself, and not merely to control himself.

Wojtyła further explains that the full experience and lived realization of the human self's personal subjectivity are manifested and actualized in self-possession and self-governance. This is because one can experience oneself as a personal subject only to the extent that one becomes aware that one possesses and governs oneself.⁷⁶ Consciousness, or more precisely, self-consciousness, which is connected with action and with efficacy as self-determination, conditions the lived experience of self-possession and self-governance. The self is not just self-conscious but also self-possessed and self-governed, something proper to a concrete human *suppositum*.⁷⁷ The self cannot be reduced to self-consciousness alone; the full dimension of the human self includes self-possession and self-governance, and is conditioned by self-consciousness. This dimension is also the basis for the full relation of the self to the personal subjectivity that is proper to a human being.⁷⁸

Virtue: Habitual Disposition of the Will and the Role of Reason

For Wojtyła, virtue is a habitual disposition of the will that enables individuals to act in accordance with reason and to achieve their fullest human potential. Virtue, as a habitual disposition of the will, is a stable and lasting quality that is developed through practice and repetition. In his analysis of chastity as a virtue, Wojtyła explains that habit is more than an ability or a provisional control over something; rather, it is mastery or power over something. Since virtue is a habit, it is a permanent and constant mastery. He writes,

Habit (*sprawność*) means more than “ability” (*zdolność*), and virtue is a habit—and a “constant” habit at that. For if a habit were merely provisional, it would not be a habit properly speaking; it would be possible to say that the given man “managed” to master a movement, whereas a virtue should give the assurance that this man will master it for certain.⁷⁹

Thus, in the case of chastity, virtue assists the will, and above all, the concupiscible power itself (*appetitus concupiscibilis*), in mastering sensual movements. If the proficiency in mastering the concupiscent

⁷⁶ K. Wojtyła, “The Person: Subject and Community,” in: Wojtyła, *Person and Community: Selected Essays*, 231.

⁷⁷ Aguas, *PAL*, 86.

⁷⁸ *Ibid.*, 86.

⁷⁹ K. Wojtyła, *Love and Responsibility*, trans. by G. Ignatik (Boston: Pauline Books & Media, 2013), 153; henceforth *LR*.

movement from sensuality is only provisional, even if one is able to manage it for some time, then it is not a fully matured virtue. The “fully mature virtue is a habit that consists in keeping constantly in balance the concupiscent power by the habitual relation to the true good (*bonum honestum*), which is defined by reason.”⁸⁰

Wojtyła also emphasizes that virtue is guided by reason, which means that virtue involves the use of intellect and wisdom to discern what is good and right. This habitual disposition is not simply a matter of external behavior, but rather, it involves a deep-seated transformation of the person, enabling him to act in accordance with his values and principles. In speaking about sexual desires and man’s objective ends, for example, Wojtyła stresses that “the correct development of the relation to the objective ends of his being remains in him in the power of reason, which directs the will, and therefore this development acquires a moral value—it is morally good or evil.”⁸¹ Reason also distinguishes among the different kinds of goods, namely: *bonum honestum*—the good that conforms to the nature of a rational being because it is in keeping with what that being desires for itself; *bonum utile*—a good that is a means to an end; and *bonum delectabile*—the subjective good of satisfaction or pleasure.⁸²

Following St. Thomas, Wojtyła stresses the directive role of reason in human action. Such a directive role is determined mainly by a holistic view of the human being, a faculty of which is reason. Reason is part of the whole human person and performs its practical functions within this whole.⁸³ The superior and directive character of the function of reason is determined in a fundamental way by the fact that reason defines the good, which is the end of the human being and his action—the *bonum honestum*. This, according to Wojtyła, is what guarantees that reason has a directive role in human life. Reason sees to it that the good desired by the will is the real and true good and not just a delectable or useful good. Even the value perceived by the will must be a real and true value of the object which is desired by the will.⁸⁴ Following St. Thomas, Wojtyła again asserts:

The moral life consists in attaining the truth in all our actions and behavior, and activity by nature always aims at some good. Consequently, the essence of moral life is the lived experience of

⁸⁰ *Ibid.*, 153.

⁸¹ *Ibid.*, 47.

⁸² See J.J. Aguas, “Ethics and Moral Philosophy of Karol Wojtyła,” *Kritike: An Online Journal of Philosophy* Vol. 7, No. 1, (June 2013), 122.

⁸³ K. Wojtyła, “On the Directive or Subservient Role of Reason in Ethics,” in: Wojtyła, *Person and Community: Selected Essays*, 67.

⁸⁴ J.J. Aguas, “Ethics and Moral Philosophy of Karol Wojtyła,” 123.

the truth of the good realized in action and the realization in that action of the good subjected to the criterion of reason and thus placed in the light of that truth.⁸⁵

This emphasis on reason is important because it highlights the fact that virtue is not simply a matter of emotional or instinctual response but rather involves a thoughtful and reflective approach to human action. Through conscious and free acts, the individual shapes their own being and develops stable dispositions, which constitute virtues. Virtuous action is not merely the performance of externally good deeds, but flows from an interiorized orientation toward the good, reflecting the person's authentic self-determination. Virtue enables individuals to self-determine their actions, making them responsible and free.

Virtue and the Integration of the Human Person

Wojtyła stresses that virtue involves the integration of the human person, which means that it involves the harmonization of the individual's emotions, desires, and actions. This integration is important because it enables individuals to act in a way that is consistent with their values and principles and to achieve their fullest human potential. Virtue integrates human faculties, such as intellect, will, and emotions, to achieve a unified and harmonious action.

Emotions belong to psychic dynamism, which refers to emotional experiences like stirring emotions or excitement; and particular emotions and passions only happen in man as a subject. Their happening or occurrence is spontaneous, which means that they are not a product of personal efficacy and self-determination. Wojtyła stresses that spontaneity means the dynamic independence of emotions from the proper efficacy of the person, that is, from his self-determination. It is possible that emotions take over from the will and freedom in the determination of action, creating a tension between these two dynamisms.

The tension between the person's efficacy or self-determination and spontaneous emotivity arises when emotional dynamism introduces a spontaneous turn toward specific values. This turn may be directed toward something attractive or a positive value, or away from something repulsive or a negative value. The fact that man is emotionally *dynamized*—which means oriented to the good and against the evil—is not so much a function of an emotional stirring or of emotions. This inclination toward

⁸⁵ K. Wojtyła, "On the Metaphysical and Phenomenological Basis of the Moral Norm," in: Wojtyła, *Person and Community: Selected Essays*, 91.

something attractive and away from something repulsive reaches the deeper roots of man's nature.⁸⁶ Man has a natural inclination toward anything perceived to be good and away from anything perceived to be evil. On the level of the psyche, emotions follow the orientation of nature, and instincts express this natural inclination. Wojtyła writes,

On the basis of precisely this orientation, at whose root inheres a deep urge of nature itself, lies the main tension between the spontaneous emotivity of nature and personal efficacy, that is, self-determination.⁸⁷

However, the experience of value is not just a matter of being inclined to a value or just a spontaneous turn toward a value; it is closely related to morality. For Wojtyła, the experience of value is not merely a spontaneous inclination toward anything perceived to be valuable; the inclination must also be under the norms of morality. There are many goods that man may be inclined to, but only the moral good perfects the very humanity of man; only the moral good can make man a better man and actualize himself.⁸⁸ The experience of value is not confined only to the psychical; it is related to the higher dynamism of the human subject, that of self-determination and transcendence. Wojtyła stresses that morality intrinsically determines man's humanity and personal nature. Hence, the experience of morality is an integral component of man's experience. Without this experience, it is impossible to build an adequate theory of person and act.⁸⁹

Now, the key element in relieving the tension between emotivity and efficacy is virtue or moral proficiency. Wojtyła explains,

The integration of the person in the act on the basis of the emotivity (emotionality and emotivity) proper to the human psyche is accomplished through habits, which, from the viewpoint of ethics, warrant the term "virtues." Essential to the concept of virtue are both the element of moral value and, with it, a relation to the norm."⁹⁰

⁸⁶ Wojtyła, *PA*, 363.

⁸⁷ *Ibid.*, 364.

⁸⁸ Hołub, "Philosophical Anthropology and Ethics," 150.

⁸⁹ Wojtyła, *PA*, 364.

⁹⁰ *Ibid.*, 364.

According to Wojtyła, the problem of integration consists in realizing the personal structure of self-governance and self-possession on the basis of psychical subjectivity, which is molded by various emotive events that cause spontaneous attraction or repulsion on the part of the subject.⁹¹ A person may feel sexually attracted spontaneously toward the opposite sex, and the challenge is to keep one's spontaneous feelings under control, thus keeping the personal structure of self-governance and self-possession intact. In this case, it is one's moral proficiency or virtue that will enable him or her to harmonize or integrate properly the personal structure and emotive subjectivity. Thus, Wojtyła asserts that this personal structure is realized through different moral proficiencies or skills. "It is precisely here that the proper function of habit is manifested—the integrative function."⁹²

Now, skills are formed by constant repetition, so when a good act is constantly repeated, it becomes a good habit or a virtue. When a person is able to restrain or channel his emotive energies into something that will not compromise his personal structure repeatedly, then he develops a good habit or virtue. It goes without saying that the realization of the personal structure of self-governance and self-possession in the context of relieving the tension between the spontaneous emotivity and efficacy or self-determination is the result of constant repetition of good acts that result in good moral habits or virtues. The personal structure of self-governance and self-possession is realized by means of different moral proficiencies or virtues.⁹³

It is in the nature of habits or virtues to subordinate the spontaneous emotivity of the subjective ego to its self-determination. They tend to subordinate the psychical subjectivity to the transcendent efficacy of the person. They do this, however, in such a way as to take maximum advantage of emotive energy instead of merely suppressing it.⁹⁴ To subordinate the emotion or the psychic inclination to transcendence or efficacy does not mean suppressing the emotive energy. The person, through his will, must, to some extent, restrain the spontaneous burst of emotive energy and must even assimilate some of it. When properly assimilated, this emotive energy fortifies the energy of the will itself considerably, and that is precisely the task of virtue. Through the exercise of these moral proficiencies, the will, without risking itself, can adopt as its own the spontaneity of emotions, but this time it is already a transformed spontaneity. This transformed spontaneity is a trait of moral proficiencies or virtues. Wojtyła writes,

⁹¹ Aguas, *PAL*, 155.

⁹² Wojtyła, *PA*, 364.

⁹³ Aguas, *PAL*, 155.

⁹⁴ Wojtyła, *PA*, 365.

To a certain extent, spontaneity is also a feature of habit—not original spontaneity, however, but one transformed by a steadfast process of so-called work on oneself. If, however, the relation to value is concerned, then the integrative process of improving one’s own psyche gradually leads to the situation in which the will—guided by the light of intellectual cognition—knows how to appropriate, in the spontaneous relation of emotion, in spontaneous attraction or repulsion, what is truly good and to choose it. It also knows how to reject what is truly evil.⁹⁵

Thus, the integrating process of developing and improving the psyche gradually produces a will which is guided by the light of reason and reference to truth and energized by a transformed spontaneity of the emotions: a will that learns how to choose and adopt the real good and reject the real bad. All these are possible through a steadfast process of character formation.

Wojtyła also stresses the crucial role of freedom in the acquisition and exercise of virtue. Genuine virtue cannot be coerced; it must be freely chosen and embraced by the individual. This freedom is inseparable from responsibility. The virtuous person is accountable for their actions and consciously directs their freedom towards the realization of objective good. Responsibility is directly related to efficacy for the simple reason that if a person is the doer of an act, then he is responsible for that act. Once again, we see here the complexity of the performance of an action. Wojtyła points out that since we relate responsibility directly to efficacy, the statement “man as the doer of X is responsible for X” reveals how complex, cohesive, and condensed are the elements that constitute when a man performs an action.⁹⁶ Not only is he responsible for the act, but he also fulfills or actualizes himself when he performs it.

The Virtue of Love and Chastity

Wojtyła highlights the inherently relational dimension of human existence and, consequently, of virtue. Virtuous actions are not performed in isolation but have an impact on others and contribute to the building of a community. This relational dimension of virtue is expressed in the virtue of love. Wojtyła places a strong emphasis on the virtue of love, which he sees as the foundation of all other virtues. According to Wojtyła, love is a virtue that involves the intentional and deliberate choice to will the good of another person. He argues that virtue is a form of love that enables individuals to act responsibly and selflessly.

⁹⁵ *Ibid.*, 365.

⁹⁶ *Ibid.*, 271.

Virtue integrates love and reason, enabling individuals to make responsible decisions that respect the dignity of others.

For Wojtyła, the human person is the most perfect being in the visible world and, therefore, has the highest value.⁹⁷ As a being with the highest value in the world because of his being created in the image of God, man has an inherent dignity that must be preserved and respected at all times. “The value of the person is, in turn, the basis of the norm that should govern actions that have a person as their object.”⁹⁸ This is the personalistic norm that demands that every person should be treated as a person. This norm is related to love. Love demands that we treat each person as a person, as an end in himself, and we are commanded to love each one.⁹⁹

One form of love that Wojtyła discusses at length is the love between a man and a woman in the context of marriage. The growth of such human love consists “in integrating the different processes that spontaneously occur in the human person, e.g., sensual attraction and sexual emotions into a conscious act of the whole person that also involves his rational faculties.”¹⁰⁰ True love does not just happen in the person but involves an experience of being an efficient cause of the act of love; it involves the act of the will; it springs from the human spirit.

Wojtyła analyzed different levels and types of love. One aspect of love that relates to our present study is love in the ethical sense. While love can be analyzed in the psychological sense, it must be subordinated to love in the ethical sense because it is in the ethical sense that love can be integrated. We can look at love as a concrete situation or as a whole series of situations, but this situation or series of situations can only be psychologically integrated and complete if the ethical value of love is present within them.¹⁰¹ Hence, Wojtyła stresses that love as an experience should be subordinated to love as a virtue because without virtue there can be no fullness in the experience of love.¹⁰² Love as a virtue is based on the affirmation of the value and dignity of the person. The person differs from a thing in structure and degree of perfection because, in the person, there is an ‘interior,’ an inner life where we find the elements of spiritual life. Wojtyła further stresses,

⁹⁷ K. Wojtyła, “The Problem of Catholic Sexual Ethics: Reflections and Postulates,” in: Wojtyła, *Person, Subject and Community: Selected Essays*, 287.

⁹⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹⁹ Aguas, *PAL*, 206.

¹⁰⁰ Kupczak, *Destined for Liberty*, 46.

¹⁰¹ Aguas, *PAL*, 240.

¹⁰² Wojtyła, *LR*, 103.

The person possesses spiritual perfection that is proper for him. This perfection determines his value. In no way may a person be treated on par with a thing (nor even on par with an individual animal), since he possesses spiritual perfection, since he is in a sense an (embodied) spirit, and not merely a “body,” even if splendidly enlivened.¹⁰³

The value of the person must then be clearly distinguished from the value present or inherent in a person.¹⁰⁴ Psychologically, love between a man and a woman is an experience related to a reaction to a sexual value. Love may be initiated by sensual or sexual attraction. Still, our consciousness is also aware that the individual of the other sex is a person. Since the other “person” is not the content of impression but the object of conceptual knowledge, the reaction to the value of a person is not as immediate as the reaction to a sexual value connected with the “body.” Nevertheless, the human being of the other sex is a person.¹⁰⁵

The affirmation of the true value of the person is the proper attitude of love. This is the fullness of love. Love in its full sense is a virtue; it is not just an emotion, much less a mere excitement of the senses. As a virtue, love is developed in the will; it is an authentic commitment of the free will of one person (the subject), resulting from the truth about another person (the object).¹⁰⁶ The will orients love as a virtue toward the value of the person, the beloved, so that the will is the source of the affirmation of the value of the person that permeates all the reactions, emotions, and the entire behavior of the subject or person in love.

Still, love as a virtue relates to affective love and to the love contained in sensual desire; love as a virtue does not eliminate sensual desire or sexual attraction. Hence, the affirmation of the value of the person, which reflects the full truth about the beloved, must be allowed to take its place among the sexual experiences that originate in man’s sensuality. Sexual attraction and falling in love are emotions that belong to “what happens in man.” In the Thomistic and Aristotelian sense, they are “acts of man,” but love as a virtue is an act of the will; it is a “human act.” Hence, there must be an integration or harmonization of love as an emotion and love as a virtue.

In explicating the nature of chastity and concupiscence, Wojtyła follows St. Thomas’s distinction between the two passions of the soul, or appetites of the soul: the irascible and the concupiscible.

¹⁰³ *Ibid.*, 104.

¹⁰⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁰⁵ Aguas, *PAL*, 241.

¹⁰⁶ Wojtyła, *LR*, 106.

Temperance is a virtue that regulates and restrains the concupiscible appetite, while chastity is the virtue that regulates and restrains the concupiscible appetite insofar as it is directed toward sexual objects.¹⁰⁷

There are certain problems that can undermine love as a virtue; these are carnal concupiscence and subjectivism. Carnal concupiscence has as its object the body and sex; it arises in the subject from the body and seeks an outlet in carnal love. For Wojtyła, it is vital to contain carnal desire within the bounds of the senses and the emotions because once it gets out of control, it can communicate itself to the will, where it can impose its own attitude towards its object. It can orient the person first toward the “body and sex” and then toward enjoyment. Subjectivism is a problem in the sense that it distorts the true nature of love when the subjective elements, that is, the elements of emotion, dominate the decision of the will. In such cases, the objective value of love is either partially or totally lost. One form of subjectivism is emotional subjectivism, in which emotions play an enormous part in the development of the subjective aspect of love,¹⁰⁸ thus undermining the objective value of love.

To counter this problem of subjectivism and the excess of concupiscence, Wojtyła proposes the virtue of chastity. For Wojtyła, the full sense of the virtue of chastity cannot be fully comprehended without understanding love as the function of relating one person to another and being disposed toward the union of persons. Love should possess an ethical wholeness and fullness (integrity); the psychological dimension is not enough to fully experience love. Love in its psychological dimension or aspect can only be completed when it possesses an ethical value, when it becomes a virtue. In this way, love attains psychological maturity precisely when it takes on ethical value, that is, when it becomes the virtue of love. Wojtyła stresses, “Only in the virtue of love are the objective demands of the personalistic norm realized, the norm that commands ‘loving’ the person and rejects any ‘use’ of him.”¹⁰⁹

Chastity is linked to the virtue of temperance, which restrains the instinctive appetites for the various material and bodily goods that attach themselves to the senses. The virtue of temperance enables the will and the appetite to subdue the sensual impulses that accompany sensual reactions. As a virtue of temperance, chastity is the efficient control of the concupiscent impulses set up by the sensual and emotional reactions. Chastity does not eliminate sensual desires and emotional impulses; rather, it not only subdues the impulses originating from the senses and emotions but also keeps the sensual appetites permanently in equilibrium by means of its habitual attitude to the true good

¹⁰⁷ Cf. Aquinas, *ST*, II-III, q.143, a.1.

¹⁰⁸ Aguas, *PAL*, 252

¹⁰⁹ Wojtyła, *LR*, 151.

determined by reason.¹¹⁰ Chastity, then, as a virtue of temperance, is in the first sense the capacity to moderate the appetites on particular occasions, and in the second and fuller sense, the efficient and consistent moderation of the appetites that ensures the natural equilibrium of the sensual appetites.¹¹¹ In this sense, chastity becomes a virtue of love for it frees love from the utilitarian attitude and subjectivism. It has “the function of making love possible as love of the person.”¹¹² Wojtyła further says:

The virtue of chastity, whose task is to liberate love from the attitude to use, must grasp not only sensuality and the concupiscence of the flesh themselves, but, in a sense even more so, those interior centers in man from which the attitude to use emerges and spreads.¹¹³

Finally, for Wojtyła, chastity is not a blind inhibition to sensuality and the physical impulses, such that the values of the body and sex are relegated to the subconscious, where they are suppressed until they explode. The essence of chastity is in the readiness “to affirm the value of the person in every situation and in raising to the personal level all reactions to the value of ‘the body and sex’.” This entails a special spiritual effort to affirm the value of the person, which can only come from within the person, from his or her spirit.¹¹⁴

The Relevance of Virtue: A Synthesis

The insights of both St. Thomas Aquinas and Karol Wojtyła on virtue remain profoundly relevant for contemporary ethical discourse. Virtue theorists stress the importance of developing good habits of character or virtues. Virtue as a state of character means that a morally good or virtuous person is not just one who performs morally right actions, but one who has developed a habit or disposition to do what is right. Such a person has learned to control or moderate his emotions, desires, and appetites, subordinating them to reason and the will. A well-formed character not only tells the truth but does so readily, happily, and easily; such a character is manifested in one’s motives, desires, and intentions. Hence, the virtuous person delights in virtuous actions and dislikes vicious or immoral ones.¹¹⁵ By analogy, a good musician

¹¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 152.

¹¹¹ *Ibid.*, 154.

¹¹² Buttiglione, 107.

¹¹³ Wojtyła, *LR*, 154.

¹¹⁴ Aguas, *PAL*, 257.

¹¹⁵ Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, Book 9, Chapter 9.

enjoys beautiful music but is pained by bad tunes. Once a person has acquired the virtue of charity, he will then habitually act in a charitable manner; once a person has developed the virtue of moderating his appetites and sexual desires, he will be able to subordinate such appetites and desires to reason and will.

Since Wojtyła followed the thoughts of St. Thomas, there are apparent similarities between their concepts; for example, both consider virtue as a good habit, that is, a habitual disposition that enables the individual to act in a moral way, based on reason and will. However, we can also see that St. Thomas and Wojtyła have contrasting philosophical focuses. First, St. Thomas Aquinas employs a metaphysical approach, drawing heavily on Aristotelian categories; he places his discussion of the virtues within the parameters of ethics and moral philosophy. Wojtyła, on the other hand, utilizes a phenomenological method, focusing on the lived experience of the person and on the emotive and personal dimensions of moral action. Second, while Aquinas acknowledges the importance of reason and the will, Wojtyła's analysis, aside from highlighting the role of these two rational faculties, delves deeper into the experiential aspects of moral action. He places a greater emphasis on the subjective agency of the person in the exercise of virtue, highlighting the role of consciousness, freedom, and self-determination. Lastly, St. Thomas is more focused on the perfection of rational power, highlighting the cardinal and theological virtues. Wojtyła, on the other hand, is more focused on the integration of the human person, emphasizing the relational dimension of virtue, expressed in the virtue of love that affirms the personhood of others.

Beyond these contrasts, we can see the complementarity of their thoughts on virtue. St. Thomas Aquinas and Karol Wojtyła, in their respective notions of virtue, focused not only on the goodness of particular action but also on perfecting the human powers and capacities and on developing the character of the person, ensuring that the person consistently acts in accordance with norms or moral standards and ultimately develops good moral character. A morally good person will be disposed to obey the law, relate ethically and harmoniously with others based on respect for the dignity of the person, perform his duties, and consider the welfare and happiness of other people. In the end, however, it is always the person who decides how to act and what course of action he or she will take, and his character that determines his actions and decisions.

St. Thomas points out that virtue, as a habit, implies the perfection of a power and, consequently, the perfection of the person. By relating virtue to human powers and emphasizing the wholly positive character of virtue as the perfection of the activity of human powers, he provided a complete definition of virtue. Virtue as a habit is something that we possess; it is not something that possesses us. A habit, in

this sense, is not an automatic and unconscious disposition that we cannot control. For Wojtyła, virtue is a habitual disposition of the will which enables the person to act in accordance with reason and to achieve his fullest human potential. He emphasizes the integration of the person's efficacy or self-determination and the spontaneous emotional dynamism of the person, as well as the relational aspect of virtue, expressed in the virtue of love. The modern understanding of habit is that it is something we do unconsciously, which therefore can sometimes drive us into doing things that are not under our control. But, for St. Thomas and Wojtyła, however, since habits can be developed in accord with our rational powers, they perfect us rather than putting us in compromising situations.

Furthermore, according to St. Thomas and Wojtyła, in perfecting our powers, virtues as habits do not bypass the will. This notion is different from the modern understanding of habit as an automatic disposition, where habits are seen as the unmindful activities of the individual. Virtues, by contrast, are moral habits that perfect the will. In the modern sense, a habit is a substitute for conscious agency, putting a person on "auto drive," so to speak. However, for St. Thomas and Wojtyła, moral habits engage and perfect rather than bypass the human will. For St. Thomas, moral virtues are dispositions that allow one to *choose* to act in certain ways: moral virtue is a habit that chooses; it is an elective habit.¹¹⁶ So, the virtues do not diminish but improve our capacity to act from reason and will. For Wojtyła, the integrating function of virtue develops and enhances the psyche, thus producing a will which is guided by reason and reference to truth. Ultimately, one who develops the virtues is able to choose and adopt the real good while rejecting the real bad. All these are possible through a steadfast process of character formation.

While St. Thomas describes habits as having the facility to perform certain acts, facility does not mean automaticity. Facility (*facilitas*) is the ability to exercise a capacity with promptness and without inner resistance, while *automaticity* is doing something without thinking. It may appear that a habit "contains a notion of something that works automatically, without participation of our consciousness, and so independently of our will, and signifies some mechanization of activity that results from a longer repetition of the same activity," different from skill, which has "no feature of mechanization in itself" but enhances "the ability to consciously do something, to do it better, faster, without hesitation or a second thought, but not without consideration and participation of higher mental functions."¹¹⁷ However, as

¹¹⁶ Aquinas, *ST*, I,II, 58.1 ad 2.

¹¹⁷ See J. Woroniecki, "Habit or Skill," in: *Jacek Woroniecki: The Polish Christian Philosophy in the 20th Century*, ed. P.S. Mazur, B. Kiereś, R. Skrzyniarz, A. Płazińska (Kraków: Ignatianum University Press, 2019), 169.

discussed, there is a difference between a habit and an automatic movement of a part of the body, some of which we can consider mannerisms. A habit is also a skill, and both are different from bodily movements characterized by *automaticity* or *mechanization*. There is a difference between the automatic and almost unconscious lighting of a cigarette and the full engagement of a pianist at the keyboard. The facility of a habit is shown in the effortless movements of athletes and in the seamless and harmonious playing of musicians. These are the product of conscious repetitive acts, and they do not diminish conscious agency. In moral decision-making, one who has acquired the virtue of prudence seems to make the right decision instantaneously, as if without forethought and bypassing rational deliberation. But in reality, the virtuous person has already developed the virtue of prudence so that his deliberation appears to be without thought. Wojtyła, for his part, stresses the harmonization of the individual's emotions, desires, and actions. The virtues enable individuals to act in a way that is consistent with their values and principles and to achieve their fullest human potential. Virtue integrates human faculties, such as intellect, will, and emotions, to achieve a unified and harmonious action. Thus, a man of virtue finds it easy, and as if without deliberation, to moderate or control his appetites and desires, having already integrated or harmonized his emotions and desires with his will and reason.

St. Thomas's framework provides a comprehensive understanding of the nature and classification of virtues, offering a clear guide for moral formation. His emphasis on the cardinal, or natural, virtues as foundational for a well-ordered life, together with the theological virtues as essential for ultimate human fulfillment, continues to offer a valuable framework for moral decision and action. Wojtyła's phenomenological approach complements Aquinas's framework by highlighting the subjective dimension of virtuous action. His emphasis on consciousness, self-determination, responsibility, love, emotions, and desires provides a richer understanding of the interiority of the human person. In a world often characterized by moral decay and absence of moral character and virtue, manifested in moral relativism, disrespect for the human person and life, and many moral illnesses mentioned at the beginning of this paper, St. Thomas's teachings underscore the importance of cultivating stable dispositions towards the good. Further, Wojtyła's insights remind us that genuine virtue stems from a free and responsible embrace of the good, rooted in truth, and resulting in the total integration of the person. Their combined perspectives offer a richer, more positive understanding of virtue that not only serves as an antidote to the moral decay in our society but also reminds us that true human flourishing is inextricably linked to the cultivation of virtue.

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**Irreducibility and the Personalistic Norm as a Departure from Thomism:
A Critique from the Thought of Karol Wojtyła/John Paul II**

Richard H. Bulzacchelli¹

Abstract

Karol Wojtyła owed a considerable debt to the thought of St. Thomas Aquinas, affirming a great deal in Aquinas’s metaphysical apparatus that was wanting, in his estimation, in much of contemporary philosophy: a grounding in *substance*, and an *objectivity* according to which we can confidently appeal to the truly *knowable* in reality, and in which we can locate definitive moral laws. At the same time, however, Wojtyła took from contemporary philosophy, especially the phenomenology of Max Scheler, a new focus upon the human person—a focus lacking, even in the great Christian thinkers of Scholasticism, Aquinas included. Wojtyła criticizes Aquinas’s view of the human person as being too “naturalistic,” instead suggesting that we ought to construct a more thoroughly developed *personalism*, giving the personal subject’s *irreducibility* “the upper hand” over natural *functionality* while avoiding any trace of subjectivism in the determination of moral norms. As a result, analyses that may seem perfectly warranted within the purely metaphysical realm cannot stand unchallenged by the truth available to human reason through the careful application of the phenomenological method. This is the point we wish to explore in this paper. What, in the view of Karol Wojtyła / Pope John Paul II, is the nature of Aquinas’s mistake here? How does Wojtyła correct it? And what practical differences does this make in terms of concrete conclusions with respect to matters of faith and morals?

Keywords

Wojtyła, John Paul II, Aquinas, personalism, reductionism, Thomistic personalism

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There can be no doubt that Karol Wojtyła owed a considerable debt to the thought of St. Thomas Aquinas, affirming a great deal in Aquinas's metaphysical apparatus that was wanting, in his estimation, in much of contemporary philosophy: a grounding in *substance*, and an *objectivity* according to which we can confidently appeal to the truly *knowable* in reality, and within which we can locate definitive moral laws. At the same time, however, Wojtyła drew from contemporary philosophy, especially the phenomenology of Max Scheler, a new focus upon the human person—a focus lacking, even in the great Christian thinkers of Scholasticism, Aquinas included. The impact of that “new focus” on the thought of Karol Wojtyła / John Paul II, and thus, on the Church's understanding of the mysteries of the faith as they pertain to the human person, reaches far, indeed. While Wojtyła draws heavily from Aquinas, even defending, at one point, the notion that we can articulate a kind of “Thomistic personalism,”² it would be naïve to suggest that Wojtyła's thought can be characterized as a development strictly continuous with that of Aquinas.³

It is well-known, of course, that Wojtyła wrote his first doctoral dissertation, on the understanding of faith in the works of St. John of the Cross, at the Angelicum in Rome under Classical Thomist Réginald Garrigou-Lagrange, O.P. In his Introduction, he noted that St. John had been deeply influenced by the thought of St. Thomas Aquinas at the University of Salamanca as a consequence of the Thomistic revival of the late fifteenth century under the influence of Francisco de Vitoria. He notes, further, that under this influence, “even then he was laying the foundation for the mystical doctrine that he would later develop from sound theological

² K. Wojtyła, “Thomistic Personalism,” in: K. Wojtyła, *Person and Community: Selected Essays*, trans. by Th. Sandok (New York: Peter Lang, 1993), 165–175. The essay originally appeared as: K. Wojtyła, “Personalizm tomistyczny,” *Znak* 13 (1961), 664–675. According to the bibliographical note appended to the essay in *Person and Community* (165), Wojtyła had presented the paper at the Fourth Annual Philosophy Week at the Catholic University of Lublin, February 17, 1961.

³ A case in point for this naive reading of Wojtyła may be found in Samuel Gregg, *Challenging the Modern World: John Paul II/Karol Wojtyła and the Development of Catholic Social Teaching* (Lanham, MD: Lexington Books, 1999). See, especially, where he writes that, “*The Acting Person* reads like neo-Thomism couched in Husserlian language” (62). Cf., also, Romanus Cessario's comment on the cover notes for Jarosław Kupczak's *Destined for Liberty* (J. Kupczak, *Destined for Liberty: The Human Person in the Philosophy of Karol Wojtyła/John Paul II* (Washington, D.C.: The Catholic University Press, 2000)), where he says, “Quite simply, he's a Thomist!” This comment leaves the impression that Wojtyła / John Paul II does exactly what Gregg suggests and nothing more: couch neo-Thomism in Husserlian language.

principles,”⁴ believing that St. John’s work in this period supports the view that there is “a basic conformity between the teaching of St. John of the Cross and that of St. Thomas Aquinas.”⁵ Nonetheless, even then, Wojtyła’s interest was less in the speculative dimension of St. John’s treatment of faith than in exploring St. John’s account of the experience of the theological virtue of faith, inasmuch as the doctrine is itself “a testimony of experience.” That testimony, he explains:

... is expressed in scholastic-mystical language, using words and concepts well known in Scholastic theology, but its primary value and significance is as a witness of personal experience. It is there, in fact, that we can discover the living and dynamic reality of the virtue of faith, its activity in the human intellect, its corollaries and the effects on the movement of the soul toward union with God.⁶

Having completed his dissertation in 1948, Wojtyła had not yet taken a turn toward phenomenology but, even then he resisted certain modes of expression he found too coldly objectivistic. Notably, his dissertation director had wanted him to employ the expression “divine object,” which Wojtyła refused to do. His turn to phenomenology would begin at the Jagiellonian University, where, for his habilitation thesis, he undertook a formative study of Max Scheler, asking whether and to what extent a Christian morality could find grounding in Scheler’s system of thought.⁷ While, in the end, he did not find Scheler’s approach sufficient, his study of Scheler proved formative, becoming an integral part of his mature philosophical and theological perspective. Stefan Swiezawski notes that later, at the Catholic University of Lublin, the philosophy department had a tendency to become lost in abstraction, but that Wojtyła was among those “who helped us maintain the balance between *theoria* and *praxis*, a balance that might

⁴ K. Wojtyła, *Faith According to Saint John of the Cross*, trans. by J. Aumann (San Francisco: Ignatius Press, 1981), 19. Original title: *Doctrina de fide apud S. Joannem a Cruce* (Rome: Pontifical University of St. Thomas Aquinas, 1948).

⁵ *Ibid.*

⁶ *Ibid.*, 23.

⁷ K. Wojtyła, *An Assessment of the Possibility for Building a Christian Ethics Based on the Presuppositions of Max Scheler*, in: K. Wojtyła, *The Lublin Lectures and Works*, “The English Critical Edition of the Works of Karol Wojtyła/John Paul II,” vol. 2, ed. A. Lopez, trans. by G. Ignatik (Washington, D.C.: The Catholic University of America Press, 2023), 383–500. Original title: *Ocena możliwości zbudowania etyki chrześcijańskiej przy założeniach systemu Maksa Schelera* (Lublin, 1959). The thesis was actually written for the Jagiellonian University Theology Department (1953), but this university was forced to close under Communist control in 1954, with the faculty reconstituting at the Seminary of Kraków.

otherwise have been lost.”⁸ He notes further that Wojtyła “tended to view phenomenological language as more communicative than scholastic terminology.”⁹ From this point forward, through his elevation to the papacy as John Paul II, Wojtyła would construct his moral thought along personalist lines. So, with the phenomenological method at his disposal, he would return to many of Aquinas’s key intuitions and yet go beyond them, departing from Aquinas on significant points, purifying and correcting his thought, and finally, moving forward to new conclusions.

Once again, while, in the main, considering himself to fall within and not in opposition to the Thomistic tradition (along with numerous others in the Lublin School), Wojtyła nonetheless comes to criticize Aquinas’s view of the human person as being too “naturalistic,” instead suggesting that we ought to construct a more thoroughly developed *personalism*.¹⁰ “In St. Thomas’ system of moral theology,” he writes:

aretology had a teleological and “naturalistic” character. This aretology arose from the Aristotelian concept of the person as a nature. The human being was treated somewhat on the model of a biological organism, in which everything is explained and acquires meaning from the point of view of “maturing” and attaining its end. Today we find this “naturalistic” concept of the human being rather inadequate. The aretology being developed today is taking on a normative and personalistic character. “Virtues” and “norms” themselves are not changing, but the way they are presented in the subject is.¹¹

Wojtyła notes that Aquinas’s moral theology rests on two interpretive elements. First, because, for Thomas, “moral theology ‘gets to the bottom’ of the reality of morality in the light of the teachings

⁸ S. Swiezawski, “Introduction: Karol Wojtyła at the Catholic University of Lublin,” in: K. Wojtyła, *Person and Community*, xiii–xiv. This essay appeared originally in Polish as S. Swiezawski, “Karol Wojtyła w Katolickim Uniwersytecie Lubelskim,” in: *Obecność: Karol Wojtyła w Katolickim Uniwersytecie Lubelskim*, ed. M. Filipiak, A. Szostek (Lublin: Redakcja Wydawnictw KUL, 1987), 9–18. Sandok prints an abridged version in *Person and Community*.

⁹ S. Swiezawski, “Introduction: Karol Wojtyła at the Catholic University of Lublin,” xiv.

¹⁰ K. Wojtyła, “Ethics and Moral Theology,” in: Wojtyła, *Person and Community*, 101–106. The essay originally appeared as: K. Wojtyła, “Etyka a teologia moralna,” *Znak* 19 (1967), 1077–1082. According to the bibliographical note appended to the essay in *Person and Community* (p. 101), the published essay is a summary of a lecture he had delivered at the Tenth Annual Philosophy Week at the Catholic University of Lublin, February 17, 1967. In this little-studied but singularly pivotal essay, written six years after his essay on “Thomistic Personalism,” Wojtyła begins to describe rather clearly what he had come to perceive, in the maturation of his own analysis, to be the limits of the Thomistic approach to moral reasoning against the horizon of contemporary philosophical insight.

¹¹ Wojtyła, “Ethics and Moral Theology,” 104–105.

on morality contained in the sources of revelation”¹²—that is, because moral theology, as a quest “to understand reality *per ultimas causas*,”¹³ is constructed on the model of a philosophical project—“[i]t stands to reason ... that theology should derive the tools for an ‘ultimate’ analysis of its own revealed contents from philosophy.”¹⁴ Second, and more specifically, “moral theology in the Thomistic sense ‘gets to the bottom’ of moral reality by explaining it on the basis of the ultimate end, which implies a particular concept of the good and a particular concept of being.”¹⁵ Wojtyła goes on to explain that this account of the ultimate end “also implies a corresponding metaphysical concept of the human being, a concept in which a ‘person’ is in a certain sense reducible to a ‘nature’: *individua substantia rationalis naturae*.”¹⁶ Wojtyła cautions that our justifiable admiration for Aquinas’s accomplishment—“a work of simply monumental proportions ... [which] can still astonish anyone who only takes the trouble to learn how to see and appreciate it ... does not have to mean—even should not mean—that we regard it as a work complete and perfect in every respect.”¹⁷ Rather, he suggests:

... in connection with the general direction of the development of philosophy, which is a movement away from the philosophy of being toward the philosophy of consciousness, the two previously mentioned interpretive elements in the structure of Thomistic theology have undergone—or at least should undergo—significant modification.¹⁸

Practically speaking, for Wojtyła this means acknowledging that the human person cannot be reduced to a mere part within a whole—to any natural, social, or cosmological *functionality*—in the determination of moral norms. The human being, precisely *as a person*, enjoys, in other words, a certain *irreducibility* to the purely natural and cosmological, with the result that, at times, analyses that may seem perfectly warranted within the purely metaphysical realm cannot stand unchallenged by the truth available to human reason through the careful application of the phenomenological method, as applied to the human subject and the experience of moral

¹² *Ibid.*, 102.

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷ *Ibid.*, 103.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

agency. This is the point we wish to explore in this paper. How does Wojtyła correct the shortcoming he comes to see in Thomistic moral theology, and what practical differences does his approach to personalism make in terms of concrete conclusions with respect to matters of faith and morals?¹⁹

Functionalism or Irreducibility?

We begin, then, by naming the problem as Wojtyła understands it. Aquinas, once again, is operating within the context of a fundamentally Aristotelian metaphysic. This is not to suggest that Aquinas does not adapt Aristotle; indeed, Wojtyła is well aware that Aquinas quite thoroughly reconstructs him—or more precisely, constructs an entirely new system of thought upon a retooled Aristotelian apparatus.²⁰ But the apparatus—skeletal at least—remains; and with it, a certain stultification of the vision of the human person Aquinas was never, himself, quite able thoroughly to overcome.²¹ A question then arises. If the root of the problem is Aquinas’s use of a fundamentally Aristotelian apparatus, does this mean that Wojtyła rejects such an apparatus?

¹⁹ Of course, in the space available to us, our examination of these questions can only be preliminary. They will inevitably open up much larger questions, not only for ethics, but for metaphysics as well. It is worth noting, however, that there are indications that Wojtyła understood the sweeping implications of this problem. Much later in life, as pope, John Paul II would call, in his encyclical letter, *Fides et ratio* (14 September 1998), not merely for a restoration of Thomism, but for philosophy in its full historical and intellectual maturity, inclusive of the contributions of contemporary thinkers, and making full use of their legitimate methods, to strive, once again, with renewed vigor, to stake out, for philosophy, a “genuinely metaphysical range” (Vatican translation, §83). He calls for this project even after affirming that, in Aquinas’s thinking, “the demands of reason and the power of faith found the most elevated synthesis ever attained by human thought” (§78). Again, these statements come more than two decades after “Ethics and Moral Theology,” but they evince the direction his thought had taken from that point. It would seem that Wojtyła did not think a simple return to Thomistic metaphysics would suffice in light of the post-Cartesian, and more importantly, post-Kantian philosophical dialogue, much less in light of the advances made in physics over the course of the twentieth century, but instead, that philosophers needed to attempt to develop a new metaphysical system of thought, capable of answering the challenges of modernity.

²⁰ Wojtyła speaks along these lines in, for example, his article, “In Search of the Basis of Perfectionism in Ethics,” in: Wojtyła, *Person and Community*, 45–56, especially 46–49. This article originally appeared as, K. Wojtyła, “W poszukiwaniu podstaw perfekcyjizmu w etyce,” *Roczniki Filozoficzne* Vol. 5 No. 4 (1955–57), 303–317.

²¹ “Classical Thomists” in line with Domingo Báñez, who pledged, “in all things to follow St. Thomas,” found themselves, whether consciously or unconsciously, imprisoned within these limitations—limitations that the Church would finally begin to confront, if only indirectly at first, in the twentieth century, beginning with the *Ressourcement*, proceeding through the Second Vatican Council, and continuing through the papacies of the post-Vatican II era. This confrontation is certainly still ongoing. Karol Wojtyła / John Paul II was a participant in this process, both as pope and as a private thinker. Though never *hostile* to Aquinas—indeed, always filially loyal and even adoring of him—Wojtyła forced a return to the question of the human person, confident that the true Thomas, as a saint and lover of the Truth, would have embraced such a re-examination and confidently undertaken the call to rethink his previous conclusions in light of new and deepened insights.

Certainly, even a cursory reading of his life's work as a philosopher, as a theologian, and as a magisterial authority would compel us to answer that question in the negative. Indeed, he quite certainly *embraces* the heritage of Aristotle—overall, at any rate. But for Wojtyła, Aristotle and Aquinas are both received with reservations, and they both require certain modifications. His reservations are not based so much on what they saw and tried to show us, but on what they did not see and, thus, on what their teaching *left out*.

Let us be clear about this point; there is nothing wrong with the hylomorphic view of the universe, as such, nor even with the application of such a view to the analysis of human action in the moral arena. Wojtyła explicitly says as much in his essay “The Problem of the Will in the Analysis of the Ethical Act,” written nearly a decade before “Ethics and Moral Theology,” and we have no reason to hold that his increasing and enduring commitment to phenomenology ever changed his view on this matter.²² He writes:

If ethical experience essentially consists in this specific becoming of the person, then the only interpretation of it that can be considered adequate is one that apprehends and expresses this ethical becoming. This is what also leads me to believe that we should consider the view of the human act developed by Thomas Aquinas an adequate interpretation of ethical experience. ... St. Thomas based his view of the human act on Aristotle's theory of potency and act, a theory by which the philosophy of being explains all changes that take place in beings. ... A conscious human act is, for St. Thomas ... an ethical experience because it is an act of will ... [and thus,] a passage from potency, since the will is a faculty

²² Indeed, once again, his call, as pope, in his encyclical letter *Fides et ratio*, for a restoration of philosophy's properly metaphysical range (§83), supports the thesis that this concern remained central to his thought throughout his life, even as Hans Köchler recounts that, in a private audience in connection with the Annual Conference of the Italian Section of the International Husserl and Phenomenological Research Society, held that year in Viterbo, Italy, in February of 1979, “he [John Paul II] assured me [Köchler] that he will always remain committed to the phenomenological movement and consider himself a phenomenologist” (H. Köchler, “Karol Wojtyła's Notion of the Irreducible in Man and the Quest for a Just World Order,” in: *Karol Wojtyła's Philosophical Legacy*, ed. N.M. Billias, et al., Cultural Heritage and Contemporary Change Series I, Culture and Values, Vol. 35, ed. G.F. McLean, (Washington, D.C.: The Council for Research in Values and Philosophy, 2008), 169). In saying that a “phenomenology of the will alone does not suffice for interpreting ethical experience,” therefore, the stress must be placed upon the word *alone*. For Wojtyła, the phenomenological method of philosophical investigation merely provides the basis for the development of a proper metaphysics.

(*potentia*) of the soul. ... [Because it cannot give an account of this becoming,] a phenomenology of the will alone does not suffice for interpreting ethical experience.²³

Wojtyła makes it clear, once again, that, for him, the problem is not the Aristotelean or Thomistic metaphysical framework *as such*. The problem, rather, is the fact that within this framework there is a tendency—a tendency to which both Aristotle and Aquinas succumb in their respective treatments of key questions—to reduce the human person to the status of an object: a *thing* among other things in the cosmos.²⁴ “Wojtyła accepts,” Rocco Buttiglione correctly asserts:

... that the traditional, nonphenomenological point of departure of anthropology objectifies man; his own point of departure is a phenomenological description of experience. While Wojtyła objects to the cosmological point of departure as inadequate in anthropology, he does not limit anthropology to phenomenology, and points to a transphenomenological approach for a complete anthropology. Wojtyła rejects Husserl’s idealistic turn, which leads to a subjectivist reflection and absolutization of consciousness.²⁵

For Wojtyła, what is missing from ethical and moral systems based on the “traditional, nonphenomenological anthropology,” which “objectifies man” from its “cosmological point of departure,” is what he calls the “personalistic norm,” the content of which he states clearly in his work *Love and Responsibility*, saying, “... we must never treat a person as a means to an end.

²³ K. Wojtyła, “The Problem of the Will in the Analysis of the Ethical Act,” in: Wojtyła, *Person and Community*, 20. This article originally appeared as K. Wojtyła, “Zagadnienie woli w analizie aktu etycznego,” *Roczniki Filozoficzne* Vol. 5, No. 1 (1955–57), 111–135. The present study will make clear that when Wojtyła says that a “phenomenology of the will alone does not suffice for interpreting ethical experience,” the stress must be placed upon the word *alone*. As Wojtyła uses the term *phenomenology* in this essay, he means specifically only a certain careful *method of observation* involving the distillation of what is *given* in experience. Because he understands phenomenology-proper in this way—that is to say, as a kind of *technique* for conducting observation—it cannot, by definition, stand alone in providing a philosophical explanation. All it does is provide the basis of raw data upon which philosophical explanations can be constructed. That said, there can be no question that Wojtyła believed deeply in phenomenology’s suitability for precisely this essential task, and that he considered himself a phenomenologist.

²⁴ On this point, see K. Wojtyła, “Ethics and Moral Theology,” especially 104.

²⁵ R. Buttiglione, *Karol Wojtyła: The Thought of the Man Who Became Pope John Paul II*, trans. by P. Guietti, F. Murphy (Grand Rapids, Michigan: William. B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 1997), 331.

[For] by giving man an intelligent and free nature ... [God] ordained that each man alone will decide for himself the ends of his activity, and not be a blind tool of someone else's ends."²⁶

Wojtyła derives this norm from Immanuel Kant's second formulation of the so-called "categorical imperative" in his *Groundwork of the Metaphysic of Morals*, where he writes, "Act in such a way that you always treat humanity whether in your own person or in the person of any other, never simply as a means, but always at the same time as an end."²⁷ Admittedly, within Kant's framework, this formulation of the categorical imperative does not admit of an end for the human person beyond himself, and on this point, Kant's anthropology differs markedly from that of both Aquinas and Wojtyła, and so also, then, does his theory of ethics. In adopting this formulation from Kant, therefore, and shaping it into his "personalistic norm," Wojtyła adapts it to an anthropology according to which the realization of our own personal good involves embracing a good beyond ourselves and doing so precisely *because* it is beyond ourselves. Wojtyła refers to this moment as "participation," and herein the human person achieves "transcendence" of his mere individuality—the moral event in which Wojtyła locates the very essence of the person-in-act.²⁸ But, while Aquinas also holds the view that human nature is oriented to a good beyond that of the individual—also sharing with Wojtyła the thesis that our human acts shape our moral quality and thus, our ontological condition as good or bad—²⁹ he does not share Wojtyła's view that our personal good is always realized when we fulfill our particular purpose in creation. Rather, for Aquinas, in some cases—and indeed, in most—the realization of fulfilling our particular purpose in creation may, as we will see, come at the positive exclusion of the good of the person as *person*.

By reducing the human person to the status of an object among other objects in the world—in other words, prioritizing the function he performs or the purpose he serves within the cosmos as a larger whole—the unique and unrepeatability value of the human person as a for-its-own-sake being is obscured, and a mechanistic functionality is allowed to replace that uniqueness in our

²⁶ K. Wojtyła, *Love and Responsibility*, trans. by H.T. Willetts (San Francisco: Ignatius Press, 1993), 27. This text originally appeared as, K. Wojtyła, *Miłość i odpowiedzialność* (Kraków: Wydawnictwo Znak, 1960).

²⁷ I. Kant, *Groundwork of the Metaphysic of Morals*, trans. by H.J. Paton (New York: Harper & Row Publishers, 1964), 96.

²⁸ K. Wojtyła, "The Person: Subject and Community," in: Wojtyła, *Person and Community*, 252–258, originally published as K. Wojtyła, "Osoba podmiot i wspólnota," *Roczniki Filozoficzne* Vol. 24, No. 2 (1976), 5–39.

²⁹ Wojtyła discusses this point of confluence in his essay, "The Personal Structure of Self-Determination," in: Wojtyła, *Person and Community*, 190–193. This essay originally appeared in print as K. Wojtyła, "Osobowa struktura samostanowienia," *Roczniki Filozoficzne* Vol. 29, No. 2 (1981), 5–12.

consideration of the person, of the person's dignity and worth, and thus of moral and even broadly theological questions.³⁰ Indeed, this tendency toward naturalistic reductionism is so pervasive a threat from within the Aristotelian-Thomistic philosophical and theological tradition that everything from anatomy to cosmology can give expression to it, and that, in sometimes rather disquieting ways.³¹

A Caveat on Wojtyła, Thomas, and Varying Thomisms

At this point, and before we proceed further, I should emphasize that I am not proposing here that Wojtyła rejects Thomas, only that he has found a point of departure between his own approach to ethics and that of Aquinas. To be sure, elements of personalism can be found in Thomas's anthropology. For example, as I have already noted, Aquinas holds that moral goodness consequent upon the human act redounds upon the ontological condition of the agent, who, being good or bad morally, is good or bad as a human being. This idea is fundamental to Wojtyła's ethico-centric anthropology, and on this basis, Wojtyła can speak meaningfully of a "Thomistic personalism." Saying that it is possible to formulate a personalist ethical framework on the basis of insights derived from the thought of Thomas Aquinas, however, is not the same thing as saying that Thomas is, himself, a personalist, nor that his system of thought is compatible with personalism without modification. By 1967, as we have already seen, Wojtyła himself stated as much explicitly.³²

³⁰ For example, Wojtyła cautions, thusly, in his essay "The Problem of Catholic Sexual Ethics: Reflections and Postulates," in: *Person and Community*, 279–299 – see, especially, 284–291. This essay originally appeared as K. Wojtyła, "Zagadnienie katolickiej etyki seksualnej: refleksje i postulatory," *Roczniki Filozoficzne* Vol. 13, No. 2 (1965), 5–25.

³¹ For example, cf. *Summa contra gentiles*, III, q. 94, a. 11, and q. 122, a. 4. It is important to understand that when Aquinas discusses the power of persons—i.e., individual substances of a rational nature—to exercise dominion over their own actions, "and which are not only made to act, like others; but which act of themselves" (*Summa theologiae*, I, q. 29, a. 1), he is speaking principally about the divine Persons, not human beings. So, while he holds that the created person is "what is most perfect in all nature" (*ST*, I, q. 29, a. 3), the fact remains that his metaphysic does not allow us to assert in an unqualified way that created persons, like God, "act of themselves," and "are not only made to act," but instead that God makes us to perform specifically those free acts he wills us to perform, and not others. His compatibilist theory of human free-will is worked out in his theory of predestination and reprobation, where, as we will see, it runs afoul of Wojtyła's personalistic norm. For English-language quotations from Aquinas's *Summa theologiae*, we use, throughout, St. Thomas Aquinas, *Summa Theologica*, 3 vols., trans. by Fathers of the English Dominican Province (New York: Benziger Brothers, Inc., 1947).

³² Wojtyła, "Ethics and Moral Theology," 103.

Thus, in the present work, it is not my intention to add further to the existing body of literature exploring the many and profound points of confluence and continuity between Thomas and Wojtyła, nor to those expounding upon the role he played in the larger Lublin School of Thomism, varied as it is. Rather, I seek to address a lacuna in drawing attention to what is *not* Thomistic in Wojtyła's thought, and to what is not personalist in the thought of Thomas Aquinas. I believe that doing so is necessary to restore a more honest understanding of the relationship between Wojtyła's "Thomistic personalism" and Thomas's own understanding of the meaning, purpose, and value of the human person in God's plan. On that score, I should stress that the reading of Thomas here is taken, with direct quotations, from Thomas's own texts. The texts chosen to make the point at the heart of this study may seem to some to paint an "extreme" view of Thomas's mind and a one-sided and distorted view of Wojtyła's posture toward it. Once again, however, that is not because the texts cited here are inauthentic, but only because the point of the article is a narrow one: to draw attention to a real difference between Aquinas and Wojtyła owing to "the general direction of the development of philosophy, which is a movement away from the philosophy of being toward the philosophy of consciousness,"³³ on the basis of which Wojtyła came to believe that Thomistic theology should undergo "significant modification."³⁴ The texts presented in this article are, further, illustrative of a certain line of thought within Thomas's system, openly defended by Classical Thomists in line with Domingo Báñez, including Réginald Garrigou-Lagrange,³⁵ Stephen A. Long,³⁶ and Thomas M. Osborne, Jr.³⁷ Their approach to Thomas fell out of favor in the wake of the Second Vatican Council, but it has enjoyed a significant resurgence in recent decades, especially in the United States. Many other variants of Thomism boast countless adherents,³⁸ and I am not suggesting that those who belong to those schools and do not hold the views I present here from St. Thomas are in no sense Thomists. Nonetheless, on the precise points at issue in the present study, the Classical Thomism of Domingo Báñez appears to me to represent a generally correct reading of St. Thomas in the texts considered here.

³³ *Ibid.*

³⁴ *Ibid.*

³⁵ R. Garrigou-Lagrange, *Predestination*, trans. by D.B. Rose (St. Louis, MO: B. Herder Book Co., 1944).

³⁶ S.A. Long, "Providence, Freedom, and Natural Law," *Nova et Vetera*, English Edition, Vol. 4, No. 3 (2006), 557-606.

³⁷ T.M. Osborne, Jr., "Thomist Premotion and Contemporary Philosophy of Religion," *Nova et Vetera*, English Edition, Vol. 4, No. 3 (2006), 607-632.

³⁸ R. Cessario, *A Short History of Thomism* (Washington, D.C.: The Catholic University of America Press, 2003).

Sexual Differentiation and the Condignity of the Sexes

Let us take, for example, the question of the relative dignity of woman to man. From within an Aristotelian framework, all contingent beings have some telic orientation and cosmic place. All things in the universe *tend* toward some *end*, seeking their ultimate resolution therein. All movement is understood on the basis of this premise. Heavy objects seek their downward place, acorns the maturity of the oak. But since all change is understood according to the reduction of some potentiality to a corresponding actuality, the development of a substance involves the interrelationship between some *active* and some *passive* principle. The active principle imparts form to matter, thus defining the object's *kinetic* trajectory.³⁹ The *father*—who is *male*—is seen as the source of the active principle in the generation of human beings, while the *mother*—who is female—is seen as the source of the *material* principle which finds itself *disposed to receive* a form: the form of the *father*, who, again, is *male*. Given the limited information available to Aristotle, and even to Aquinas—indeed, to any human being prior to the rise of contemporary biology—there seemed sound metaphysical reasons for holding this view, including the observable fact that children, who are less fully developed than adults, more closely resemble women than men in their overall morphology.⁴⁰ But this account of sexual differentiation still fails the test of *irreducibility*, and it ends with the assertion that the highest form of friendship is not available in

³⁹ See, Aristotle, *Generation of Animals*, 728^b22–729^b20, 730^a24–730^b31.

⁴⁰ Aristotle mentions this point in several places. In his, *On the Generation of Animals*, he observes, for example, that boys who are rendered eunuchs prior to puberty do not develop body hair beyond the pubic region, nor do their voices change, and that men rendered eunuchs tend to lose their body hair, except in the pubic region (784^a5–12). Similar discussions occur in *Problems* (294^b19–38, 895^a32–36, 897^b23–27). Aristotle also mentions the relationship between children and women when he speculates about why, in the bovine, the calf's voice tends to be lower than in the adult of the species, while this is typically not the case in other animals. He notes that this fact is consistent with his overall observation that the child bears a closer resemblance to the female in any given species than to the male, since, in the bovine, the voice of the cow tends to be lower than that of the bull (*Problems* 901^b24–29). Of course, today, we know that the physiology at work in the process of development from conception to adulthood is far more complex than Aristotle could have been expected to have imagined it to be. Given this complexity, the fact that children bear a closer resemblance to women than they do to men cannot, in any way, lead to the inference that women are somehow ontologically stunted.

the relationship between husband and wife⁴¹ because such a friendship requires *equality of dignity*, while the woman, as something *half-formed*,⁴² is ontologically inferior to her husband.

Admittedly, Scripture makes quite clear the fact that this mistake is difficult for fallen man to avoid,⁴³ and thus Aristotle can be excused, to some extent, for making it. But what of Aquinas? He has the benefit of revelation, in which the primeval condignity of man and woman is made

⁴¹ See Aristotle's discussion of friendship in Books VIII–IX of the *Nicomachean Ethics* (1156^b5–1172^a15). While he maintains that perfect friendship is based upon perfect equality (1156^b5–35), he goes on to say that the friendship of husband and wife is based upon a condition of inequality between the parties (1158^b13–18). To be fair to Aristotle, however, he does hold out the possibility that a friendship based upon virtue can arise between husband and wife in the event that both are virtuous (1162^a25–26), but he simultaneously holds that men and women cannot be virtuous in qualitatively the same way in every respect (*Politics*, 1277^b8–33).

⁴² *Generation of Animals*, 737^a27–29.

⁴³ This is very much to the point in the story of the Man and the Woman in the garden. The story shows the woman being made from the “rib” (עֲצָצָה = *tsélâ*) of the man—that is, from the *region of the body that envelops the heart: the very bones of the man in the deepest recesses of his being—the “chamber” of his soul*. The woman is formed of the man's own inner being—his deepest longings and vulnerabilities. At first, he does not, properly speaking, *name* her, as he names the other animals, placing them under his dominion. Rather, he *describes* her, discovering the fullness of his *own* identity in *her* otherness, and in the fact that her otherness has himself as its reference point. This enables him to see his own otherness to her, such that he discovers the fact that he, as a person, is referenced to another. He is called to make a gift of himself. (In his capacity as pope, John Paul II will develop this theme at length, for example, in the Wednesday *Audiences* he devoted to his *Theology of the Body*. See, especially, those lessons delivered during the span of January 2–February 20, 1980.) The Hebrew text also makes the point of male-female mutuality rather clearly when God says, “I will make a helper over-against him” or “a helper fitted-to-him” or “present-to-him” (עֹזֵר כְּנַגְדּוֹ = *e'ēšeh lōw 'ezer kandeḡōw*) to describe what God intended the woman to be for the man when he first declared that “it is not good for the man to be alone” (Gen 2:18). She is to be *one-fitted-to-him*, not in the sense of subordination, but in the sense of complementarity and, to borrow a phrase from Martin Buber, “personal making present” (M. Buber, “Elements of the Interhuman,” trans. by R.G. Smith, in: M. Buber, *The Knowledge of Man: Selected Essays*, ed. M. Friedman (Atlantic Highlands, NJ: Humanities Press International, Inc, 1988), 68–71). Thus, it is only *after sin* that the woman becomes finally subjugated to the man and given over to his exploitation (3:16). This point is made, not only in God's utterance of the curse at 3:16, but also in the fact that the Man goes on to *name* her, in the proper sense, as they leave the garden (3:20). More subtly, revelation actually references this paradox in the fact that, in the *Decalogue*, the commandment against coveting one's neighbor's *possessions* and that against coveting his *wife* are given together in a single proposition (Exodus 20:17, Deuteronomy 5:21). This leads to ambiguity, such that the real meaning of the commandments concerning these questions can only be discerned if the heart is pure. Only, in other words, if we are sensitive to the *personalistic norm*, will we be able to see, given the concupiscible burden of fallenness, that a woman simply *cannot* be a possession, and thus that the sin of coveting one's neighbor's ox is not only *quantitatively* but *qualitatively* different from that of coveting his wife. John Paul II points out that the predominating language of the Old Testament did tend to objectify the woman as a kind of property belonging to her husband, and that the legal recognition of polygamy was, itself, a manifestation of this tendency (see his Wednesday *Audiences* of August 13, 1980–August 20, 1980). With Christianity, the ambiguity of the commandments is overcome, not only with Christ's restoration of the pure state of matrimony as it was “from the beginning,” and thus, the prohibition of divorce (Cf. Matthew 19:3–9), but also in Paul's development of the Bridegroom imagery according to which he works out a fully sacramental understanding of the relationship between husband and wife in the life of grace (Ephesians 5:21–33). For John Paul II's work on the *Theology of the Body* see John Paul II, *Man and Woman He Created Them: A Theology of the Body*, trans. by M. Waldstein (Boston: Pauline Books & Media, 2006) – we reference, here, pp. 177–204, and 267–274. For the Hebrew Old Testament, see *The Interlinear Hebrew-Greek-English Bible*, 4 vols., ed. & trans. by J.P. Green, Sr. (Hendrickson Publishers, 2009), vols. 1–3.

plain, and femininity revered as the fundamental expression of the human person's posture in relationship to God, who seeks us as his bride.

Actually, Aquinas does not fully perceive this truth. While he rejects Aristotle's conclusion that the highest form of friendship is not available between husband and wife,⁴⁴ he does not reject the underlying premise upon which Aristotle advances his argument.⁴⁵ Instead, pointing to the sacramental fullness of matrimony as an image of Christ's relationship to the Church, he appeals to the gift of *grace* by which a lower nature can be raised to a higher *posse*, such that, through the sacramental grace of matrimony, the woman is given a sort of *analogous* condignity with her husband,⁴⁶ just as the human person is, in this way, given condignity with God through the infusion of sanctifying grace, without thereby altering the brute fact of the creature's inherent inferiority.

It is worthy of note, of course, that while Aquinas accepts the claim that God presents his "image" in human being in both sexes,⁴⁷ he does not suppose that there is really anything about human sexuality *per se* to manifest that image.⁴⁸ Prudence Allen characterizes this view, which she calls "gender unity," as "supporting the importance of a sexless soul, and devaluing the human body."⁴⁹ The inner co-equality of relationality belonging to the nature of the Triune God does not,

⁴⁴ *ScG*, III, q. 123, a. 6.

⁴⁵ Indeed, Aquinas is quite explicit on the ontological inferiority of women. See, for example, *ST*, I, q. 92, a. 1, ad 2; I, q. 93, a. 4, ad 1; *ScG*, III, c. 94, §11; and *Quaestiones disputatae de veritate*, q. 5, a. 9, ad 9.

⁴⁶ *ST*, III-Suppl, q. 49, a. 3. Here, Aquinas argues that *indissolubility* is the effect of grace in matrimony, and thus that this imprints a kind of character upon the recipients of the sacrament. In this case, it gives the man and the woman power over one another at the bodily level, extending beyond what natural procreative obligation appears to require. This kind of union gives the wife a share in her husband's life, and thus inferentially, a kind of *equality* with him, through the grace the sacrament affords. This degree of equality would not be possible in a purely natural marriage. Now, in his *Sententia libri ethicorum* (VIII, Lect. 12, §1723), Aquinas grants Aristotle's observation that if both husband and wife are virtuous, their marriage can be based on virtue (*Nicomachean Ethics* 1162^a19–24). But this alone does not raise the status of their friendship to the highest form, since the highest form of friendship requires equality *in all ways* (1156^b5–35), while the virtues proper to husband and wife are different, in a way *analogous to*, but *not quite reducible to*, that proper to master and servant (*Politics* 1277^b8–33). While, for Aquinas, a form of equality exists even in a purely natural (i.e., *licit*, but *non-sacramental*) marriage (*ScG*, III, q. 124, aa. 4–5), that equality is really one based upon a kind of *constitutional arrangement* whereby a micro-political organism is formed. The husband and wife are equal in the sense that the foot and the eye are equally oriented toward the good of the body, even as the eye possesses the greater dignity (*ibid.* III, q. 94, a. 11). The friendship of husband and wife may be based on virtue, but it is not the same *sort* of virtue; it is a virtue of *inequality* and, thus, preclusive of friendship's highest form without some superaddition to nature (cf. *ibid.* III, q. 123, a. 7).

⁴⁷ *ST*, I, q. 93, a. 4.

⁴⁸ *Ibid.* I, q. 93, a. 6.

⁴⁹ P. Allen, *The Concept of Women, II: The Early Humanistic Revolution, 1250–1500* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2002), 231. For more on the Neoplatonic roots of this issue in the period she describes as "early humanism," see the entire discussion under the subtitle, "Christian, Neoplatonic, and Stoic Roots of Early Humanist Views of Women", 224–233.

for Aquinas, find expression in the phenomenological given of human sexual differentiation, as such. Indeed, he explicitly denies this assertion⁵⁰—a fact that, ironically, evinces the presence of the concept in his own time. Rather, Aquinas sees the image of God in the human being expressed exclusively in the specifying *differentia* of human nature, i.e., *rationality*.⁵¹ He thus sees the distinction of the sexes as essentially twofold in purpose, at least as far as so-called “pure nature” is concerned. First, it affords the opportunity for the continuity in generative unity of rational animality, wherein the image of God, who is *rational*, is manifest in the material universe.⁵² Second, precisely inasmuch as sexual distinction rests, according to this Aristotelian perspective, in a diversity of *ontic nobility*, it allows God to manifest his qualitative infinity in a universe of finite beings by expressing his majesty in the multiplication of creatures across a vast ontological gradation.⁵³

Wojtyła, as John Paul II, takes a rather different stance with respect to this question; and he does so on the basis of the personalistic norm that allows room for the philosopher to “pause at the irreducible,”⁵⁴ and to question his metaphysical presumptions in light of what is clearly given about the person in the phenomenological moment. John Paul II is able to acknowledge that human sexual differentiation, as such, manifests the image of God.⁵⁵ Human persons discover, in their *maleness* and *femaleness*, a mutual orientation to the *other*. Most of all through sexual differentiation, the human person is able to *know* and *be known*, both *by himself* and *by the other*; and thus, in his own deepened *self-aware self-possession*, he is able to make a *gift* of himself to one who *receives* him and *embodies* him without consuming and negating him.⁵⁶

⁵⁰ *ST*, I, q. 93, a. 6, ad 2.

⁵¹ *Ibid.* I, q. 93, a. 6.

⁵² *ScG*, III, q. 94, a. 11; *De verit.*, q. V, a. 9, ad 9.

⁵³ Cf. *ST*, I, q. 92, aa. 1–2; *ScG*, III, q. 94, a. 11; and *De verit.*, q. V, a. 9, ad 9.

⁵⁴ K. Wojtyła, “Subjectivity and the Irreducible in the Human Being,” in: *Person and Community*, 213–214. This essay, pivotal for any real understanding of Wojtyła’s broader philosophical views, originally appeared as K. Wojtyła, “Podmiotowość i ‘to co nieredukowalne’ w człowieku,” *Ethos* Vol. 1, No. 2–3 (1988), 21–28. According to the editorial notes appended to the translation, this paper is considerably earlier than its first publication would suggest; Wojtyła sent it to a conference in Paris, held June 13–14, 1975. Beyond the date of the conference, no further specifics of the event are provided.

⁵⁵ Cf. Wojtyła, *Man and Woman He Created Them*, 163–164. In this passage, delivered November 14, 1979, John Paul II not only suggests that the creation of the human being as “male and female” *does* present us with an image of God in and through sexual differentiation, but that, in fact, this *relational* dimension of the divine image “constitutes perhaps the deepest theological aspect of everything we can say about man” (164). The view expressed by John Paul II here borrows very closely from the Trinitarian model discussed by St. Augustine in his *De Trinitate*, XII.5—a view Aquinas had come to dismiss as “manifestly absurd” (*ST*, I, q. 93, a. 6, ad 2).

⁵⁶ This is precisely the line of reasoning employed by Paul VI in his encyclical letter, *Humanae vitae* (25 July 1968), §§8–9. Wojtyła discusses this idea in his essay, K. Wojtyła, “The Teaching of the Encyclical *Humanae Vitae* on Love:

This philosophical awareness prepares John Paul II to receive the Scriptural witness of Genesis in a way that seemingly escapes the horizons of Aquinas's theological imagination; and thus is born, for the Church, a new and revitalizing theological approach—that of *somatic theology* or, as it is more commonly known, *the theology of the body*.⁵⁷

Before going further in the present critique, of course, we should point out that the phenomenological method, though refined and brought to maturity in the twentieth century, is, at its root, properly something belonging, first above all, to precisely that philosophical realism to which Aristotle and Aquinas, and so many of the Scholastics, had attempted to give voice. Experience, and the *roots* of that experience, provide the brute facts concerning which whatever else we say must give account. These *givens* are to be the *matter* of our philosophical discourse—a matter already disposed to a certain *form* that comes to be known through a process, not of manipulation or contrivance, but of *discovery*, precisely in and through our encounter with the concrete evidence presented to us by the world. That being said—and we cannot enter into any lengthy discussion of the matter here, for it would take us far afield of our stated purpose—Duns Scotus, however much he may be criticized in his own right, must be heralded among the Scholastics for his sensitivity to the phenomenological given and his readiness to “pause before the irreducible.” He did not hold the Aristotelian-Thomistic view of the woman as an ontological inferior, but instead saw, consistent with revelation, that the woman, along with the man, operates as an active principle in the order of generation.⁵⁸ He knew no more about reproductive biology than Aquinas, but he was able to step back and allow what was given in the phenomenological moment to, as Wojtyła says, “have the upper hand” over metaphysical abstraction,⁵⁹ and thus to

An Analysis of the Text,” in: Wojtyła, *Person and Community*, 301–314. This essay originally appeared as K. Wojtyła, “Nauka encykliki ‘Humanae vitae’ o miłości,” *Analecta Cracoviensia* 1 (1969), 341–356, which he delivered in September 1968 at a theological conference on *Humanae vitae* (editorial note in *Person and Community*, 301). This theme is also consistent with his thinking in *Love and Responsibility*, and in his *theology of the body*, which he developed thoroughly early in his papacy as John Paul II.

⁵⁷ Indeed, what we describe here is the essential thrust of the whole project. Again, see Wojtyła, *Man and Woman He Created Them*, (in toto).

⁵⁸ *Ordinatio* III, dist. 4, q. *unica*. This text, in both Latin and English, with a worthy complement of notes, is readily available in John Duns Scotus, *Four Questions on Mary*, trans. by A.B. Wolter (Saint Bonaventure, New York: The Franciscan Institute, 2000), 77–110.

⁵⁹ In his essay, “Subjectivity and the Irreducible,” Wojtyła says, “We cannot complete the picture through [metaphysical or naturalistic] reduction alone; we also cannot remain within the framework of the irreducible alone (for then we would not be able to get beyond the pure self). The one must be cognitively supplemented by the other. Nevertheless, given the variety of circumstances of the real existence of human beings, we must always leave the greater space in this cognitive effort for the irreducible; we must, as it were, give the irreducible the upper hand when thinking about the human being that is invisible and wholly internal and whereby each human being, myself

set a task for metaphysics as a discipline. Scotus was prepared to accept the challenge of re-examining his metaphysical principles and their implications in light of the givenness of real-life experience.⁶⁰ In the end, it is precisely the fruits of his phenomenological sensitivity with respect to this point that disposed him, philosophically, to receive from within the deposit of faith, as a theologian, the truth of the Immaculate Conception of the Virgin Mary and the scope of its importance to the whole of the faith.⁶¹

In any event, we have, in the absence of this habitual readiness to “pause before the irreducible,” a rather distorted view of human sexual differentiation and sexual meaning. From within this distorted view, we are led, moreover, to still other distorted conclusions in the realm of human sexuality. These arise, once again, on the basis of an overly *naturalistic* understanding of the human person.⁶²

The Sexual Act and Sexual Sin

The sexual act is *by nature* oriented to generation; and thus, any intentional subversion of that dimension of the act is *immoral* precisely insofar as it constitutes a free and informed choice—a human act—to contravene what is proper to nature. It is an offense against the natural law because, as rational beings, we are able to understand the order of nature, and thus we are bound to assent to that order as our own good.⁶³ This, all conscientious Catholic moralists would affirm

included, is an ‘eyewitness’ of his or her own self—of his or her own humanity and person” (p. 214). A bit later in the same essay, he writes, “What does it mean to *pause cognitively at lived experience*? This ‘pausing’ should be understood in relation to the irreducible” (p. 215). Given the discussion in the whole of the essay, and in particular in the passages immediately following this second quote, it is clear that Wojtyła is speaking of the prerogative of the phenomenological method in directing and correcting metaphysical analyses. Indeed, he goes on to say, “The thinker seeking the ultimate philosophical truth about the human being no longer moves in a ‘purely metaphysical terrain,’ but finds elements in abundance testifying to both the materiality and the spirituality of the human being, elements that bring both of these aspects into sharper relief. These elements then form the building blocks for further metaphysical construction” (p. 216).

⁶⁰ For a more thorough discussion of the divergence between Scotus and Aquinas on the question of sexual differentiation, see R.H. Bulzacchelli, “Femininity as a Positive Perfection and the Active Participation of Woman in Generativity in the Philosophical Theology of John Duns Scotus,” in: *A Companion to Medieval Christian Humanism: Essays on Principal Thinkers*, ed. J.P. Bequette, Brill’s Companion to the Christian Tradition: A Series on the Intellectual and Religious Life of Europe, 500–1800, ed. Christopher M. Bellitto, vol. 69 (Leiden and Boston: Brill, 2016), 274–296.

⁶¹ *Ordinatio* III, dist. 3, q. 1. Again, the reader may find this text in Latin and English with notes in *Four Questions on Mary*, 29–62.

⁶² K. Wojtyła, “The Problem of Catholic Sexual Ethics: Reflections and Postulates,” 288–291.

⁶³ *ScG*, III, q. 122, aa. 4–5.

without hesitation; but if we follow this line of reasoning too far before taking the time to “pause before the irreducible,” we end by weighing the relative gravity of various sexual sins in an intuitively bizarre and offensive way. For, according to Aquinas, this line of reasoning leads inexorably to the conclusion that masturbation, homosexual acts, outright bestiality, and the deliberate exclusion of the generative potency of the act between heterosexual partners are all qualitatively, and therefore, absolutely, more serious than rape and adultery.⁶⁴ Indeed, Aquinas states quite explicitly that these sins rank second only to homicide.⁶⁵

Aquinas is certainly correct to conclude that all four of these acts are objectively disordered and constitute grave matter, at the very least. But again, his analysis here fails the test of irreducibility. “Getting to the Bottom” of morality by explaining it on the basis of the ultimate end,” writes Wojtyła, “has given way to explaining and justifying morality on the basis of values and norms. We are concerned today not so much with determining the ultimate end of moral conduct as with giving an ultimate justification of the norms of morality.”⁶⁶

From within the scope of a personalist analysis, these acts, however similar at the purely biological level—considering the natural generative purpose of the sexual organs—are really not reducible in the way Aquinas suggests. Phenomenologically, the real issues involved here are obvious. It is true, as Aquinas points out, that homosexual acts and acts of bestiality differ, biologically, on the basis of the fact that the first involves the use of the sexual organs within the context of an encounter with an individual of the wrong *sex*, while the second involves such

⁶⁴ *ST*, II-II, q. 154, a. 12.

⁶⁵ “Nor, in fact, should it be deemed a slight sin for a man to arrange for the emission of semen apart from the proper purpose of generating and bringing up children. . . . [T]he inordinate emission of semen is incompatible with the natural good; namely the preservation of the species. Hence, after the sin of homicide whereby a human nature already in existence is destroyed, this type of sin appears to take next place, for by it the generation of human nature is precluded” (*ScG*, III, q. 122 a. 9). We quote here from Saint Thomas Aquinas, *Summa contra gentiles*, 5 vols., trans. by A.C. Pegis (Notre Dame: University of Notre Dame Press, 1975).

⁶⁶ Wojtyła, “Ethics and Moral Theology,” 103. Here, there can be no question that Wojtyła understands himself to depart from Aquinas on this matter: “The credit for bringing about this change in how the central problem of ethics is posed and formulated undeniably goes to Kant. But to accept Kant’s point of departure in ethics—that is, to regard the problem of the justification of norms as the chief ethical problem—is not necessarily to accept Kant’s solution. Indeed, a search for the ultimate justification of moral norms may lead us straight to the ultimate end. This is not presupposed in advance in the point of departure. One thing, however, is presupposed right from the start: in the whole way ethics is treated, normative rather than teleological tendencies will prevail, even in the case of ‘teleological’ conclusions” (*ibid.*). Once again, for Wojtyła, this alteration in his point of departure from teleological to normative reasoning represents precisely the sort of “serious modification” to Thomistic moral theology he deems necessary (*ibid.*), and which cannot be presupposed from the start to yield the same conclusions. Even if it often does, the reasoning by which those conclusions are justified will not be the same.

use with an individual of the wrong *species*;⁶⁷ and he is probably correct to say that the latter is more seriously disordered than the former.⁶⁸ But in naming the reason for the relative gravity of these sins, he misses the more fundamental issue—that, in the case of bestiality, inasmuch as the act is performed with a member of a different *species*, it attempts a somatic union with a *non-person*. Failure to take this fact into account—the fact of the *personhood* or *non-personhood* of the sexual-other—cuts us off from a fully mature analysis of the moral stakes in question.⁶⁹ The same must be said of contraceptive acts between heterosexuals.⁷⁰ Indeed, the juxtaposition, so commonly offered in today’s socio-political debates, of the committed homosexual relationship over against the transient, intentionally infecund, heterosexual encounter, in many respects forces precisely the right questions here. Aquinas’s judgment that contraceptive heterosexual acts are less grave than homosexual acts may be correct in the final analysis, but to make the case strictly on the grounds of the natural orientation of the organs is, once again, to miss the deeper point. It is to ignore the phenomenological givenness of sexual differentiation, precisely at the point of personal irreducibility; for we must insist that while sexual differentiation includes the biological purpose of the sexual act, it also transcends it quite definitively. Sexual differentiation thus includes other dimensions of meaning which must be taken into consideration if the nature of the offense is fully to be understood. The issue is not simply one of the orientation of the offenders’ respective *body parts*, but much more importantly, what it means to be *male* and *female*, and what it means to be a *psychosomatic unity* whose body-form reveals a truth about our identity, and about the fundamental orientation of our very *personhood*.

That being said, we can return, again, to the question of masturbation, which, by its very nature, often feigns, in the psyche of the sinner, a dimension of the experiential gesture of interpersonal encounter and mutual self-donation even while definitively excluding it. For that reason, Aquinas’s naturalistic analysis treats only the most superficial truth about the act, failing, thereby, to deal with the real problem. Masturbation represents its own sort of evil, thus engendering different moral consequences, both for the sinner and for the larger human

⁶⁷ *ST*, II-II, q. 154, a. 12, ad 4.

⁶⁸ *Ibid.*

⁶⁹ Cf. Wojtyła, “The Problem of Catholic Sexual Ethics,” 284–291. Wojtyła does not concern himself here, at all, with the question of homosexuality, but the reasoning he employs is easily applied.

⁷⁰ Indeed, see Wojtyła, “The Teaching of the Encyclical *Humanae Vitae* on Love,” 304–310, and, especially, 308.

community, than the other acts we have thus far considered.⁷¹ *Is it* correct to say that the use of the sexual organs without venereal contact is more profoundly evil than the use of the same organs in a potentially fecund but morally self-directed, uncommitted, and commoditizing act of fornication? Psychologically, an act of masturbation may well stem from an otherwise healthy orientation toward fully marital intercourse, open to procreation, as the agent experiences the frustration arising from the absence of a marital relationship. The objective biology of the act is one thing—and we must, admittedly, accept the moral truth comported therein—but the motivating moral value to which the sin-act gives concrete expression can *neither* be ignored in the analysis. The irreducibility of the *person to nature* and *biology* defies any attempt to package masturbation, sodomy, and bestiality together in the way that Aquinas attempts to package them, because his taxonomy of sin, here, rests upon an emphasis so reductionistic as to pass by, entirely, the domain of lived experience whereby the irreducible human person is disclosed. Indeed, to do so would be a disservice, because the moralist would thereby forego an opportunity to bring to light the fullness of the moral truth, consequently abandoning any reasonable attempt to persuade *of* that truth those engaged in these behaviors, who know from the givenness of their own experience that such demarcations lack sufficient nuance to be finally trustworthy.

This, however, is not the end of the problem for Aquinas. For, as we have said, on the very same naturalistic grounds according to which he has argued thus far, he goes on to assert that, precisely insofar as the aforementioned acts positively exclude the procreative purpose of

⁷¹ It would be impossible to undertake a thorough analysis of the problem of masturbation here, but we can offer a brief indication of the direction such an analysis would have to take if we wished to offer a *personalist* treatment, rather than a strictly *naturalist* treatment, which now seems inadequate. Because masturbation involves the satisfaction of the sexual urge outside the context of mutual self-giving and is, thus, an *inward turning* in response to the urge to *transcend the limits of self-enclosure*, it ends by radicalizing the alienation of loneliness. This happens because there is a close link in human beings between the arousal of the sexual urge and the subjective experience of personal separateness. Ironically, therefore, masturbation tends to be addictive, even to the point at which the offender forgoes actual human contact for the sake of satisfying the sexual urge which, though temporarily quieted, *re-presents* itself with ever-greater intensity. The problem stems, really, from the fact that the sexual urge in human beings comports a spiritual and personal significance, calling the human person *out of* himself or herself, into the realm of the *interpersonal* and, finally, into the realm of the *we*. Thus, the sexual urge calls us to locate the *Self* in the *other*, while sexual sin tends to reverse this trajectory to varying degrees, with an attempt to locate the *other* in the *Self*. Masturbation clearly manifests this turn with its characteristic accompaniment of sexual fantasy, in which the *object* of desire—another human being—is denied any authentic personal subjectivity, but is instead *constructed* in the mind of the offender according to the prescriptions of the offender's own desires. This is why sexual sin—most of all masturbation—can never satisfy the sexual urge in the way that a genuine covenantal conjugal relationship can. It does not answer the *spiritual* need for personal self-transcendence that gives rise to it, but instead leaves the offender trapped within his or her own personal self-enclosure.

the sexual organs in the process of their use, they are the *most grave* of all sexual sins.⁷² Aquinas is quite clear on this point: *rape* is *not* as serious a sin as *masturbation*, because while masturbation positively frustrates the generative orientation of the sexual organs in their use, rape does not; it is, at least in theory, possible for a rapist to impregnate his victim.⁷³ Indeed, for Aquinas, *rape*, as such, does not sink to the level of *any* of the sins we have mentioned thus far, for, where all of those sins are closed to the generative orientation of the sexual act, rape alone is open to it. But are we really prepared to say that even contraceptive intercourse between husband and wife is morally worse than *rape*, where the generative orientation of the sexual organs is not positively frustrated? Once we “pause at the irreducible,” it becomes clear that to intrude upon the psychosomatic self-determination of the person is an offense fundamentally more perverse than giving reciprocity to another person’s voluntarily self-exploitive inclinations. Both are morally wrong, and gravely so; but it remains important to name the precise nature of the sin in each case. If we fail to do so—in this case especially—we end by violating the dignity of the human person by a sheer act of philosophical analysis, inasmuch as we fail to give the *irreducible person* the upper hand over metaphysics.⁷⁴

⁷² *ST*, II-II, q. 154, a. 12.

⁷³ *Ibid.*

⁷⁴ In the case of fornication, both parties sin, while in the case of rape, only the offender sins. Paradoxically, however, rape is more serious precisely because the victim is denied any real agency in the governance of her own person—her own psychosomatic integrity—in precisely that dimension of her bodily existence most closely tied to the value-modality of *self-possession* : *self-donation* (cf., on the concept of “value-modalities,” M. Scheler, *Formalism in Ethics and Non-Formal Ethics of Values: A New Attempt toward the Foundation of an Ethical Personalism*, trans. by M.S. Fings, R.L. Funk, Northwestern University Studies in Phenomenology & Existential Philosophy Series, ed. John Wild (Evanston, IL: Northwestern University Press, 1973), 104). This, after all, is really what it means to be *raped*. The exercise of the sexual faculty cuts to the very deepest reaches of our psychosomatic unity, such that to deny someone, in this very sphere, the dignity of *personal subjectivity*—that is, being *the subject of his or her own actions*—is to reduce that person to the status of a mere *object*. The offender fundamentally excludes his victim from the act, even as he absorbs her in it as its direct object. Rape, therefore, is among the most acute instances of what Wojtyła names *alienation*—that is, the opposite of what he calls, “participation,” which requires subjective affirmation, through personal action, of a commonly-affirmed value, as a consciously and freely affirmed dimension of each agent’s self-fulfillment (Wojtyła, “The Person: Subject and Community,” 252–258). We can and should argue, of course, that fornication also objectifies the person in a certain sense. But *lived experience* makes clear that human beings respond in profoundly different ways to these two modes of exploitation. Rape is *total* objectification, fornication is not, no matter how close it may come to the line. Indeed, this is precisely the point at issue in society’s outcry against “date rape drugs,” which are used to dissociate a woman’s *psychical discretion* from her *somatic activations*, reducing her to a non-participating sexual robot. The Casanova may care little about *who* his conquest is, but his thrill can only come through her voluntary self-surrender. The date-rapist has lost sight of even this value; he takes the outward appearance of surrender at the expense of its inner, voluntary character. This is an essential difference between fornication and date rape—an act which is really and properly rape. From a personalist point of view, this difference places rape at the very top of the hierarchy of sexual sins.

Today, many moralists who confess explicit fidelity to magisterial authority, and who ground their considerations in the personalist approach of John Paul II himself, would regard the presence of seminal fluids, with their potential to result in a wholly uninvited pregnancy consequent upon a violation of the woman's personal self-possession, as a *continuing assault*, and they would, on that basis, countenance the use of strictly anti-ovulatory measures provided there is no risk of abortion.⁷⁵ These thinkers reject the characterization of such measures as properly "contraceptive," since the question of *contraception* is taken to involve a *willingness* to engage in the sexual act, but with the intention, then, of frustrating its purpose. In the present case, however, there is no intention to frustrate the purpose of a sexual act, since the rape victim has not participated in any sexual *act qua act* at all. Indeed, her assailant has simply performed a sexual act, biologically speaking, upon her, unilaterally.⁷⁶ The use of anti-ovulatory interventions in this case represents, therefore, an attempt to preserve what remains, if anything, of the self-determination of the woman, whose *somatic boundaries* constitute a sacred space not to be transgressed through an act of interpersonal trespass wholly antithetical to her will. Those who endorse such interventions would argue that a woman enjoys a clear right never to *abort* a pregnancy, no matter the circumstances under which she conceived, but certainly to *prevent* a pregnancy consequent upon *rape*—and that, precisely on the basis of the *personalistic norm*, apart from which the deeper meaning of human sexuality, and thus of the sexual act, cannot be fully understood. For the time being at least, the Church appears to entrust this question to the academic debate, and to tolerate within the bounds of Catholic moral conduct the recommendations of these moralists. That fact alone speaks volumes about the Church's refusal to reduce the sexual act to the level of a purely natural purpose.

⁷⁵ Indeed, this is the official position of the United States Conference of Catholic Bishops, as articulated in *Ethical and Religious Directives for Catholic Health Care Services*, 4th ed. (Washington, D.C.: United States Conference of Catholic Bishops, June 15, 2001), III.36. The bishops advise that "A female who has been raped should be able to defend herself against a potential conception from the sexual assault. If, after appropriate testing, there is no evidence that conception has occurred already, she may be treated with medications that would prevent ovulation, sperm capacitation, or fertilization. It is not permissible, however, to initiate or to recommend treatments that have as their purpose or direct effect the removal, destruction, or interference with the implantation of a fertilized ovum."

⁷⁶ Wojtyła is quite insistent on this point in *The Acting Person*. He draws the distinction between an *activity* or *activation*, on the one hand, and an *act* in the full and proper sense, on the other. The latter implies *efficacious auto-determinism*. Thus, Wojtyła essentially equates the terms *act* and *human act*. On the part of the victim, rape is, by its very definition, not a human act, because it does not proceed from free-will (as in the case of *forcible* rape) or understanding (as in the case of *statutory* rape, for example).

The Person and the Community

Now, we have spoken, thus far, only about matters pertaining to the ethics of the sexual act, and how too heavy an emphasis upon a naturalistic understanding of the human person often leads to incomplete and sometimes altogether errant judgments in this arena. But the implications of the naturalistic approach to the human person go deeper than this. For Aquinas, because the human person exists for the purpose of instantiating a nature—the *rational* nature—which can be realized according to varying degrees of perfection, the human being is really viewed not principally as an end in himself but as a *means* to a still higher end determined by God.⁷⁷ The primary value here is not the individual *person*, but the *species*, for the sake of which the individual person exists. Wojtyła recognizes and even legitimizes what is correct in Aquinas’s intuition, here—namely that the human individual cannot be understood solely in respect of himself, but always, at the very core of his being, is already a kind of reference to the *other*—to a *community* of persons.⁷⁸ But their confluence on this quality of the human person does not mean that we can simply *equate* the view of Wojtyła with that of Aquinas on the broader question of the person in relation to the community

⁷⁷ See, for example, *ST*, I, qq. 22–23; *ScG*, III, q. 94, a. 11. Aquinas is explicit in his assertion that the human person is *not* an end in himself, but an end ordered to something greater—something for the sake of which the individual person’s naturally (or even supernaturally) ordered good may have to be frustrated according to God’s providence. In spite of this, the contrary view is widely assigned to him. That said, it may well be the case that, in the mediaeval West, Aquinas first cast certain questions or concepts in a light that allowed for later development in the direction the Church, and even the wider philosophical discussion, have been able to follow to a fully personalist conclusion. This fully personalist position is affirmed consistently by Karol Wojtyła / John Paul II and finds articulation at the Second Vatican Council in the claim that the human person “... is the only creature on earth which God willed for itself” (Vatican Council II, Pastoral Constitution on the Church in the Modern World, *Gaudium et spes* (7 December 1965), §24). It would be difficult to deny that this position expresses the mature mind of the Church, and that the Church sees this articulation as expressing the inner content of revelation in a rich and penetrating way. Nonetheless, this position is emphatically *not* that of Aquinas himself. In an earlier work of my own, I am guilty of ascribing the personalist view of the individual human being to Aquinas (R.H. Bulzacchelli, *Judged by the Law of Freedom: A History of the Faith-Works Controversy and a Resolution in the Thought of St. Thomas Aquinas* (Lanham, MD: University Press of America, 2006), 53). Wojtyła seems to do this as well (“Thomistic Personalism,” especially 166–167, 174) since, there, he does not draw any distinction between the propositions “human beings are the noblest creatures in the universe” and “human beings are made for their own sakes.” Neither had I done so in my own earlier work. For Aquinas, however, the first proposition is true, but not the second. He would acknowledge that all things in the universe are ordained for the good of human beings, but he would not accept the claim that the universe as a whole is so ordained. Aquinas does not say, in other words, that “the universe exists for the sake of the human person,” but that “the human person exists for the sake of the universe” (*ST*, I, q. 23, a. 7).

⁷⁸ Wojtyła, “Thomistic Personalism,” 173–174. Cf., also, *Gaudium et spes*, §25.

or the species. Indeed, the point of departure between the two can be illustrated clearly in their respective attitudes toward the just use of capital punishment.

On the question of capital punishment, Aquinas can only be characterized as an *enthusiast*. Because the human being exists to instantiate the rational nature and has his fundamental value as an individual precisely in this, a descent from rationality—as through sin—means a diminution of his *objective value*.⁷⁹ Of course, we must be careful to understand this point correctly, as Wojtyła, for his own part, certainly does. Aquinas’s metaphysic prevents him from suggesting that the human being ceases to be *human* by nature on account of sin;⁸⁰ and as far as this point goes, Wojtyła finds, in Aquinas, something of profound importance, especially for today’s debates over the whole panoply of life issues.⁸¹ Wojtyła also finds, in Aquinas, the important intuition that the human being can change his *moral character* in and through his acts.⁸² But where Aquinas’s belief that not only the moral *character* of the person but also the person’s *fundamental value* as an individual is tied to his acts, Wojtyła and Aquinas must part company. Again, Aquinas’s conclusion here is really the result of his tendency to engage in *natural reductionism*, whereby the natural purpose of the person is subordinated to a larger social purpose in quite the same way that a *body part* has its purpose and value in the *whole*.⁸³ Ironically, where Aquinas *underemphasized* this wholeness in his consideration of sexual issues, he now *overemphasizes* it in his treatment of this political issue. In both cases, he has lost sight of the *person* as the irreducible reference point of our considerations. For, in Aquinas’s view, the sinner is regarded, precisely in

⁷⁹ *ST*, II-II, q. 64, a. 2, ad 3.

⁸⁰ Cf. *ST*, II-II, q. 64, a. 3, ad 2. For Aquinas, *nature* pertains to what is *essential* in the human being, while *sin* is an *accidental characteristic*. It is one of the possible contraries a substance is capable of assuming; but the substance is capable of assuming it only on account of that which is essential to it. The fact that the human being is capable both of *sin* and *repentance* (even if repentance is only possible through grace) reveals to us that a substance—the human being—perdures through sin.

⁸¹ Cf. K. Wojtyła, *The Acting Person*, trans. by A. Potocki (Dordrecht: D. Reidel Publishing Company, 1979), ch. 3.2 (pp. 112–113), 3.3 (p. 120), 3.6 (pp. 130–131), 3.9 (pp. 146–147). See also his later work in his capacity as the Successor of Peter, Pope John Paul II, in the encyclical letter *Veritatis splendor* (6 August 1993), §§75, 78.

⁸² This is among the central points at issue in *The Acting Person*, for example. In his magisterial writings, of course, this point remained, for John Paul II, a central issue, and is at the root of his comments in *Veritatis splendor*, when he critiques a wide range of contemporary ethical theories (§§65–70, 74–75). Cf., also, John Paul II, *Fides et ratio*, §89.

⁸³ *ST*, II-II, q. 64, a. 2. Wojtyła sees this as a problem to which the events of the twentieth century drew the Church’s attention in a definitive way. He writes, “We know that such situations in history have frequently led to a deeper reflection on Christian truth as a whole, as well as on particular aspects of it. That is also the case today. The truth about the human being, in turn, has a distinctly privileged place in this whole process. After nearly twenty years of ideological debate in Poland, it has become clear that at the center of this debate is not cosmology or philosophy of nature but philosophical anthropology and ethics: the great and fundamental controversy about the human being” (Wojtyła, “The Person: Subject and Community,” 220).

his descent from rationality, as a *diseased appendage* of the body politic—a kind of *cancerous limb* to be amputated and cast away.⁸⁴ Aquinas regards this action—the execution of the sinner at the hands of the State—as something praiseworthy.⁸⁵ Indeed, when he argues in favor of the execution of heretics, he provides as a justification of the practice the fact that still lesser offenses, like the forgery of currency (*falsarii pecuniae*), are rightly punished by execution.⁸⁶ That being said, from within a personalist perspective, his argument in favor of capital punishment is stunning indeed. Unlike Augustine, who sees the practice as falling within the objective rights of the State but nevertheless discourages it for the sake of a witness to nobler things,⁸⁷ Aquinas *encourages* capital punishment as long as it can be administered without harm to the innocent.⁸⁸ He writes:

It is lawful to kill dumb animals, insofar as they are naturally directed to man's use, as the imperfect is directed to the perfect. Now every part is directed to the whole, as imperfect to perfect, wherefore every part is naturally for the sake of the whole. For this reason, we observe that if the health of the whole body demands the excision of a member, through its being decayed or infectious to the other members, it will be both praiseworthy and advantageous to have it cut away. Now every individual person is compared to the whole community as part to whole. Therefore, if a man be dangerous and infectious to the community, on account of some sin, it is praiseworthy and advantageous that he be killed in order to safeguard the common good, *since a little leaven corrupteth the whole lump* (1 Cor. v. 6).⁸⁹

⁸⁴ *ST*, II-II, q. 11, a. 3; q. 64, a. 2.

⁸⁵ *Ibid.* II-II, q. 64, a. 2.

⁸⁶ *Ibid.* II-II, q. 11, a. 3. At this point, however, we should note that Aquinas sees this action as a very serious offense against society. In his world, money is a physical commodity tied to limited material resources and backed by the political community (usually in the person of the king), so forging money meant devaluing everyone's currency, which in turn meant not only lying but also stealing, proportionally, from everyone in society, including the poorest of the poor. His example of the forgery of money, here, could easily be substituted with any number of other offenses against society involving the fabrication of documents bearing the authority of the political community in some way, thus eroding the public trust and the integrity of the rule of law. One could imagine any number of examples here, and our own time and forms of government have not lessened the applicability of this concept.

⁸⁷ Augustine, *Letters*, 133, 134.

⁸⁸ *ST*, II-II, q. 64, a. 2, ad 1–2.

⁸⁹ *Ibid.*, II-II, q. 64, a. 2.

It is not so much that what Aquinas says here is wholly *false*, but again, that it is false by way of its *insufficiency*, which belongs to it on account of its *reductionism*, which does not allow space for us to “pause before the irreducible.” John Paul II’s treatment of capital punishment in *Evangelium Vitae* reflects Wojtyła’s concern for the irreducibility of the human person and the application of the personalistic norm. There, his treatment does more than simply *urge* the State to temper justice with mercy; it represents much more than a departure from Aquinas on a question of *emphasis*. Precisely on the basis of the personalistic norm,⁹⁰ John Paul II reconsiders the objective moral character of the public act of execution, and on the basis of that reconsideration, he denies the State moral license to perform it unless doing so is a practical necessity for ensuring the safety of the innocent. Again, while Aquinas argues that capital punishment is to be *favored* even for *lesser* crimes, unless its application poses a mortal danger to the innocent *along* with the guilty, John Paul II takes precisely the *opposite* stance, declaring that, in the contemporary world, the circumstances that would justify its application are “very rare, if not practically non-existent.”⁹¹

⁹⁰ John Paul II clearly references the personalistic norm in his statement about the purpose of punishment immediately preceding his judgment concerning the status of capital punishment in industrialized society in his encyclical letter *Evangelium vitae* (25 March 1995), §56. His line of reasoning is based upon the duty of society to restore the offender to the proper exercise of personal freedom.

⁹¹ John Paul II, *Evangelium vitae*, §56. Following the publication of *Evangelium vitae*, Pope John Paul II ordered a revision of the *Catechism of the Catholic Church* in 1997, the first edition of which had been published in 1994. This revision added the following sentence to §2267, incorporating a quote from *Evangelium vitae*, §56: “Today, in fact, given the means at the State’s disposal to effectively repress crime by rendering inoffensive the one who has committed it, without depriving him definitively of the possibility of redeeming himself, cases of absolute necessity for suppression of the offender ‘today ... are very rare, if not practically nonexistent.’” In a memorandum directed to the bishops of the United States in 2004, intended to address an as-yet unresolved controversy regarding admission to Holy Communion in light of canon 916 of the 1983 *Code of Canon Law*, as it may relate to persons in the public eye who advance grave evil (such as politicians who promote abortion), Joseph Cardinal Ratzinger wrote: “Not all moral issues have the same moral weight as abortion and euthanasia. For example, if a Catholic were to be at odds with the Holy Father on the application of capital punishment or on the decision to wage war, he would not for that reason be considered unworthy to present himself to receive Holy Communion. While the Church exhorts civil authorities to seek peace, not war, and to exercise discretion and mercy in imposing punishment on criminals, it may still be permissible to take up arms to repel an aggressor or to have recourse to capital punishment. There may be a legitimate diversity of opinion even among Catholics about waging war and applying the death penalty, but not however with regard to abortion and euthanasia” (J. Ratzinger, memorandum, *Worthiness to Receive Holy Communion: General Principles* (July 2004), §3). In 2018, however, Pope Francis ordered the complete rewriting of the paragraph to read: “Recourse to the death penalty on the part of legitimate authority, following a fair trial, was long considered an appropriate response to the gravity of certain crimes and an acceptable, albeit extreme, means of safeguarding the common good. [] Today, however, there is an increasing awareness that the dignity of the person is not lost even after the commission of very serious crimes. In addition, a new understanding has emerged of the significance of penal sanctions imposed by the state. Lastly, more effective systems of detention have been developed, which ensure the due protection of citizens but, at the same time, do not definitively deprive the guilty of the possibility of redemption. [] Consequently, the Church teaches, in the light of the Gospel, that ‘the death penalty

Cosmology or The Personalistic Norm?

No matter what other issues may come before us, however, there looms above all a fundamental *theological* question—the question of the ultimate destiny of the human person. For Aquinas, again, the human person is to be understood not as a *for-its-own-sake being*, but as a being for the sake of a higher, *divine* agenda. It is important for us to understand what this means for Aquinas. He does not hold simply that the human being is made by God for the purpose of becoming more than he already is by nature. Rather, Aquinas holds that the human person, *qua* human person, exists to serve a larger *cosmic* goal intended by God, namely the manifestation of the divine glory.⁹² The individual human person is subordinated to this end and finds his real value precisely in this, most of all. For Aquinas, this cosmic purpose is positively *exclusive of*

is inadmissible because it is an attack on the inviolability and dignity of the person' (Francis, *Address to Participants in the Meeting Organized by the Pontifical Council for the Promotion of the New Evangelization*, 11 October 2017: *L'Osservatore Romano*, 13 October 2017, 5), and she works with determination for its abolition worldwide." In his encyclical letter *Fratelli tutti* (3 October 2020), Pope Francis presents an extensive discourse on the death penalty, saying that "Saint John Paul II stated clearly and firmly that the death penalty is inadequate from a moral standpoint and no longer necessary from that of penal justice. There can be no stepping back from this position. Today we state clearly that 'the death penalty is inadmissible' and the Church is firmly committed to calling for its abolition worldwide" (§263). In the declaration on human dignity, *Dignitas infinita* (2 April 2024), the Dicastery for the Doctrine of the Faith describes capital punishment in language that appears to identify capital punishment as *malum in se*, as always and everywhere wrong, saying that it "violates the inalienable dignity of every person, regardless of the circumstances" (§34). In light of these teachings under Francis, a firestorm of controversy has broken out in Catholic academic circles over the question of whether Francis had contradicted the ordinary and universal magisterium, which until now had always left room for the just application of capital punishment, with some popes even describing it as positively good. Without entering into that controversy here, we would point out that even Francis, in *Fratelli tutti*, does not condemn capital punishment as *malum in se*, but instead condemns making recourse to capital punishment when alternative punishments are available to safeguard the public. Indeed, John Paul II and Francis both speak, in their respective encyclicals, from the privileged vantage point of a nation in the contemporary West, in which they find it "impossible to imagine that states today have no other means than capital punishment to protect the lives of other people from the unjust aggressor" (*Fratelli tutti*, §267, quoting from, Pope Francis, *Address to the Delegates of the International Association of Penal Law* [23 October 2014], II.a). Leaving aside the factual question of whether, in fact, it is true that there is, today, no political community on earth in which "no other means than capital punishment [is available] to protect the lives of other people from the unjust aggressor," it is impossible to deny that such political communities have existed in the past and could exist again in the future. Acknowledging these possibilities reveals that recent magisterial condemnation of the application of capital punishment is itself conditioned on circumstance. When the Dicastery for the Doctrine of the Faith declares that capital punishment "violates the inalienable dignity of every person, regardless of the circumstances," we must consider that statement as something less than categorical and deny that it represents a pronouncement against the practice as *malum in se*. Present controversies aside, however, it is possible to see in recent magisterial teaching regarding capital punishment a certain development of approach to the question based on the application of the personalistic norm.

⁹² *ST*, I, q. 23, a. 5, ad 3.

the ultimate good of some—and indeed of the preponderance—of human persons.⁹³ This is a dimension of Aquinas thought that seems, largely, to escape our attention today. We tend either to dismiss it as a tangential, anachronistic appendage of his overall system, or else to ignore it altogether.⁹⁴ But with the advent of the personalistic norm, the question of whether, in the end, Aquinas’s system can stand at all without the *reprobate* would seem to have been forced upon us. However that question is finally to be answered, the role of reprobation in Aquinas’s system is a lucid manifestation of his tendency toward natural reductionism.

Aquinas is quite clear in his affirmation that rational beings exist to provide an audience for the manifestation of God’s glory.⁹⁵ Assembling this audience requires, in particular, the *elect*: those whom God chooses from all eternity to delight in him. In and through the elect, God displays his mercy and generosity,⁹⁶ and of these human creatures only can it be said that they are ends for ends. For, according to Aquinas, in order to reveal the full scope of his mercy, God also requires for the elect a counterexample. Thus, from eternity, God providentially intends the reprobation of the masses.⁹⁷ While he does not want to say that God positively wills sin, Aquinas does explicitly hold that the reprobate are not reprobate because of their sins, but that they sin because they are reprobate, and reprobates must go to hell.⁹⁸ In the end, Aquinas’s view on this question does appear

⁹³ *Ibid.*, I, q. 23, a. 7, ad 3.

⁹⁴ Indeed, in my own work, *Judged by the Law of Freedom*, I had rather consciously bracketed this dimension of Aquinas’s thought under the hypothesis that his metaphysical view actually suggests an alternative path that he, for his own part, could not appreciate on account of a certain poverty of exegesis with respect to the scriptural themes of providence, predestination, perseverance, election, and the Book of Life. I now wonder if the matter really moves the other way—that is, if his exegesis came to be driven by the metaphysical categories to which he had already given his assent. No doubt, Aquinas did not perceive himself as subordinating revelation to metaphysics, especially since his exegetical tendencies on these points were widely embraced by his contemporaries, even across metaphysical lines of disputation. But Wojtyła, too, seems rather critical of Aquinas on this score, even as he expresses his profound admiration for him. Once again, see Wojtyła, “Ethics and Moral Theology,” 101–106. There, he notes, once again, that St. Thomas is engaged in an exercise of interpreting “scripture and tradition in keeping with the magisterium of the Church *by means of a particular philosophical system*” (p. 101), which “appears as an intellectual synthesis that goes far beyond the threshold of exegesis ... [arranging the content of revelation] by means of metaphysical categories” (pp. 102–103). Again, Wojtyła cautions that “The admiration we have for this ‘summa,’ however, does not have to mean—and even should not mean—that we regard it as a work complete and perfect in every respect. The inner bond ... that exists between speculative theology and philosophy directs us today to look at this remarkable work [i.e., Aquinas’s system of speculative theology] as a ‘fruit of its times,’ that is, to view it not only within the framework of the state of philosophy in St. Thomas’ day but also from the perspective of the subsequent development of philosophy” (p. 103). Clearly, for Wojtyła, the inherent limits associated with all attempts, however noble, finally to synthesize the sum of natural knowledge even as we continue to advance in it must leave us cautious, lest we constrain God’s self-revelation within the bounds of what we already understand.

⁹⁵ Cf. *ST*, I, q. 23, a. 5

⁹⁶ *Ibid.*

⁹⁷ *Ibid.*, I, q. 23, a. 7, ad 3.

⁹⁸ *Ibid.*, I, q. 23, a. 3.

to reduce not only to an assertion of the *eternal security of the elect*, but also to a thesis of *double-predestination*.⁹⁹ Accordingly, there exists, for Aquinas, a two-tiered order of human worth. The elect exist for the sake of the manifestation of God's glory in terms of mercy, while the reprobate exist for the sake of the elect; they are *things*, like any other things in the great cosmic collective, not ends in themselves. Aquinas makes this clear:

[God] preordained the measurements of the universe, and what number would befit the essential parts of that universe—that is to say, which have in some way been ordained in perpetuity; how many spheres, how many stars, how many elements, and how many species. Individuals, however, which undergo corruption, are not ordained, as it were, chiefly for the good of the universe, but in a secondary way, inasmuch as the good of the species is preserved in them. Whence, although God knows the total number of individuals, the number of oxen, flies, and such-like, is not preordained by God *per se*; but divine providence produces just so many as are sufficient for the preservation of the species. Now of all creatures the rational creature is chiefly ordained for the good of the universe, being as such incorruptible; but more especially those who attain to eternal happiness, since they more immediately reach the ultimate end. Whence the number of the predestined is certain to God; not only by way of knowledge, but also by way of principle preordination.

It is not exactly the same in the case of the number of the reprobate, who would seem to be preordained by God for the good of the elect.¹⁰⁰

⁹⁹ Aquinas is careful to draw a distinction between *predestination*, on the one hand, and *reprobation*, on the other (*ibid.*, I, q. 23, a. 3). Yet, in his system, both the number of the reprobate and the number of the elect are certain, fixed, and pre-assigned by God from eternity. Strictly speaking, the status of a person as reprobate or elect cannot be changed by his or her choices and actions. Rather, in and through our choices and actions, we merely go on to *realize*, in the course of time, our eternally fixed status. In the case of the *predestined* or the *elect*, this comes by virtue of the aid of grace. In the case of the reprobate, this comes precisely in the *abandonment* of the sinner by God, who withholds from him just that grace without which he will fail in the good. In Jamesian terms, this careful semantic distinction, however well it serves Aquinas's system, represents, in the kerygmatic arena, "a difference that makes no difference." As he puts it in his famous example about whether the man trying to catch a squirrel circling a tree is going around the squirrel or *vice versa*, "If no practical difference whatever can be traced, then the alternatives mean practically the same thing, and all dispute is idle. Whenever a dispute is serious, we ought to be able to show some practical difference that must follow from one side or the other's being right" (W. James, *Pragmatism*, ed. B. Kuklick (Indianapolis: Hackett Publishing Company, 1981), 26). We need not advocate for an unqualified Jamesian pragmatism here to recognize the applicability of his point to the present question. Whether, on a Calvinistic model, God positively predestines a man to hell, or, on a Thomistic model, he is excluded from salvation in God's eternal choosing and thus consigned to hell with a divine foreknowledge that is "the cause of things" (*ST*, I, q. 14, a. 8), makes no practical difference to the reprobate for whom the avoidance of hell was never within God's positive will for him.

¹⁰⁰ *ST*, I, q. 23, a. 7.

As pope, in his encyclical *Dives in misericordia*, however, John Paul II insists that the mystery of election includes “each and every individual,”¹⁰¹ and again, “every man and woman.”¹⁰² The possibility that some may be reprobate he nowhere ascribes to some fundamental orientation of God’s providence or his overall cosmic plan, nor does he even regard it as a certainty of revelation that any concrete historical person is definitively damned.¹⁰³ Rather, Wojtyła clearly holds that the human person is, according to *Gaudium et Spes*, of which, at the Second Vatican Council, he was among the principle authors along with Henri de Lubac, “the only creature on earth that God has willed for its own sake.”¹⁰⁴ Only the most prejudiced reading of *Gaudium et spes* §24 would allow for the qualification of this claim through an *ad hoc* appeal to the reprobate. Indeed, it is precisely on the basis of the *personalistic norm* that such a move becomes immediately recognizable as an *absurdity*—for to *be a person*, for Wojtyła, is to be a *for-its-own-sake* being. If God makes some for the sake of others, to the exclusion of their own ultimate good, it is clear that he makes some who are *not persons* according to Wojtyła’s understanding of the term. In his pre-papal work, *Love and Responsibility*, Wojtyła is explicit on this point, directly contradicting Aquinas’s thesis, based, as it is, upon a naturalistic, cosmological understanding of the human person. Again, he writes:

... we must never treat a person as a means to an end. This principle has a universal validity. Nobody can use a person as a means towards an end, no human being, nor yet God the Creator. On the part of God, indeed, it is totally out of the question, since, by giving man

¹⁰¹ John Paul II, encyclical letter, *Dives in misericordia* (November 30, 1980), §7.

¹⁰² *Ibid.*, §4.

¹⁰³ In his private pastoral work, *Crossing the Threshold of Hope*, John Paul II holds out the theoretical possibility of hell as an inscrutable mystery, but one necessary for the safeguarding, precisely, of human-personal self-determination. He writes, “Can God, who has loved man so much, permit the man who rejects Him to be condemned to eternal torment? And yet the words of Matthew’s Gospel are unequivocal. In Matthew’s Gospel, He speaks clearly to those who will go to eternal punishment (cf. Mt 25:46). Who will these be? The Church has never made any pronouncement in this regard. This is a mystery that embraces the holiness of God and the conscience of man. The silence of the Church is, therefore, the only appropriate position for Christian faith. Even when Jesus says of Judas, the traitor, ‘It would be better for that man if he had never been born’ (Mt 26:24), His words do not allude for certain to eternal damnation.” His Holiness John Paul II, *Crossing the Threshold of Hope*, ed. V. Messori, trans. by J. McPhee, M. McPhee (New York: Alfred A. Knopf, 1994), 185–186.

¹⁰⁴ John Paul II, *Gaudium et spes*, §24.

an intelligent and free nature, he has thereby ordained that each man alone will decide for himself the ends of his activity, and not be a blind tool of someone else's ends.¹⁰⁵

Thus, while we may well affirm precisely that non-persons—"oxen, flies, and such like"—can be treated as mere means to ends, even a cursory "pause before the irreducible" forbids us to say the same of a member of our own species. For he is more than a man; she is more than a woman; she is a *person*—a unique, unrepeatable, for her own sake being. She is, therefore, *irreducible* to some natural, societal, or cosmological purpose; for she is a child of God, chosen for love, and called, above all else, to delight forever in his heavenly embrace. She is made for an interpersonal encounter—the mutual self-donation between the creaturely bride and her heavenly Bridegroom, who formed her as an image of his own heart and loved her into being and life.

Due primarily to the influence of Lublin Thomism and, in particular, Karol Wojtyła in the past, roughly, half-century of Catholic thought (itself largely a consequence of Wojtyła's accession to the papacy as John Paul II on 16 October 1978), it has become common for Catholic intellectuals to speak of "Thomistic personalism." But, just as there are many variants of Thomism, which in various ways find in the thought of Thomas Aquinas a foundation upon which to build, while adapting Thomas's thought in light of new questions and findings, if our reference point for the phrase, "Thomistic personalism" is Thomas himself and "Classical Thomism," it is, in a certain sense, an oxymoron. This is because, to the extent that the term "personalism" requires the affirmation of personal irreducibility and the personalistic norm, as Karol Wojtyła insists, Thomas Aquinas himself is not a personalist, and there is no way to make him one without far-reaching, substantive revision—or, as Wojtyła says, "significant modification."¹⁰⁶ I am not, of course, suggesting that we should not speak of such a thing at all, only that in doing so we should recognize that we have had to make adjustments to the Thomism of St. Thomas himself and the Classical Thomists, according to whom the person is "chiefly ordained for the good of the universe ... more especially those who attain to eternal happiness. ... [while] the reprobate ... [are] preordained by God for the good of the elect. ..."¹⁰⁷ Wojtyła departs decisively from this view, insisting, once again, that "Nobody can use a person as a means towards an end, no human

¹⁰⁵ Wojtyła, *Love and Responsibility*, 27.

¹⁰⁶ Wojtyła, "Ethics and Moral Theology," 103.

¹⁰⁷ Cf., *ST*, I, q. 23, a. 7.

being, nor yet God the Creator.”¹⁰⁸ Nonetheless, if we are willing, as Wojtyła has done, to build upon the foundation Thomas has laid for Catholic thought, grateful for what he has provided while facing the limits of his framework and correcting his errors of omission in light of the genuine insights of contemporary philosophy and theology, it is possible, perhaps, to arrive at a new synthesis.

¹⁰⁸ Wojtyła, *Love and Responsibility*, 27.

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***Divinus in Caro: Karol Wojtyła's Ontological Personalism
Between Theomorphism and Technomorphism***¹

Blaise D. Ringor²

Abstract

Modernity's crisis of human self-understanding has been characterized by two opposed reductions of the person. On one side, a **theomorphic** tendency frames the human being exclusively in relation to the divine, often at the expense of the creature's own integrity and agency. On the other, a **technomorphic** tendency reduces the person to a manipulable object of technology and biology, flattening human existence to measurable functions. This paper argues that Karol Wojtyła's ontological personalism mediates these extremes through a deeper retrieval of the person as *divinus in caro*—the divine image manifested in flesh. Wojtyła's philosophy of the acting person, centered on efficacy, self-determination, and transcendence of the person in act, both affirms the human orientation to God (thus correcting technocratic reductionism) and insists on the creaturely reality and freedom of the person (thereby correcting one-sided theocentrism). In four parts, the argument unfolds the anthropological dilemmas of theomorphism and technomorphism and shows how Wojtyła's integration of classical metaphysics with phenomenology preserves the irreducible uniqueness and dignity of the human person, offering a philosophical defense of the person as both subject and end of moral action.

Keywords

personalism, theomorphism, technocracy, self-determination, efficacy, human dignity

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Introduction: *The Anthropological Dilemma of Modernity*

In the late modern age, the human being finds itself pulled between two opposing visions of what it means to be a person. One vision, born of an earlier religious epoch, sees the human chiefly as an image of God—*imago Dei*—defined by a relation of creaturely dependence and resemblance to the divine. Another vision, emerging from the secular scientific revolution, regards the human in purely naturalistic or technical terms—as an *object* within the empirical world, to be understood by the same methods that apply to animals or machines. These two visions, **theomorphic** and **technomorphic**, stand as extreme responses to the fragmentation of the once-unified Christian anthropology. Each contains a partial truth about the human person, yet each, when taken as complete in itself, imposes a profound reduction. The result is an anthropological dilemma: either define man so exclusively by a divine prototype that his own worldly reality and freedom are obscured, or define man so exclusively by technological and biological categories that his transcendent depth and irreducible dignity vanish.

This crisis did not emerge overnight but developed through the upheavals of modern intellectual history. The Enlightenment’s exaltation of reason and empirical science gradually displaced the pre-modern view of man as a creature “willed for his own sake”³ by a Creator (to use the famous phrase from *Gaudium et Spes*). In the wake of the Enlightenment, some thinkers responded by doubling down on the divine paradigm—seeking to re-ground human meaning in God alone—while others embraced an ever-purer secularism, treating the human being as nothing more than a clever animal or a biochemical machine. By the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, the tension had become acute. On the one hand, *theomorphic* tendencies appeared in philosophies that defined moral value solely by reference to God or the “holy,” risking a neglect of human rationality and freedom. On the other hand, *technomorphic* tendencies took hold in ideologies that trumpeted the “death of God” and placed all faith in scientific progress or social engineering, often reducing persons to cogs in vast technological or economic systems. As John F. Crosby observes, personalist philosophers of the last century were united in opposing **both** these extremes: they resisted “turning persons into autonomous selves detached from all bonds of solidarity” (the individualistic trajectory of technocratic liberalism) **and** resisted “the opposite error of

³ Second Vatican Council, *Gaudium et Spes* (Pastoral Constitution on the Church in the Modern World, 1965), §24.

absorbing the individual person into the social whole”⁴ or into any overarching absolute that negates individuality. The drama of the person in modernity has thus been a struggle to assert a fuller understanding of human dignity against oversimplifications that would either subsume the person into divinity or dissolve the person into material nature.

It is precisely in this context that Karol Wojtyła—better known as Pope John Paul II—developed his **ontological personalism** as a response to the anthropological crisis. Wojtyła entered the philosophical scene as both a disciple of **classical metaphysics**⁵ and an innovator who employed **phenomenology** to deepen our grasp of lived human experience. In his work *Person and Act* (also translated as *The Acting Person*), Wojtyła set out to secure the insight that the human being is *irreducible*—not exhaustively definable by any lower principle or external archetype. He insisted on the **integrity of the person** as a being at once corporeal and spiritual, anchored in concrete action and experience, yet open to what transcends empirical determinism. This insistence can be seen as a mediated solution to the modern dilemma. Rather than a half-measure or compromise, Wojtyła offers a **dialectical retrieval**: he reaches back behind the false dichotomy to an ontology of the person in which the truths of both sides—the transcendent orientation of the person to the divine, and the concrete reality of the person as an active subject in the world—find their harmonious integration.

In what follows, we unfold this argument in four stages. **First**, we examine the *theomorphic reduction* of the human being, understanding both its motivation and its pitfalls. **Next**, we turn to

⁴ J.F. Crosby, “Preface to *Personalist Papers*,” in: J.F. Crosby, *Personalist Papers* (Washington, D.C.: Catholic University of America Press, 2004), x.

⁵ John Paul II defends the preservation of the *sapiential dimension* of philosophy which can be found in a genuine metaphysical range that prevents swinging to any extremes. He says: “the need for a philosophy of *genuinely metaphysical* range, capable, that is, of transcending empirical data in order to attain something absolute, ultimate and foundational in its search for truth. This requirement is implicit in sapiential and analytical knowledge alike; in particular, it is a requirement for knowing the moral good, which has its ultimate foundation in the Supreme Good—God himself. Here I do not mean to speak of metaphysics in the sense of a specific school or a particular historical current of thought. I want only to state that reality and truth do transcend the factual and the empirical, and to vindicate the human being’s capacity to know this transcendent and metaphysical dimension in a way that is true and certain, albeit imperfect and analogical. In this sense, metaphysics should not be seen as an alternative to anthropology, since it is metaphysics which makes it possible to ground the concept of personal dignity in virtue of their spiritual nature. In a special way, the person constitutes a privileged locus for the encounter with being, and hence with metaphysical enquiry. Wherever men and women discover a call to the absolute and transcendent, the metaphysical dimension of reality opens up before them: in truth, in beauty, in moral values, in other persons, in being itself, in God. We face a great challenge at the end of this millennium to move from *phenomenon* to *foundation*, a step as necessary as it is urgent. We cannot stop short at experience alone; even if experience does reveal the human being’s interiority and spirituality, speculative thinking must penetrate to the spiritual core and the ground from which it rises. Therefore, a philosophy which shuns metaphysics would be radically unsuited to the task of mediation in the understanding of Revelation.” John Paul II, *Fides et Ratio* (1998), §83.

the opposite, *technomorphic reduction*, which currently exerts enormous cultural influence through the proliferation of science and technology. Having seen how each one-sidedly distorts the truth of the person, we then explore Wojtyła’s personalist ontology as a **third**, deeper path that both negates and fulfills the extremes. **Finally**, we conclude by showing how this ontological personalism preserves the irreducible mystery and worth of the person, mediating between theomorphism and technomorphism on a more profound ontological ground. Throughout, we draw on Wojtyła’s own philosophical and magisterial writings, as well as the insights of contemporary commentators and critics of modernity, to substantiate each step of the argument. The aim is to demonstrate that only by retrieving the full truth of *divinus in caro*—the divine image in the fleshly, acting person—can we resolve the anthropological paradoxes of our time.

Theomorphism: False Deification

The first extreme to consider is what may be called **theomorphic anthropology**—an understanding of the human being primarily in terms of a resemblance to God. In this view, the defining mark of the person is that he or she bears a divine image or is related to a divine reality; apart from that relation, the meaning of “human” collapses. Such an approach has deep roots in Western thought: one thinks of the biblical idea of *imago Dei*, or the Platonic–Augustinian notion that the soul finds its true self only in God. Properly understood, the idea that the human being is *theomorphic* (God-shaped) is a radical affirmation of human dignity. It declares that what is highest in us is not reducible to any worldly element—our worth comes from a transcendent source. Wojtyła himself, as a Catholic thinker, fully embraces the truth that the human person is created in God’s image and called to communion with Him. The problem arises, however, when this truth is **isolated and absolutized** in a one-sided way. The *theomorphic* view can become reductive if it neglects the integrity of human nature and reason, collapsing the human into the divine in a manner that bypasses the person’s own act and experience. In its distorted form, theomorphism can lead to a kind of *fideism*—an excessive emphasis on faith or divine authority that undermines the proper role of reason and human agency. Wojtyła himself warned against this error. In his encyclical *Fides et Ratio*, John Paul II identified **fideism** as a tendency that “fails to recognize the importance of rational knowledge and philosophical discourse for understanding

faith,”⁶ and thus ultimately **undermines the truth about the human person** by severing it from reason’s insights.⁷ A theomorphic anthropology, if it lapses into fideism, risks portraying the person as a *passive receptor of divine attributes* rather than an *active, efficacious individual subject* (i.e., *Suppositum*).

A concrete example of the theomorphic reduction can be found in the ethical personalism of Max Scheler—ironically, a thinker whom Wojtyła both admired and later critically engaged. Scheler spoke of man as *the “theomorphic” being*, defining the human being by his unique orientation toward God as the highest value. In Scheler’s analysis, the human person is the only earthly being who can grasp “spiritual values,” especially the value of “the holy,” and thereby man is distinguished as God-related.⁸ Scheler thus rooted human dignity in the **experience of the divine**: “Only under the light of the idea of God does man constitute the highest of the earthly beings ... It is thanks to it that man is for Scheler a theo-morphic being.”⁹ On the face of it, this seems to echo the classic *imago Dei* doctrine, yet Wojtyła discerned a critical flaw in Scheler’s formulation. For Scheler, the divine to which man relates remains merely an “idea of God,” a value

⁶ *Ibid.*, §55. The Pope also criticizes fideism for undervaluing reason: “Against the temptations of fideism, however, it was necessary to stress the unity of truth and thus the positive contribution which rational knowledge can and must make to faith’s knowledge. Even if faith is superior to reason there can never be a true divergence between faith and reason, since the same God who reveals the mysteries and bestows the gift of faith has also placed in the human spirit the light of reason. This God could not deny himself, nor could the truth ever contradict the truth.” *Ibid.*, §55. John Paul II warns that a proper Christian anthropology requires the harmonious collaboration of faith and reason, without which the human person is not fully understood.

⁷ Fideism, in its refusal to recognize the autonomy and validity of philosophical reason, is castigated within the framework of *Fides et Ratio* as a betrayal of both theology and philosophy. The rejection of reason as a legitimate partner in the pursuit of truth results in an impoverished faith, one that is reduced to mere subjectivity or sentimentality. Such a stance ultimately undermines the Catholic intellectual tradition, which has historically insisted on the harmony of faith and reason. Joseph Koterski emphasizes that fideism is not merely a theological error but a philosophical abdication, one that contributes to the broader collapse of metaphysical confidence in the postmodern academy, where “reason finds itself in need of some defense.” J.W. Koterski, “The Challenge To Metaphysics In *Fides et ratio*,” in: *The Two Wings of Catholic Thought: Essays on Fides et Ratio*, eds. D.R. Foster, J.W. Koterski (Washington, D.C.: Catholic University of America Press, 2003), 22. The fideist’s dismissal of rational inquiry mirrors the postmodern suspicion toward truth itself, thereby capitulating to the very nihilism it ought to resist. It is precisely this retreat from metaphysics that renders fideism not only an error but a symptom of the deeper cultural malady—a surrender to what the text calls the “abyss,” where meaning is dimmed and the soul is left to stumble “without knowing where they are going.” *Ibid.*, 23.

⁸ K. Wojtyła, *The Lublin Lectures and Works on Max Scheler*, “The English Critical Edition of the Works of Karol Wojtyła/John Paul II,” vol. 2, ed. A. Lopez, trans. by G. Ignatik (Washington, D.C.: Catholic University of America Press, 2023), 473.

⁹ K. Wojtyła, “An Assessment of the Possibility of Constructing a Christian Ethics on the Basis of the System of Max Scheler,” in: K. Wojtyła, *The Lublin Lectures and Works on Max Scheler*, 471–472. Here Wojtyła analyzes Scheler’s concept of the human person as *theomorphic*. He explains that for Scheler, man is “theo-morphic” only through the *Erlebnis* (lived experience) of the idea of God, founded on the value of the holy, rather than through any real ontological relation to the Creator. Wojtyła finds this inadequate for a Christian ethics, which demands a real relationship with the living God and a full acknowledgment of human freedom in response to God.

posited in the intentional feeling of the subject.¹⁰ The human person's theomorphic character, in this view, does not depend on a real, existing God who creates and calls the person; it depends only on the *experience of value*. As Wojtyła notes, Scheler "is not concerned with the real relation to God as to an existing, positively defined Reality. His point is only the lived-experience of the idea of God."¹¹ In other words, the human being is defined as the God-analogous animal solely by virtue of having a certain kind of religious consciousness. This move—which might be termed an *idealized theomorphism*—effectively sidelines the ontological reality of both God and man. It makes man's dignity rest on a subjective disposition (feeling the absolute value of the holy) rather than on the **being** of the person as such.

Wojtyła regarded this as insufficient, and indeed dangerous. In *Person and Act*, as well as in his earlier analyses of Scheler's ethics found in his habilitation thesis, *The Lublin Lectures and Works on Max Scheler*, Wojtyła argued that Scheler's approach, for all its appreciation of the spiritual dimension, failed to do justice to the **full truth of the person**. By prioritizing emotional intuition of value over the factual reality of human freedom, Scheler inadvertently diminished the role of the **human will and intellect** in moral life. The person became, in Scheler's phenomenology, a conduit for values rather than a self-determining agent. Wojtyła saw here an anthropological reduction akin to a subtle fideism: the person's lived experience of values (analogous to a kind of secular "faith") was allowed to override the structure of human action and reason. In effect, man was being **defined from "above"** by reference to God or the absolute, in a way that did not sufficiently account for man's own dynamism¹² "from within."¹³ This is precisely the pattern of theomorphic reduction we are concerned with. It acknowledges something true—that the human person transcends the merely material by relation to the divine—but it skews the balance by ignoring the autonomous participation of the person in that relation.

¹⁰ Wojtyła, *The Lublin Lectures and Works on Max Scheler*, 481.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, 474

¹² Wojtyła explains that this term is "... connected to the Greek *dýnamis*, having both Platonic and Aristotelian genealogy; from there it was passed on to medieval philosophy (*potentia*). In modern philosophy, dynamism (Leibniz) is opposed to mechanism (Descartes). 'Dynamics,' which we most often understand—also in the context of this study—as the opposite of statics, is very closely linked to dynamism." W. Wojtyła, "Person and Act," in: K. Wojtyła, *Person and Act and Related Essays*, "The English Critical Edition of the Works of Karol Wojtyła/John Paul II," vol. 1, ed. A. Lopez, trans. by G. Ignatik (Washington, D.C.: Catholic University of America Press, 2021), 161n1.

¹³ Blaise Pascal warns us against the same danger. He says: "If we submit everything to reason our religion will be left with nothing mysterious or supernatural. If we offend the principles of reason our religion will be absurd and ridiculous." B. Pascal, *Pensées*, trans. by H. Levi (New York: Oxford University Press, 1995), §204.

The dangers of theomorphic reduction can manifest in various cultural forms. In religious contexts, it can appear as an overly theocentric human image that verges on suppressing human freedom and responsibility. One thinks of strains of thought in which human morality is conceived in purely extrinsic terms (“because God said so”) without understanding the person’s inner participation in the good. Carried to an extreme, theomorphism shades into a kind of religious **authoritarianism or quietism**, where the human is expected to efface himself entirely before God. Such an outlook, if uncorrected, paradoxically undermines the very dignity it seeks to protect—the person’s value is affirmed, but only as a sort of shadow of God, not as a true agent. This is at odds with the Christian understanding that grace builds on nature—that the divine image in man elevates rather than nullifies his created faculties of intellect and will. Wojtyła, especially in his magisterial teaching, took great pains to combat *false oppositions* between God and man. He emphasized that recognizing man’s relation to God should never mean the denial of human reason or freedom—rather, the light of faith **elevates** reason and the fulfillment of divine communion **perfects** human freedom; it does not abolish them.¹⁴

Thus, Wojtyła’s critique of the theomorphic reduction was fundamentally an effort to restore **wholeness**. The person cannot be defined solely by an abstract reference to God; the person must be understood in the concrete reality of personal being and action, even as we acknowledge the Godward dimension of that being. In place of a one-sided theomorphism, Wojtyła proposes what we might call an **integral theonomy**: the human person is indeed ordained to divine communion and bears God’s image, but this truth unfolds *through* the person’s own rational, free, embodied existence—rather than negating it. As the Second Vatican Council taught: “Man, who is the only creature on earth which God willed for itself, cannot fully find himself except through a sincere gift of self.” Wojtyła loved to quote this line, seeing in it a synthesis of the vertical and horizontal dimensions of personhood. Man is “willed for himself” by God—a direct refutation of any collectivist or purely instrumental view of human nature, yet man finds his fulfillment in

¹⁴ John Paul II, *Fides et Ratio*, §§48–50. John Paul recounts how the modern split between faith and reason led to opposite excesses—rationalism and fideism—and he proposes a recovery of their intrinsic unity. He often used circular or spiral imagery: “Faith and reason are like two wings on which the human spirit rises to the contemplation of truth.” In §§50-55, he specifically addresses fideism, to paraphrase, John Paul II contends that: “With the rise of the empirical sciences, some began to think that what is real is only what can be experimentally verified. In reaction, others pushed reason aside, making faith the only path to truth. This caused a separation harmful to the understanding of man. ... A mentality has developed that separates the realm of faith from the realm of reason. But truth is one. The unity of the human person demands a unified approach.” This teaching undergirds John Paul II’s approach of integrating the divine and the rational dimensions in anthropology.

making a **gift of self**—a refutation of any isolated, static theomorphism that would treat man as a mere receptacle of divinity. The self-gift implies an active, free, and relational character of human fulfillment. We will return to this idea later, for it is pivotal in Wojtyła’s resolution of the extremes.

In summary, the theomorphic reduction, when it forgets the human subject, leads to an anthropology of extrinsic dependence that can slide into fideism¹⁵ or a depreciation of reason. It upholds the truth that the **person is oriented beyond himself** to the absolute, but it misconstrues that truth by effectively absorbing the human into the divine or into an idea of the divine. Wojtyła’s philosophy agrees that the human person has a transcendent reference (indeed, this will be crucial to his own account), but it insists that this reference must be grounded in the **ontological structure of the person**—in the person’s own act of existing and self-determination. Only in that way can we safeguard what is irreducibly human while honoring what is divine. The full response to theomorphism’s shortcomings, however, will become clear only after we have examined the opposite error. For it is often in reaction to an exaggerated theocentrism that modern thought swings to the other extreme: the **technomorphic** vision of man as a purely worldly mechanism. Wojtyła’s genius lies in understanding the interplay between these errors and retrieving a stance that refutes one not by espousing the other but by going deeper than both.

¹⁵ More than *fideism*, another manifestation of this is what Christian Smith calls Moralistic Therapeutic Deism. He characterizes it as follows: First, “Moralistic Therapeutic Deism is about inculcating a moralistic approach to life. It believes that central to living a good and happy life is being a good, moral person. That means being nice, kind, pleasant, respectful, and responsible; working on self-improvement; taking care of one’s health; and doing one’s best to be successful.” Second, “This is not a religion of repentance from sin, of keeping the Sabbath, of living as a servant of a sovereign divine, of steadfastly saying one’s prayers, of faithfully observing high holy days, of building character through suffering, of basking in God’s love and grace, of spending oneself in gratitude and love for the cause of social justice, etc. Rather, what appears to be the actual dominant religion among ... teenagers is centrally about feeling good, happy, secure, at peace. It is about attaining subjective well-being, being able to resolve problems, and getting along amiably with other people.” Third, Moralistic Therapeutic Deism “is about belief in a particular kind of God, one who exists, created the world, and defines our general moral order, but not one who is particularly personally involved in our affairs—especially affairs in which we would prefer not to have God involved. Most of the time, the God of this faith keeps a safe distance. He is often described by teens as ‘watching over everything from above’ and ‘the creator of everything and is just up there now controlling everything.’” See Ch. Smith, “On ‘Moralistic Therapeutic Deism’ as U.S. Teenagers’ Actual, Tacit, De Facto Religious Faith,” in: *Soul Searching: The Religious and Spiritual Lives of American Teenagers* (Oxford University Press, 2005), 118–172.

Technomorphism: The Cosmological Reduction of Man to Machine and Matter

If theomorphic anthropology places man *too high*—subsuming him under the divine without remainder—**technomorphic anthropology** does the opposite: it collapses man *downward*, defining him by sub-personal categories drawn from technology, biology, or animal behavior. Here, the human being is understood fundamentally as an object among objects, a clever primate or an algorithmic organism whose distinctive personal traits (mind, freedom, moral selfhood) are regarded as incidental or illusory. The rise of technomorphic thinking is intertwined with the ascendant power of modern science and technology. As scientific naturalism extended its explanatory domain, the ancient notion of man as *imago Dei* gave way to man as *imago naturae*—an image of nature, a product of blind evolutionary forces, differing in degree but not in kind from other animals. In parallel, the success of technology in controlling nature fueled a vision of the human as chiefly a *technician* or *machine-maker*, even a kind of machine himself. **Augusto Del Noce** diagnosed this trajectory as a result of what he called: “the eclipse of the sacred.” In modernity, he argued, this eclipse led to a civilization in which “every human activity ... [came] to be viewed from the standpoint of the competition man versus nature.”¹⁶ With no “invisible principle” like a soul or divine spark recognized in man, **every value was narrowed to the value of material well-being**, and even religion was tacitly reinterpreted as merely a means of vital enhancement.¹⁷ In such a worldview, the transcendent dimension is not merely ignored; it is actively denied. Man is not the steward of creation under God’s ordinance, but rather a self-interested being engaged in a zero-sum struggle with nature, seeking dominance through technique.

By the mid-20th century, this technomorphic perspective crystallized into what some have called the “**technocratic paradigm**.” The person came to be seen as a bundle of quantifiable processes: chemical interactions in the brain, drives inherited from our animal past, socio—

¹⁶ A. Del Noce, *The Age of Secularization*, trans. by C. Lancellotti (Montreal: McGill-Queen’s University Press, 2017), 163–168. Del Noce examines how technological society emerged from the “eclipse of the sacred.”

¹⁷ Del Noce also writes: “it was not technological progress per se that generated this type of civilization, but the eclipse of the sacred ... The only remaining value will be the increment of perceptible life; in short, well-being, and every human activity, and religion itself, will be viewed as a vitalizing tool.” (Del Noce, *The Age of Secularization*, 167.) He notes that this view of man is diametrically opposed to the one presupposed by Christianity and classical philosophy, which saw man as carrying an invisible divine principle. Thus, secular technocracy redefines man in purely immanent terms.

economic behaviors predictable through statistics, and so on. The unique *subjectivity* of the person—that interior space of consciousness and freedom—was either bracketed out as irrelevant or explained away in impersonal terms. The logical extreme of this tendency is evident in certain currents of contemporary thought and popular science. Historian Yuval Noah Harari, for instance, prophesies a future in which **Homo sapiens** is surpassed by its own technological creations, possibly even to the point of human extinction or obsolescence. In his provocative work *Nexus*, Harari argues that modern science increasingly understands organisms (including humans) as nothing more than **biochemical algorithms**, and that advanced algorithms (AI) may soon outstrip human intelligence.¹⁸ He warns that if humanity unthinkingly embraces a new faith in data and technology—what he terms “*Dataism*”—we might surrender our autonomy and dissolve “within the torrent of information ... like a clump of earth within a gushing river.”¹⁹ This graphic image of dissolution is the technomorphic nightmare: the human being reduced to a nugatory blip in the cosmic data-flow, no longer a sovereign subject but at best a *resource* or *information processor*. The very title *Homo Deus* (“Man-God”) is ironic, for it suggests that by the pursuit of godlike technological power, man may end up annihilating the qualities that made him human in the first place.²⁰

Yet one need not delve into speculative futurism to see the effects of technomorphism; they are apparent in everyday attitudes and institutions. Physician and writer Atul Gawande has candidly described how contemporary medicine, with all its miraculous technology, can fail to truly **care for the person**. In treating aging and dying as purely technical problems to be managed, modern medicine often subjects individuals to dehumanizing routines and interventions that ignore their subjective needs and dignity. Gawande observes that “we have allowed our fates to be controlled by the imperatives of medicine, technology, and strangers,” especially in the last stage

¹⁸ Y.N. Harari, *Nexus: A Brief History of Information Networks From Stone Age to AI* (New York: Random House, 2024). Harari argues that modern science has eroded the traditional humanist notion of free-willed individuals. He suggests that once AI and bioengineering advance sufficiently, humans may either merge with technology or be superseded by it. Though Harari’s tone is often speculative, his work exemplifies the *technomorphic* outlook in which human consciousness is seen as a hackable data-processing system rather than a soul or metaphysically unique entity.

¹⁹ Y.N. Harari, “Weaponizing Information,” in: *Nexus*, 19.

²⁰ In reflecting on *Homo Deus* a few years after its publication, Harari summarizes: “That book argued that the real hero of history has always been information, rather than *Homo sapiens* ... and that while we hope better information technology will give us health, happiness, and power, it may actually take power away from us ... *Homo Deus* hypothesized that if humans aren’t careful, we might dissolve within the torrent of information like a clump of earth within a gushing river.” Harari, “Weaponizing Information,” 19. This colorful metaphor captures the concern that human agency and identity could be lost in the tidal wave of big data and AI decision-making.

of life, leading to “callousness, inhumanity, and extraordinary suffering.”²¹ In a technomorphic healthcare system, the person is tacitly viewed as a biomechanical problem to be solved; the subtle aspirations of the soul—for meaning, for relational closure, for spiritual peace—are outside the purview of treatment. The result, as Gawande notes, is that “the waning days of our lives are given over to treatments that addle our brains and sap our bodies for a sliver’s chance of benefit. They are spent in institutions ... where regimented, anonymous routines cut us off from all the things that matter to us in life.”²² This poignant testimony illustrates how an exclusive focus on technical efficacy (prolonging life, managing organs) can **betray the person**, leaving their deeper good unaddressed. Lacking “a coherent view of how people might live successfully all the way to their very end,” technological society often sacrifices personal well-being to its own inexorable logic of control and efficiency.²³ The human becomes, in a sense, a prisoner of technology’s triumphs—a being whose life is orchestrated by machines and procedures, rather than by personal meaning and choice.

Philosophically, technomorphism is underwritten by **scientism**: the belief that only the empirico-mathematical sciences yield true knowledge, and thus that man must be understood in the same reductive terms those sciences employ. Michael Hanby incisively critiques this outlook. Modern science, Hanby notes, often operates with an ontology that gives “analysis ... priority over synthesis,” which reduces wholes to parts, and conflates **historical causality** with **ontological identity**.²⁴ In biology, for example, life is sometimes defined entirely by the evolutionary history of organisms and their genetic code, as if there were no formal or spiritual principles at work. Hanby points out that such reductionism “reduces ontological identity to causal history and systemic function.”²⁵ Consequently, when this approach turns to the human person, it tends to explain personhood *away* by reference to evolutionary advantage or neurochemical events. However, Hanby argues that this reduction is **self-defeating**: every time we state a truth about

²¹ A. Gawande, *Being Mortal: Medicine and What Matters in the End* (New York: Metropolitan Books, 2014), 18–19. Gawande notes: “Lacking a coherent view of how people might live successfully all the way to their very end, we have allowed our fates to be controlled by the imperatives of medicine, technology, and strangers.” *Ibid.*, 19. He calls for a reintegration of personal well-being and meaning into how we handle aging and dying, implying an anthropological shift away from pure technicism toward personalism in medicine.

²² *Ibid.*, 8–9. This critique highlights the depersonalization that can occur in a hyper-technologized approach to care.

²³ *Ibid.*, 9, 15–16. He discusses how lacking a coherent view of a good life to the end, society inflicts harms in pursuit of safety or mere survival. These passages convey the human cost of a technomorphic mindset in healthcare: people’s qualitative needs and personal preferences are trumped by procedural efficiency and risk avoidance.

²⁴ M. Hanby, *No God, No Science? Theology, Cosmology, Biology* (Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell, 2013), 116.

²⁵ *Ibid.*, 348.

reality (even in the hard sciences), we implicitly invoke forms and meanings that cannot themselves be explained in purely material terms.²⁶ The very act of making an intelligible statement assumes a rational order that transcends brute factual occurrence. Thus, the scientific erasure of formal and spiritual causes cannot account for the intelligibility of the world—including the world of the knowing, willing subject. In a provocative turn, Hanby suggests reversing the modern ontological priority: instead of treating primitive physical processes as the paradigm for understanding life and being, we should treat the **person**—“the incommunicable existence of a rational nature”—as paradigmatic.²⁷ By doing so, we recognize that what is highest (personal existence) sheds light on what is lower, rather than attempting to derive the higher from the lower at the cost of meaning. This aligns perfectly with Wojtyła’s own approach, which as we will see bases its metaphysics in the irreducible experience of personal being.

Returning to the cultural manifestations of technomorphism, we find they oscillate between **two poles**: on the one hand, an individualistic ethos that treats each person as an isolated unit of consumption and production—an “**autonomous self**” defined by preferences, to be satisfied by technical means; on the other, a collectivist or systemic ethos that subordinates persons to the mechanisms of society or state (the person as a statistic, a worker, a replaceable part of the whole). These two might seem contrary, but as Del Noce observed, they can coincide within the same secular-technocratic worldview. With the loss of any higher truth, “the only remaining value will be the increment of perceptible life; in short, well-being,”²⁸ and all institutions and norms bend to that end. The “society of well-being” then treats truth itself as merely an instrument for life: what is true is what works for material prosperity.²⁹ Under such conditions, whether one emphasizes individual choice or collective efficiency, the **transcendent horizon** is gone. Man does not answer to God or to objective moral truth, but only to his own impulses and systems—which soon acquire a tyrannical momentum. It is no surprise that where technocratic materialism has reigned, it has led to dystopian outcomes: the trivialization of human birth and death, the specter of eugenics, the manipulation of human psychology for profit, and the degradation of the natural environment. Harari’s imagined future of intelligent algorithms

²⁶ *Ibid.*, 349.

²⁷ *Ibid.*, 314-316, 348.

²⁸ Del Noce, *The Age of Secularization*, 167.

²⁹ *Ibid.*, 167–168. Del Noce explains the “society of well-being”: “*Benessere* in the original, which in Italian has a more specific meaning than the English ‘well-being,’ since it refers strictly to material and psycho-physical well-being.” (*Ibid.*, 217n.1.)

deciding our fates is but a continuation of a long trend: the displacement of the human person from the center of concern.

We can thus summarize the technomorphic reduction as follows: it **denies the vertical dimension** of the person (any openness to the transcendent) and flattens the **horizontal dimension** into impersonal processes. Man is either a god unto himself (in rhetoric) or a machine made of meat (in practice)—in both cases, not truly *someone*, only *something*. The ultimate paradox is that technomorphism often promises a kind of secular exaltation of man (through science we shall conquer all ills, perhaps even achieve immortality or “Homo Deus”), but in reality, it delivers a diminished humanity. This was foreseen by thinkers like Nietzsche, who declared the death of God so that the “Superman” could arise—but as history shows, the death of the divine image in man often eventuates in the sub-human creeping in. As one commentator put it, when man eliminates God in the name of self-elevation, “now it is our will that the Superman shall live”³⁰—yet that will to power eventually consumes its own creators, leaving not a god-man but a hollow man.³¹ We end up, to paraphrase C.S. Lewis, “abolishing man” in the pursuit of mastering nature.³²

Against this bleak backdrop, Karol Wojtyła’s personalism stands as a radiant alternative. He saw clearly that neither a retreat into unreasoning fideism nor an embrace of soulless scientism could safeguard the full truth of the person. The human being demands an account that does justice to **both** the earthy reality of our existence and the heavenly calling of our nature. Any anthropology missing either of these poles will collapse into reductionism. Thus, if the preceding sections have delineated the *Scylla and Charybdis* of contemporary thought, the next section seeks the navigational path between—or rather, **above**—them. That path is Wojtyła’s **ontology of the person**, which can be viewed as a synthesis that transcends the thesis of theomorphism and the antithesis of technomorphism. It is to this positive vision that we now turn.

³⁰ However, as twentieth-century history shows, attempts to create “Supermen” via ideology or science often resulted in great dehumanization. Wojtyła was keenly aware of this history (living through both Nazi and Communist regimes) and it reinforced his conviction that only a view which upholds an objective moral order (ultimately grounded in God) truly protects human dignity.

³¹ F. Nietzsche, *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*, Part IV (“The Song of Melancholy”), and *Beyond Good and Evil*, §126. Nietzsche famously has Zarathustra proclaim, “God is dead; now we want the Superman to live.” (cf. H. de Lubac, *The Drama of Atheist Humanism*, trans. by E. Riley, (San Francisco: Ignatius, 1995), 57–59). The idea is that by killing the idea of God, man might elevate himself to a godlike stature. Paul van Tongeren, in *Reinterpreting Modern Culture: An Introduction to Nietzsche’s Philosophy* (West Lafayette: Purdue UP, 2000), explains how Nietzsche’s vision sought a transvaluation of all values with man’s will to power at the center.

³² See C.S. Lewis, *The Abolition of Man* (New York: HarperCollins Publishers, 2015).

Wojtyła's Ontological Personalism

Wojtyła's project can be aptly described as a *retrieval of the full reality of the person* at a metaphysical depth that undercuts the false dichotomy of the extremes. Rather than propose a superficial compromise between the sacred and the secular visions of man, Wojtyła returns to fundamental experiences and classical insights to rebuild an anthropology on solid first principles. His method is notably **integrative**: he brings together the objective perspective of Thomistic metaphysics (with its emphasis on *being, form, teleology*, etc.) and the subjective perspective of phenomenology (with its emphasis on *conscious experience, intentionality*, and the *interior life* of the subject). In doing so, he constructs a vision of the human person as an irreducible **someone**—an integral union of body and soul, an acting subject who realizes himself in moral freedom and in relation to truth, goodness, and ultimately, God. This personalism is **ontological** in that it is grounded in the very being of the person (not merely in social or psychological claims), and it is personalism precisely because it takes the *person* (not subpersonal elements) as the primary analogue for understanding reality.

A key move Wojtyła makes is to distinguish between what he calls the “**cosmological**” and the “**personalistic**” understanding of the human being. The cosmological approach (characteristic of classical antiquity—mainly Aristotle—and of medieval philosophy—mainly St. Thomas Aquinas) situates man within the larger order of being: man is a *rational animal*,³³ a substance composed of matter and form, classified by genus and species. This approach yields the enduring definition of personhood from Boethius: *persona est naturae rationalis individua substantia*—an individual substance of a rational nature. Wojtyła has great respect for this definition; he sees it as fundamentally true. However, he also recognizes that by itself, it remains somewhat abstract and does not yet illuminate the **inner life** of the person. The personalistic

³³ D.C. Schindler correctly explains this attribution to Aristotle of *man as a rational animal*. Schindler points out that: “Because of the fundamental distinction between human thought and human action, and so between *theoretical* science and *practical* science, we ultimately have two master, or ‘architectonic,’ sciences, one for each order. The architectonic theoretical science is metaphysics and the architectonic practical science is politics. It is worth noting that this basic division in the sciences corresponds to the two classical definitions of man, which stem from Aristotle: man is the *rational* (i.e., ‘metaphysical’) animal, and man is the *political* animal.” He continues in a footnote: “It is worth noting that Aristotle does not explicitly use the expression ‘rational animal,’ but it is clearly implied as the point of this chapter in the *Ethics* and has been attributed to Aristotle no doubt by analogy to his expression ‘*zoon politikon*’.” D.C. Schindler, *God and the City* (Indiana, U.S.A.: St. Augustine’s Press, 2023), 23—24. [original emphases]

approach, by contrast, starts from the lived experience of being a self and an agent. It asks: *What is it like to be a person? How do we experience ourselves as different from objects?* Here Wojtyła introduces concepts like **self-governance**,³⁴ **self-possession**,³⁵ and **self-determination**,³⁶ which emerged from his phenomenological analysis of action and consciousness. In experience, the human person finds that he is not a thing moved by external forces alone; he has an **inner center of causality**. I do not merely undergo events; *I act*. This sense of “*I act*”—Wojtyła calls it the moment of **efficacy**—reveals that I am the efficient cause of my own free deeds.³⁷ And in causing my actions, I also, in some sense, cause *myself*: I shape myself morally, I become virtuous or vicious, I fulfill or deform my potential. This Wojtyłaan idea of **self-determination** means that through free choice, the person **determines himself to be a certain kind of person** (honest or dishonest, courageous or cowardly, etc.). It is an application of the Aristotelian-Thomistic notion that act follows being (*agere sequitur esse*), but Wojtyła casts it in the first-person perspective of the acting subject.³⁸

³⁴ Wojtyła highlights that: “*Self-governance* can also be expressed as a specific complexity: on the one hand, the person is the one who governs, who governs himself, and, on the other hand, he himself is the one whom he governs. We understand self-governance here as something different from what is indicated by the colloquial phrase ‘mastery over oneself.’” Wojtyła, “Person and Act,” 209.

³⁵ Wojtyła explains that: “*Self-possession* as a specific structural property of the person is revealed and at the same time confirmed in action through the will. The simple lived-experience ‘I will’ cannot be correctly read in the dynamic totality of man without considering that specific complexity in it, proper only to the person, contributed by self-possession. Self-determination is possible only on the basis of self-possession; every ‘I will’ is precisely such self-determination, not as the content of lived-experience isolated from the dynamic whole but as the content deeply rooted in this totality. ‘I will’ as actual self-determination structurally presupposes self-possession. For one can determine only what he really possesses. And only the one who possesses can determine. Man determines himself by the will because he possesses himself. At the same time, the will, every real ‘I will,’ confirms and realizes the self-possession proper only to the person—the fact that he is *sui iuris*.” *Ibid.*, 208.

³⁶ Self-Determination is the highest expression of Freedom. Wojtyła contends that “Freedom is identified with self-determination—with the self-determination in which we discover the will as a property of the person. Hence, freedom appears as the property of the person connected with the will, with the concrete ‘I will,’ which contains, as previously ascertained, the lived-experience ‘I can but do not have to.’ In the analysis of self-determination, we descend to the very roots of both this ‘I will’ and this ‘I can but do not have to.’ The freedom proper to man, the freedom of the person through the will, is identified with self-determination as the existential, fullest, and most fundamental reality.” *Ibid.*, 217.

³⁷ It is important to note what Grzegorz Hołub remarks on Wojtyła’s notion of efficacy. Hołub points out that for Wojtyła, “the subject’s efficacy is not a one- dimensional causation but an intentional coordination of various forces and powers, be they natural or non- natural ones. Thus, finally, we stand before a project that is between a traditional divide (realist vs. idealist philosophy), and it is therefore prone to criticism from both sides. At the same time, this type of conception provokes a philosophical discussion and that is why it is promising.” G. Hołub, *Understanding the Person: Essays on the Personalism of Karol Wojtyła* (Bern: Peter Lang, 2021), 146.

³⁸ One of the most indispensable value of “Self-determination” is that it separates the person from animals and emphasizes also his *uniqueness* and *irreducibility*. This has been explained accurately by Grzegorz Ignatik when he argues that “... animals lack not only the ability to determine their ‘I’ but also the ‘I’ itself. This lack is due to the absence of consciousness and the personal structures of self-possession and self-governance.” G. Ignatik, *Person*

From these considerations arises a picture of the person as a dynamic, self-directed whole. The classical “cosmological” definition is not negated but enriched: the person is an individual *who not only has a rational nature but owns and shapes this nature through conscious choices*. In Wojtyła’s terms, the person is a **subject**. By *subject* he does not mean an ephemeral stream of consciousness (as in some modern philosophies), but a being that exists in itself (*in se*) and can also *reflect upon itself*. Wojtyła was fond of the term “**incommunicable**”³⁹ to describe the person’s uniqueness: each person, being an *unrepeatable someone*, cannot be exchanged or substituted by any other. This notion echoes personalist thinkers like John Crosby, who stresses that the *unrepeatability* of each person is a fundamental source of dignity—one that “inserts [personal dignity] from the beginning within our common human nature”⁴⁰—without negating that common nature. Every human shares the same nature (and thus universal rights and value), yet each person bears that nature in a singular manner that is **theirs alone**. This incommunicability is precisely what is lost in both theomorphism (where individual persons might be seen as interchangeable instances of “the human as image of God”) and technomorphism (where persons are interchangeable units or functions). Wojtyła’s ontology insists on the unity of nature and person: *each person has the full shared human nature, but each person is much more than a mere instance of a category—each is a unique center of being and action*. This insight directly preserves the **irreducibility** of the person: no analysis into components (genes, neurons, social conditioning) can capture the person as person; nor can subsumption under a general idea (Man, or Image of God, or Citizen, etc.) exhaust the concrete reality of this *I* who acts and is aware of itself.

Another crucial aspect of Wojtyła’s personalism is the integration of the **body-soul composite (i.e. hylomorphism)**.⁴¹ Against any spiritualistic tendency of theomorphism that might

and Value: Karol Wojtyła’s Personalistic and Normative Theory of Man, Morality, and Love (Lanham: Lexington Books, 2021), 41.

³⁹ To be incommunicable means to be *accountable* in every *conscious action* insofar as no one can *will* for you except yourself. Every decision and choices can only be executed by the person himself. Of course, this excludes special moral circumstances. Acosta is correct in saying that “From the point of view of action, we can distinguish an aspect of nature that is common to every human being and, at the same time, another exceptional aspect, metaphysically incommunicable, in each individual that constitutes his own identity, his personal ‘I.’” M. Acosta and A.J. Reimers, *Karol Wojtyła’s Personalist Philosophy: Understanding Person and Act* (Washington, D.C.: The Catholic University of America Press, 2016), 117

⁴⁰ Crosby, *Personalist Papers*, 22.

⁴¹ It is clear that “Wojtyła was far from proposing that the human being should be segmented. He never adhered to a thesis that the human being is only a bodily creature or a spiritual self, nor merely a moral being or a rational creature. Following Aristotle, Wojtyła still perceived the human being as an animal rationale. This was interestingly demonstrated when he distinguished two approaches to the human being: a cosmological and a personal.” Hořub, *Understanding the Person: Essays on the Personalism of Karol Wojtyła*, 144.

downplay the body, and against any materialistic tendency of technomorphism that might treat the body as a mere biological mechanism, Wojtyła upholds the classical hylomorphic view (from Aristotle and Aquinas) that the human being is a substantial unity of body and soul. In his philosophical anthropology, he emphasizes the person's lived embodiment. We experience not only "I act," but also "*I feel*"—we have sensual, emotional, and bodily vitality, what Wojtyła calls the *somato-vegetative* and *psycho-emotive* dynamism of the self, which the Thomist tradition tends to overlook. These layers are not independent substances, but dimensions of the one personal being. Wojtyła introduces the idea of **integration**⁴² to describe how the rational and spiritual faculties (intellect and will) integrate the lower faculties (senses, emotions, instincts) into the unity of the acting person. A morally mature person is not one who suppresses or ignores his body, but one who harmonizes it under the guidance of reason and will toward genuinely good ends. Thus, neither the body nor the spirit is neglected: the person is essentially *someone incarnate*. This has profound implications for both extremes we discussed: it counters the technocratic inclination to treat the body as a mere object (for the body is inalienably mine—*my body*, suffused with personal meaning and subjectivity) and simultaneously counters any puritanical inclination to treat the body as a prison of the soul (for the body is genuinely part of the personal self, capable of being a vehicle of self-expression and gift). Indeed, in Wojtyła's later theological reflections (the *Theology of the Body*), he would say, "the body expresses the person."⁴³ Without straying into theology here, we can note how consistent this is with his philosophical foundation: the body is personal, not an extrinsic instrument.

From the integration of bodily and spiritual dimensions flows the concept of the **transcendence of the person in act**.⁴⁴ When the person freely chooses a good—especially

⁴² Aguas explains that, for Wojtyła, integration "... refers to the wholeness of the person which emerges from the complexity of the structure of the human person." J.J. Aguas, *Person, Action, and Love: The Philosophical Thoughts of Karol Wojtyła (John Paul II)* (Manila: UST Publishing House, 2014), 125. However, we must be cautious, since *disintegration* may happen to a person—that is, the lack of self-governance in cases such as the psychological alteration of reality—but he does not cease to possess the wholeness of the dignity of his personhood.

⁴³ K. Wojtyła (Pope John Paul II), *Man and Woman He Created Them: A Theology of the Body*, trans. by M. Waldstein (Boston: Pauline Books, 2006), 185 – (General Audience of Jan 16, 1980). John Paul II teaches that the human body, in its masculinity or femininity, "*expresses the person*" and manifests the spiritual and the divine image in the visible realm. This is a theological extension of the philosophical point that the body is personal. As he put it in an earlier audience (Nov 14, 1979), "The body, and it alone, is capable of making visible the invisible, the spiritual and the divine." This notion harmonizes with Wojtyła's philosophical integration of body and soul.

⁴⁴ Wojtyła identifies two kinds of transcendence: horizontal and vertical. Reimers illumines us in this specific point of Wojtyła. Reimers explains that "Horizontal transcendence is a response to value, as well as an effort to realize a value in a particular situation. Vertical transcendence, on the other hand, questions the value in terms of some standard of good, because the values as presented immediately in consciousness do not, of themselves, validate their

a moral good that is truly worthwhile—he or she experiences a *transcendence* of the self’s prior limitations. Wojtyła illustrates that, in a morally significant choice, the person not only affects the external world but also rises above the inertia of internal impulses or social pressures—*going out of oneself* toward value.⁴⁵ This is a kind of vertical transcendence: every free act affirms that the person’s identity is not bound by the momentary sum of desires or material conditions; rather, the person can *become more* through action. Here Wojtyła weds a classical notion of teleology (actions have an orientation toward ends, ultimately to the ultimate end which is God) with a phenomenological description of freedom. One perceives that true freedom is not arbitrariness but is deeply linked to truth and goodness: *to choose the good is simultaneously to fulfill oneself.*

own goodness.” A.J. Reimers, *Truth About the Good: Moral Norms in the Thought of John Paul II* (Ave Maria, FL: Sapientia Press, 2011), 99. Furthermore, I wish to add that there is a distinction between *transcendence* in the ontological sense (i.e., *unum, verum, bonum, pulchrum*) and *transcendence* in the moral sense (which Wojtyła speaks about). Now, *transcendence in the moral sense* must affirm the *transcendence in the ontological sense* through action. Thus, in this sense the person’s basis for “ought” must always be “is.”

⁴⁵ Wojtyła’s distinction between “values” and “good” represents a fundamental critique of modern axiology and a return to classical metaphysical realism grounded in the Aristotelian-Thomistic tradition. The good (*bonum*) possesses ontological primacy as it is convertible with being itself—“*bonum et ens sunt idem secundum rem*” (K. Wojtyła, “The Lublin Lectures,” in: Wojtyła, *The Lublin Lectures and Works on Max Scheler*, 108)—while values constitute the experiential and phenomenological dimension through which persons encounter and respond to goods in their lived-experience. This distinction is crucial for understanding Wojtyła’s rejection of Scheler’s purely emotionalistic axiology, which treats values as autonomous realities irreducible to being and truth. As Wojtyła argues, “the weakest point of the Schelerian system is the complete separation of value, the good, from truth” (*ibid.*, 154). For Wojtyła, the good is fundamentally teleological, serving as the proper object of the will in its natural orientation toward ends, whereas values function as mediating experiences that must be grounded in rational judgment about what truly constitutes the good for the acting person.

The ontological foundation of this distinction lies in Wojtyła’s understanding of the good as rooted in the existential structure of being itself. Following Thomas Aquinas, Wojtyła maintains that “the good is identified with being” but emphasizes that “the good is not only identified with being but also constitutes the end of all being” (*ibid.*, 105). This teleological dimension means that the good functions as the ultimate terminus of rational appetite, while values represent the experiential pathway through which persons discover and choose particular goods. The crucial mediating role belongs to truth and conscience: “The moment of truth is essential in the lived-experience of value. This is the truth about this or that object as this or that good” (Wojtyła, “Person and Act,” 244). This integration of truth with value-experience distinguishes Wojtyła’s position from both Kantian formalism and Schelerian emotivism, as it requires that authentic moral choice involve both the phenomenological recognition of values and the rational judgment of conscience about the true good.

The ethical implications of this distinction are profound for Wojtyła’s understanding of human action and moral development. Unlike Scheler’s “purely emotionalistic intuitionism [which] excludes the rational, efficacious, and creative contribution of the person in shaping the morality of acts” (Wojtyła, “The Lublin Lectures,” 154), Wojtyła insists that moral values emerge through the person’s self-determination in relation to the true good. The person achieves transcendence not merely through emotional value-intuition but through the integration of value-experience with truthful judgment: “Freedom contains dependence on truth, and this is manifested with full vividness in conscience. For the function of conscience consists in designating the true good in the act and, with this, in creating duty” (Wojtyła, “Person and Act,” 259). This means that while values provide the experiential content of moral consciousness, the good represents the objective reality that grounds moral obligation and enables authentic self-fulfillment. The person fulfills himself not simply through experiencing values but through choosing the true good in accordance with the judgment of conscience, thereby actualizing his transcendent capacity for self-determination in truth.

Conversely, to choose what is evil or false is to violate one's own personal reality—a self-determinative act that distorts. In Wojtyła's striking phrase, "man, who is the only creature on earth God willed for itself, cannot fully find himself except through a sincere gift of self,"⁴⁶ we see a phrase we encountered earlier as a corrective to theomorphism, but it also crowns his personalism: it signals that the person finds fulfillment (transcends self) through self-giving love. This insight masterfully mediates between extremes. Against technomorphism's self-centered utilitarianism, it insists that fulfillment is not in self-assertion or consumption but in self-donation—a concept utterly at odds with a worldview that measures everything by productivity or biological success. And against a distorted theomorphism, it clarifies that the way man relates to God (and reflects God) is precisely through the exercise of love in freedom, not by a negation of his own faculties. In fact, the statement from *Gaudium et Spes* is an example of "**deeper ontological retrieval**": the Council Fathers retrieved an ancient Christian truth (that man images a self-giving God) in personalist language that overcomes the static individualism-versus-collectivism binary. Wojtyła's philosophy undergirds that move by showing that self-gift is rooted in the structure of the person as self-determining and self-transcending.

Having sketched Wojtyła's personalist ontology, we can see more explicitly how it mediates between the earlier extremes and preserves the person's irreducibility. **First**, Wojtyła does justice to the *theomorphic* truth without reducing it. He agrees that man is oriented to God—indeed, he would affirm that the person is *capax Dei* (capable of communion with God) and that the ultimate fulfillment of self-gift is a participation in the divine life of love. But crucially, this orientation is not imposed extrinsically; it is built into our very being. The person's spiritual faculties (intellect, open to truth; will, open to good) are the "places" of this orientation. Thus, the relation to God is realized *through* the exercise of reason in seeking truth and of will in choosing good, not by bypassing them. We might say Wojtyła promotes a *rational theomorphism*: to be God-like is not to abandon one's humanity, but to fully actualize it in accord with truth and

⁴⁶ John Paul II frequently discussed technology in his social encyclicals. In *Redemptor Hominis* (1979), §§15–16, he cautions that technological advancement without an equivalent advancement in moral responsibility leads to fearsome outcomes: "This epoch of history ... with the aid of science and technology, has ... remarkable hopes ... and also exposed the human race to the threat of self-destruction ... The ultimate test of technology should be the respect due to the human person." Similarly, in *Centesimus Annus* (1991), §37, he warns against treating profit and technological progress as ends in themselves at the expense of the person: "In fact, the human person is the measure of the dignity of work ... Man remains above all a being who seeks the truth and strives to live in the truth." These magisterial teachings reflect Wojtyła's personalist principle that technology must be subordinated to human values, not vice versa.

love. This clearly rejects any fideistic devaluation of reason. Far from seeing faith and reason as opposed, Wojtyła argues (in line with Thomistic tradition) that truth is one and that all genuine paths to truth converge. In the preliminary reflection in *Fides et Ratio*, he wrote that faith purifies reason and reason purifies faith; the two are “like two wings on which the human spirit rises to the contemplation of truth.”⁴⁷ In personalist terms, the divine image in man—the *divinus in caro*—consists in the spiritual creature who can know and choose and thereby give himself in love. Wojtyła’s ontology thus validates the God-ward destiny of man, but only in tandem with the integrity of human nature. **Second**, Wojtyła absolutely refutes the *technomorphic* reduction by re-grounding all the phenomena that scientism misinterprets within a richer metaphysical frame. Where technomorphism sees only neurons firing, Wojtyła acknowledges neurons *along with* the conscious subject who uses and directs his physiological processes. Where technomorphism sees behavior conditioned by environment, Wojtyła points to the interior evaluation and decision that shape behavior from within. Importantly, Wojtyła’s view does not reject the findings of science—the body and its mechanisms are real, and the influences of biology and psychology are real—but it **integrates** them. As Hanby suggested, making the person the paradigm of analysis liberates us from having to treat the lower as the cause of the higher; instead, we can see the person as a *whole* in which material, biological, emotional, and rational aspects cooperate in a hierarchy. The personal soul is the form of the body, giving unity and direction. This means technology and science become *servants of the person* once again, instead of arbiters of his identity. Wojtyła often spoke of the proper place of technology: he lauded scientific progress for its benefits yet warned that, without a moral orientation toward the human good, technology could become a false idol or tyrant over man. In his encyclical *Redemptor Hominis*, he famously stated that scientific and technological progress, for all its advantages, carries the risk of a “radical and sudden turn ... against man” if not guided by ethical truth about the person.⁴⁸ Only if the person, as a moral subject, remains the **measure** of technology will technology truly serve humanity and not the other way around.

⁴⁷ John Paul II, preface to *Fides et Ratio* (1998).

⁴⁸ John Paul II, *Redemptor Hominis* (1979), §§15-16: “Man often seems to see no other meaning in his natural environment than what he can use and exploit ... We have to suspect that the growth of technology is not in itself enough to guarantee human happiness ... It is a question ... of the priority of ethics over technology, of the primacy of the person over things, of the superiority of spirit over matter.” Here, the Pope reiterates—in pastoral form—the philosophical point that persons are subjects and ends, and that the material world, including technology, must be ordered to personal and spiritual ends.

At this juncture, one can appreciate how Wojtyła mediates the opposition of theomorphism and technomorphism through what can be called a **sacramental anthropology**—“sacramental” in the philosophical (not strictly theological) sense that the human person, as a *body-spirit unity*, makes the divine present in the world of matter in a real, though analogous, way. The title of this paper, *Divinus in Caro* (“the divine in flesh”), alludes to the Christological mystery that ultimately grounds Christian personalism: the Incarnation of God. While Wojtyła’s own philosophical arguments do not presuppose Christian revelation, they are notably congenial to it. By safeguarding both the spiritual dignity and the bodily reality of the person, Wojtyła’s ontology provides a rational foundation for the belief that humans are destined to share in God’s life while remaining fully themselves. The **irreducibility of the person**—the notion that each person is a unique subject who cannot be replaced or summed up by any categories—finds its ultimate vindication in the perspective that each person is directly called by God to a fulfillment transcending the world. Yet that transcendent fulfillment—in Christian terms, the beatific vision, the communion of saints—is not a negation of our humanity but its crown. Even at the level of philosophy, Wojtyła shows that transcendence is not an add-on but an essential capacity of human action and existence. This is why neither theomorphism nor technomorphism has the final word: each miss that the **transcendent** (the Divine) and the **immanent** (the human, the material) are not competitors at the deepest level of reality. They interpenetrate in the person, properly understood. Wojtyła’s friend and collaborator, the theologian Ratzinger (later Pope Benedict XVI), expressed a similar idea by saying that the anthropological question and the God-question are inextricably linked—remove God, and the anthropology goes awry; remove a true humanism, and our understanding of God becomes distorted. Wojtyła’s personalism stands exactly at that intersection, mediating the two.

To bring these reflections to a focal point: in Wojtyła’s personalist ontology, **the person is a being that is at once grounded in himself and open to what lies beyond himself.** This “beyond” has a twofold reference: beyond the self toward others (community, love) and beyond the created order toward the Creator (transcendence, worship). Wojtyła recovers the classical *communio* dimension of personhood—that persons exist in relation—but he does so without sacrificing the subjectivity and freedom discovered by modern philosophy. In his vision, each person is *incommunicably unique* yet called to give himself in communion; each person is under God, yet God does not annihilate human freedom but guarantees it. Thus, personalism is

the true **mediating third way** after the collapse of the old dichotomies. It refuses to see the relationship between man and God as a zero-sum game (as some moderns caricature it), and it refuses to see the relationship between person and nature as a zero-sum game. Instead, it posits an ontological generosity in being: the human person—precisely by being more fully human (rational, free, loving)—comes more into the likeness of God; and the human person, by respecting his own embodied reality and the rest of creation, ennobles nature rather than despoiling it. We recall Hanby’s observation that Darwin himself noted how the presence of higher faculties in man “ennobled” the lower creatures by analogy—a point suggesting that the emergence of mind does not degrade matter but elevates its significance.⁴⁹ Wojtyła would concur that, in the person, matter itself is taken up into a new, personal meaning; hence, the human body is not just matter—it is the matrix of personal presence and action).

Wojtyła’s thought also provides practical ethical orientation. If the person is a self-determining, self-giving agent of intrinsic worth, then he or she must never be treated as a mere means to an end. This sounds like Kant’s categorical imperative, and indeed Wojtyła acknowledged the value of Kantian ethics in affirming the person as an end. But Wojtyła pushes further: not only should we *not use* persons, but we are called to **love** them. In one of his early works, *Love and Responsibility*, he stated, “It is rightly due to the person to be treated as an object of love, and not as an object of use.”⁵⁰ Love, in this sense, means affirming the other as having absolute value and committing oneself to that other’s good. Such a posture fulfills both the law of reason and the deepest yearning of the heart—it is where duty and happiness coincide. Under technomorphism, love tends to be instrumentalized or reduced to biochemical attraction; under misconceived theomorphism, love might be overshadowed by duty to an abstract principle. But under Wojtyła’s personalism, authentic love becomes the synthesis of the true and the good in personal relations, reflecting the very life of God. Love is the mode of personal communion that mirrors the Trinitarian communion (though that theological connection lies beyond the scope of philosophy proper). The upshot is that the **irreducible person** is also the *responsible* person:

⁴⁹ M. Hanby, *No God, No Science?*, 348.

⁵⁰ K. Wojtyła, *Love and Responsibility*, trans. by G. Ignatik (Boston, Pauline Books & Media, 2013), 26. Wojtyła states: “The person is a kind of good to which only love constitutes the proper and fully-mature relation” (*ibid.*, 25). This means that any use of a person (treating them as an object or means) is fundamentally incompatible with that person’s dignity. This ethical principle builds directly on his anthropology: since a person possesses self-determination and is an end in himself, the only appropriate way to relate to such a person is through self-giving love that honors his autonomy and worth. This principle synthesizes the insights of Kant (respect for persons) with the insights of Christian charity.

because each of us is a someone, each of us bears the responsibility to treat every other human being in accordance with their exalted status as *Divinus in caro*—and likewise to order our use of technology and our devotion to God in ways that honor, rather than efface, personal reality.

Wojtyła’s personalism *mediates* the extremes by retrieving the **ontological nucleus** that both extremes had lost. *Theomorphism* and *technomorphism*, despite appearances, are like mirror images—each in its own way divorces what must be united (the divine and the human, the subject and the object). Wojtyła reunites what is sundered through a deeper vision of *being-as-person*. In doing so, he does not oscillate between poles but regrounds the discussion at a level where the opposition is transcended. This is a classically metaphysical move: finding the more ample framework in which partial truths can be reconciled. The framework here is the act and being of the person. As David C. Schindler himself has argued in another context, any attempt to think being while excluding the mystery of personhood will end in contradictions, because personhood is the highest revelation of being’s interior richness.⁵¹ Wojtyła’s philosophy enshrines that insight. The person is *sui iuris et alteri partis*⁵²—master of himself and able to give himself—a paradoxical composite of autonomy and relation that reflects the very structure of reality better than any atomistic or monistic model. In Wojtyła’s metaphysical anthropology, we therefore find a powerful vindication of the **irreducibility of the human person**: irreducible to impersonal forces, irreducible to a mere exemplar of a genus, irreducible to anything but itself. Each person is a new locus of meaning and value in the cosmos, the meeting point of the finite and the infinite. In each person, in a certain sense, creation is recapitulated and open to transcendent fulfillment. This realization is what can save our culture from both the idolatry of techné and a reactionary sacralism—it gives us the true scale of the human being.

⁵¹ Hanby, *No God, No Science?*, 348–350. Hanby, drawing on D.C. Schindler, argues that modern ontology’s reduction of being to material history is untenable because it must tacitly employ the fuller notion of being (including form and intelligibility) even to describe history. In a footnote referencing D.C. Schindler, Hanby notes: “Transcendent form and identity are tacitly invoked even when they are denied; without them, history ceases to be intelligible at all.” (*Ibid.*, 349). He suggests that making the person (in Richard of St. Victor’s definition as “incommunicable existence of rational nature”) the paradigm of being is more adequate (*ibid.*, 348). This resonates with Wojtyła’s approach of understanding being through the lens of personal existence.

⁵² I am completely aware that Wojtyła uses the term “*alteri incommunicabilis*” in relation to Self-Determination. “If self-determination reveals that man is the object of his own subject, it thereby simultaneously manifests a particular complexity, which is proper to man as a person. St. Thomas, and with him the whole tradition of Christian thought, emphasizes that ‘*persona est sui iuris et alteri incommunicabilis*.’” K. Wojtyła, “Personal Structure of Self-Determination,” in: Wojtyła, *Person and Act and Related Essays*, 463. Furthermore, there is a difference between *ontological incommunicability* which is given at the very moment of creation of the person and *moral incommunicability* where the person *willfully* gives himself/herself to another person such as in Marriage. See K. Wojtyła, “On the Meaning of Spousal Love,” in: Wojtyła, *Love and Responsibility*.

Conclusion

Has philosophy reached its end as a meaningful endeavor, as some suspect in this age of specialization and polarization? If one follows the arc of our analysis—from theomorphism to technomorphism to their resolution in personalism—one finds a hopeful answer: the end of philosophy (its goal or purpose) is not to abolish mystery in favor of facile clarity but to lead us to a deeper contemplation of the mystery at the heart of reality—the mystery of the person. Karol Wojtyła’s unfolding of personalist ontology exemplifies this by taking the seemingly irreconcilable tensions of modern thought and showing that they are resolved in the higher unity of the truth about the person. **The irreducibility of the person**, which Wojtyła champions, is not a stubborn obstacle to understanding but rather the key to understanding everything else rightly. It ensures that neither God nor the world is misconstrued in our self-understanding: God is not the rival of human freedom but its ground and guarantor—though not *a la Descartes*⁵³—and the material world is not the master of man but the arena of his self-giving creativity under God’s providence. In Wojtyła’s philosophical vision, man rediscovers himself as *Divinus in caro*—a creature dust-born yet heaven-destined, immanent in nature yet transcendent in spirit.

The mediation achieved by Wojtyła’s personalism has profound implications. It guards human dignity in an era of biotechnological temptation, insisting that no enhancement or algorithm can ever replace the core of *who* a person is. It also enriches theological anthropology, suggesting that grace and nature, the divine and the human, meet in the person in a way that fulfills both without confusion—an insight traceable to the Chalcedonian principle that, in Christ, true God and true man, we discern the pattern for all divine-human interaction. In societal terms, Wojtyła’s vision challenges both the libertarian individualism that leaves persons isolated and the collectivist technocracy that subsumes persons into systems. It proposes instead a civilization of love and truth, in which each person is respected as a subject and encouraged to flourish through virtuous action and solidarity with others. Such a civilization would neither worship technology nor reject it but place it at the service of integral human development. It would neither impose a theocratic negation of reason nor embrace a secular negation of spirit but would cultivate the proper harmony of faith

⁵³ J. Collins, *God in Modern Philosophy* (Chicago, USA: Henry Regenery Company, 1959), 55-64.

and reason, recognizing that the human quest for meaning spans scientific discovery, philosophical wisdom, and religious insight.

In a nutshell, Wojtyła’s ontological personalism offers a compelling resolution to the anthropological crisis of our times by unveiling a more capacious understanding of being human. It is an understanding in which **efficacy** (man as an agent), **self-determination** (man as free), and **transcendence in act** (man as oriented beyond himself) are central categories—precisely those needed to counter the passivity of theomorphic reduction and the fragmentation of technomorphic reduction. What emerges is a portrait of the human person as a creature who, in all actions, stands at a crossroads of the material and the spiritual, time and eternity. Each person is a microcosm and a mediator of creation, capable of knowing the world and of knowing God, capable of shaping the world and of giving himself in love to God and neighbor. In the face of systems that would reduce this mystery—whether in the name of heaven or of earth—Wojtyła’s voice rings out in dense, challenging prose: the *person* is the fundamental category of reality to which all analysis must finally refer. To forget this is to lose our way; to remember it is to open the door to genuine wisdom.

To conclude, the irreducible person—the *acting person*, in Wojtyła’s thoughts—stands as the answer to the riddle posed by the extremes of theomorphism and technomorphism. Wojtyła mediates these extremes not by splitting the difference but by ascending to the source: the ontological structure of personhood itself, which images divine freedom in creaturely form. His philosophy exemplifies the dictum that truth is often “spherical” rather than flat—one must move to a higher dimension to see how apparent contraries unite. By developing a four-part dialectic that led us from problem to deeper problem to solution, and fittingly, we find that the “end of philosophy”—understood not as a termination but as a goal—is the contemplation of the person as the incarnation of the divine, *Divinus in Caro*. In every human person, an entire universe is in communion with the Creator; and in light of that metaphysical truth, all attempts to reduce the person to something less must be firmly rejected. The final word must be one of affirmation: **Yes, the human person truly is a mystery, irreducible and invaluable, the bearer of a divine likeness in the midst of a technological age.** To recognize this is to ensure that neither the promises of technocracy nor the fervor of theocracy will lead us astray from authentic personalism. It is to secure the inviolable core of what and who we are—beings made of earth, yet breathing the breath of God. And this simultaneously allows us to avoid repeating the error of

Descartes, who, according to John Paul II, is “The philosopher who formulated the principle of ‘*Cogito, ergo sum*’, ‘I think, therefore I am’, [and] also gave the modern concept of man its distinctive dualistic character, [which, in effect] makes a radical contrast in man between spirit and body, between body and spirit. But man is a person in the unity of his body and his spirit. The body can never be reduced to mere matter: it is a *spiritualized body*, just as man's spirit is so closely united to the body that he can be described as *an embodied spirit*. The richest source for knowledge of the body is the Word made flesh.”⁵⁴

⁵⁴ John Paul II, *Letter to Families* (1994), §2.

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